

Health effects of transportation noise for children and adolescents: an umbrella review and burden of disease estimation

Authors:

Nicole Engelmann (Swiss TPH), Xing Jiang (Swiss TPH), Núria Blanes Guàrdia (Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona), Danielle Vienneau (Swiss TPH), Martin Rösli (Swiss TPH)

Cover design: EEA

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Layout: EEA / ETC HE (European Topic Centre on Human Health and the Environment.)

Publication Date: 19 February 2025

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14892796

Version: 1

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How to cite this report:

Engelmann N., Jiang X., Blanes Guàrdia N., Vienneau D., & Röösl M. (2025). *Health effects of transportation noise for children and adolescents: an umbrella review and burden of disease estimation*. (Eionet Report – ETC HE 2024/11). European Topic Centre on Human Health and the Environment.

The report is available from <https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/all-etc-reports> and <https://zenodo.org/communities/eea-etc/?page=1&size=20>.

ETC HE coordinator: Stiftelsen NILU, Kjeller, Norway (<https://www.nilu.com/>)

ETC HE consortium partners: Federal Environment Agency/Umweltbundesamt (UBA), Aether Limited, Czech Hydrometeorological Institute (CHMI), Institut National de l'Environnement Industriel et des Risques (INERIS), Swiss Tropical and Public Health Institute (Swiss TPH), Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB), Vlaamse Instelling voor Technologisch Onderzoek (VITO), 4sfera Innova S.L.U., klarFAKTe.U

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Acknowledgements

The ETC task manager was Eulalia Peris and Gerardo Sanchez (institution). Many thanks for helpful comments and inspiring discussion. We thank a lot to our reviewers of an earlier version of this report: Jurgen Buekers (VITO), Sarah Kienzler (UBA), Dietrich Plass (UBA).

Summary

Exposure to noise from transport sources, in particular road traffic noise, is a major environmental problem in Europe. Over 20% of the EU's population live in areas where traffic noise levels exceeds 55 dB L_{DEN} . This implies that approximately 14 million children aged 6-17 in Europe (including Iceland, Norway and Switzerland) are exposed to these transport noise levels of 55dB or higher. Transportation noise may affect the development of children and adolescents.

The aim of this report is to characterize the health risks of environmental noise exposure at school and home to children and adolescents; to derive state of the art exposure-response functions (ERFs) for established health relevant effects; to estimate the burden of environmental noise on selected health outcomes and to review noise intervention studies in children and adolescents.

The literature review consists of a scoping and an Umbrella+ review. From the scoping review, adverse birth outcomes, behavioural problems, blood pressure, cognitive outcomes and weight related outcomes are selected as priority outcome for the Umbrella+ review. In the Umbrella+ review the newest systematic reviews of high quality is combined with additional high-quality original studies published after the selected high quality systematic reviews. Certainty of evidence of exposure-outcome pairs is rated using the same criteria as in the *Environmental Noise Guidelines for the European Region* (WHO ENG) (WHO Europe, 2018) with ratings of *high*, *moderate*, *low* and *very low*. Outcomes with high or moderate certainty of evidence with at least one transportation noise source are selected for a burden of disease assessment.

For reading and oral comprehension, behavioural problems and overweight moderate certainty of evidence for an association with one transportation noise source is found. For behavioural problems and overweight an ERF is derived from the literature using a meta-analysis. Corresponding pooled relative risks are 1.073 (95%-CI: 1.009, 1.142) and 1.063 (95%-CI: 1.007, 1.122) per 10 dB increase in L_{DEN} with an effect threshold of 45 dB. For reading and oral comprehension, we chose the same relationship previously used in the Noise in Europe Report by the EEA (2020) with an effect threshold of 50 dB (L_{den}).

The environmental burden of disease is calculated for three scenarios: i) using a quantification threshold of $L_{DEN}=55$ dB in line with the reporting threshold of Environmental Noise Directive (END); ii) using the WHO guidelines as a quantification threshold; and iii) using the identified effect threshold of 45 or 50 dB, respectively.

For all three scenarios, noise exposure is assessed at the place of residence using data reported for 2021. Baseline disability adjusted life years (DALYs) for attention deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) and conduct disorders are derived from Global Burden of Disease for the assessment of behavioural problems attributed to noise. For reading and oral comprehension the ERF provides directly the number of affected children, which was multiplied with a disability weight of 0.013 to calculate DALYs. For overweight, prevalence data are from the Global Health Observatory data. In the absence of disability weight for this outcome, only number of attributable children are calculated.

Using a quantification threshold $L_{DEN}=55$ dB yields about 564,000 children with reading difficulties, 63,000 children with behavioral problems and 272,000 children with overweight attributable to transportation noise exposure in Europe. Most noise-related impacts stem from road traffic, particularly in urban areas, where noise levels often exceed regulatory limits. For the other two scenarios the estimated burden is somewhat (WHO guidelines) or substantially (effect threshold) higher.

Table S-1 Number of children and adolescents (6-17 years) with behavioural problems, reading impairments and overweight attributable to transportation noise above the END threshold (55 dB) in 2021, EEA-31

		Behavioural problems	Reading and oral Comprehension	Overweight
Inside urban areas	Road	42,000	356,000	174,000
	Rail	5,000	42,000	20,000
	Air	500	6,000	2,000
Outside urban areas	Road	11,000	117,000	49,000
	Rail	5,000	41,000	26,000
	Air	200	3,000	1,000
Total		63,000	564,000	272,000

For the literature review on intervention studies, we used the classification developed for the Environmental Noise Guidelines for the European Region with the following five types of interventions.

1. Type A: reduction of noise at the source (e.g. speed limits, low noise tyres)
2. Type B: reduce noise propagation (e.g. barriers and insulation)
3. Type C: changes in infrastructure (e.g. closure of an airport)
4. Type D: modify the environment in general (e.g. change soundscape, greenness)
5. Type E: education and communication Interventions (change of behaviour or coping strategies of people).

We only identified five papers in children addressing noise interventions in children. Two papers described beneficial effects from an airport relocation on the cognitive performance and blood pressure. Two papers found increased noise awareness in children and high school students after education interventions and one study observed that classroom acoustic improvements yielded to better concentrations and less fatigue in primary school children as addressed by the teacher.

In conclusion, gaps in noise mapping and research implies that the full burden of noise for children and adolescent may be underestimated. Children and adolescents are a particularly vulnerable population. Impaired development during childhood and adolescence may have long lasting consequences into adulthood and contribute to inequality in the society, since noise exposure is most prevalent among disadvantaged populations. Given the substantial burden from transportation noise, interventions to minimize the health impact of noise are warranted. Most effective are upstream measures aimed at reducing noise at source such as lowering speed limits, reducing motor and tyre noise, and targeting high-emission noise sources.

1 Introduction

1.1 Background

Sound is part of our life and an important factor in evolution as a means for communication, orientation and warning signal. Our organism is capable of generating sound as well as perceiving and processing it. This is in contrast to many other hazards, some of which we are unable to perceive. Sound perception is mediated by subjective factors, attitudes and context, which also determines whether it is wanted or unwanted. Unwanted and/or harmful sound is defined as noise (Fink, 2019).

Sound refers to the air pressure fluctuations recorded by a measuring device. Sound pressure levels are expressed in decibel scale (dB) and refers to the logarithm of the measured air pressure fluctuation with the air pressure level at the hearing threshold. A doubling of the sound intensity (e.g. doubling of traffic) corresponds to an increase in the sound pressure level of 3 dB. Ten identical sound sources increase the sound pressure level by 10 dB. Such an increase in the sound pressure level is perceived by humans as an approximate doubling of the subjectively perceived volume. As people do not perceive all frequencies with the same intensity, an additional filter is used in sound level meters to simulate the frequency dependent sensitivity of the human ear. These A-weighted sound levels [in dB(A)] are used in environmental research and noise legislations and also in this report, even if not specifically expressed. Common averaging periods for sound pressure levels are 24 hours ($L_{Aeq,24h}$), 16 hours for the daytime (L_{DAY} or $L_{Aeq,16h}$) or 8 hours for the night-time (L_{NIGHT} or $L_{Aeq,8h}$). The time-weighted noise indicator L_{DEN} is also frequently used. DEN stands for a day-evening-night weighting, in which evening noise (18:00-22:00 or 19:00-23:00) receives an additional 5 dB and night-time noise (22:00-6:00 or 23:00-7:00) an additional 10 dB.

To protect from health effects of chronic noise exposure, the World Health Organization (WHO) published the *Environmental Noise Guidelines for the European Region* (WHO ENG) (WHO Europe, 2018). According to these, a guideline value of 40-45 dB is recommended for road, railway or aircraft noise at night, and a guideline value of 45-54 dB is provided for L_{DEN} . The WHO guideline values are not legally binding for the member states. For this reason, the Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council on the assessment and management of environmental noise [Directive 2002/49/EC] (END) continues to apply in the EU. END does not set any source-specific limit values at the EU level, thus leaving it to Member States to establish binding national limit values if they wish so. But END requires the Member States to report data to the Commission only from 55 dB L_{DEN} and 50 dB L_{NIGHT} . Its aim is to prevent, avoid or minimise the harmful effects of environmental noise.

The most significant source of environmental noise in Europe is transportation noise, in particular road traffic noise (EEA, 2020). According to estimates from the European Environment Agency based on data from 2017 (EEA, 2020), a total of 113 million people in Europe (including EU-27, UK, NO, CH and IS) were regularly exposed to road traffic noise of $L_{DEN} = 55$ dB or more, 22 million people have to tolerate corresponding rail traffic noise and 4 million people aircraft noise. There are also many other sources, such as industrial plants, construction sites, military operations and wind turbine. Some of these sources are less prevalent and thus fewer people are exposed to them. As a consequence, health risk research related to these sources is scarce, in particular in relation to rare diseases. Other sources like neighbourhood noise are relatively prevalent but difficult to model and predict for large study populations, which also prevents research on rare diseases.

1.2 Noise and Health in Children and Adolescents

1.2.1 Hearing Loss

Young children can hear frequencies up to 20,000 Hz. Children's ears are particularly sensitive to damage from noise. High level of sound results in permanent hearing damage. Depending on the exposure duration, such effects may occur above 70 dB and thus the WHO guidelines recommends that yearly average from all leisure noise sources combined should not exceed this value (WHO Europe, 2018). To derive exposure limits for other time averages, the equal energy principle can be used. The equal energy principle states that the total effect of sound is proportional to the total amount of sound energy received by the ear, irrespective of the distribution of that energy in time (WHO, 1999). As an example this translates for occupational exposure to 85 dB. Such high sound exposure damages the hair cells in the inner ear. The hearing can recover from short-term overloads in quiet phases. However, a complete loss of sensory cells is irreversible. Noise-induced hearing loss manifests particularly in the range around 4 kHz, which is the most sensitive for the healthy ear (this affects the understanding of speech, especially sibilants). While acute hearing damage is usually noticed immediately (e.g. sudden hearing loss, tinnitus, hearing loss, dull hearing impression), the slowly developing hearing damage caused by long-term exposure to noise is hardly noticed at first. Young people in particular therefore often underestimate the health risks posed, for example, by loud music.

Whereas for adults, workplace is a common reason for hearing loss (Lie et al., 2016), for children and adolescent the causes of hearing damage can be primarily found in leisure activities. Critical is thereby listening of loud music, which may include live music and discos, but also the use of headphones from personal music players and mobile phone. Additional critical sources are near explosions of fireworks and the sound of loud toys or machines. General Product Safety Directive (2001/95/EC) mandates that manufacturers ensure products do not pose risks to consumer health. For headphones, this includes mitigating risks associated with prolonged exposure to high sound levels. According to the EN 50332 standard, personal music players and headphones sold in the EU must have a default volume limit of 85 dB. A systematic review of research published between 1990 and 2015 found based on 23 observational studies that prevalence of hearing impairment (>15 dB hearing level) was about 10% among children, adolescents and young adults (<23 years) (Le Clercq et al., 2016). Up to 69% of the analysed participants reported to have experienced hearing-related symptoms after exposure to music, which most often was tinnitus, but also the feeling of pain or pressure in the ears and perceived hearing difficulties were regularly reported. Tinnitus was experienced on average by ca. 40% of the participants. In six out of seven experimental studies observed temporary threshold shifts after exposure to music. In conclusion, these data suggest an association between music exposure and hearing loss in children. The relevance of hearing for a healthy development, was confirmed in another review. Children with hearing loss have a twofold risk of experiencing psychosocial difficulties compared to normal hearing peers (De Jong et al., 2024). Since research on hearing impairment in children and adolescent from environmental noise sources is virtually inexistent and leisure activities are suspected to be the main reason, this report does not consider these health effects despite its high public health relevance. The focus of this review is on so-called extra-aural health effects of noise that is independent of ear damages as described in following chapter 1.2.2.

1.2.2 Extra-Aural Health Effects of Noise in Children and Adolescents

After sound enters the ear, it is processed in the brain stem, where an immediate response is induced in the event of loud, surprising noises (reflex). The limbic system, including the amygdala, is also involved, which explains why sounds can cause strong positive or negative emotions (Sørensen et al., 2024). Unwanted sound thus leads to a stress response, which puts the body into flight or fight mode (Figure 1). Physiologically, stress reactions lead to an excitation of the autonomic nervous system and thus to a rise in blood pressure and an increase in pulse rate. In addition, the hypothalamic-pituitary-

adrenal axis is activated, resulting in the release of stress hormones such as catecholamines and glucocorticoids as well as blood sugar and other energy suppliers. These reactions cause oxidative stress and inflammatory reactions. In addition, perceived stress from noise results in behavioural and emotional responses such as aggression, anxiety, feeling helpless and may also affect sleep behaviour. These cumulative stress from noise on mental and physical health increased the allostatic load (McEwen, 2006), which finally may result in the development of a disease (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Overview on proposed noise effects mechanism for children adapted from (Babisch, 2002; McEwen, 2006)

Most research on the extra-aural health effects of noise has been conducted in adults. It is likely that the stress response of children and adolescents from noise may be different compared to adults. Further, the metabolism of children differs from that of adults, and they are still in development (Castro et al., 2022). Thus, effects from noise in children are expected to be different than observed effects in adults. To better understand how noise affects children’s health and their development is central to sustainable living and to the prevention of illness.

One of the first large noise studies on children was a cross-sectional study of 2,844 children attending schools around three major airports in the Netherlands, Spain and United Kingdom (Stansfeld et al.,

2005). In this study significant impairment of reading comprehension and recognition memory as well as an association with annoyance was observed. Various hypotheses have been postulated how noise could affect children's health and in particular their cognitive performance and/or behaviour in addition to the above-described stress response. For example, the experience of being powerless against the noise exposure could induce resignation, demotivation and other behavioural problems, which can ultimately affect learning performance. Similarly, a loss of motivation due to noise could lead to a reduced performance of the teacher. Quite trivially, traffic noise or the overflights of aeroplanes could also affect the teacher's intelligibility in the classroom leading to repeated interruptions, the need for repeated instruction and inefficient teaching. Noise at home could affect the sleep of children, thereby impairing memory consolidation. In a Swiss cohort study, for example, the development of cognitive performance and hyperactivity/inattention symptoms in relation to noise was more pronounced in children whose bedroom faced a major road (Tangermann et al., 2022, 2023). To address these hypotheses, noise studies in children that address both exposure settings noise at school and noise at home, are of particular interest.

2 Objectives

This report focuses on the health effects of noise on children and adolescents and will build upon the previous work reviewing the environmental health risks in children and adolescents, specifically related to indoor and ambient air pollution (Castro et al., 2022), chemicals (Bessemers et al., 2023), and climate change (Graber et al., 2024).

These are the objectives of this report:

1. A characterization of the health risks to children and adolescents from environmental noise exposure at school and home.
2. Propose state of the art exposure-response functions (ERFs) for established effects in children and adolescents.
3. Estimate the burden of environmental noise on selected health outcomes in children and adolescents.
4. Review noise intervention studies in children and adolescents.

Altogether, this report will contribute to the evidence on environmental risk factors for children and adolescents in Europe.

3 PART I: Evaluation of the Scientific Evidence on the Effect of Environmental Noise on the Health of Children and Adolescents

3.1 Method of Literature Review

To compile the most recent evidence, we used an Umbrella+ review to first identify the newest systematic reviews of high quality and additional high-quality original studies published after the selected high quality systematic reviews.

3.1.1 Scoping and Prioritizing

The identification of relevant health outcomes for children's and adolescent's health was based on a literature search conducted in 2023 (Engelmann et al., 2023), complemented with a literature search for additional health outcomes and expert knowledge.

Within this scoping exercise the following health effects were selected as priority outcomes: adverse birth outcomes, behavioural problems, blood pressure, cognition including reading comprehension and obesity, summarized in Chapter 3.2.1 to Chapter 3.2.5. We found little research in children or adolescents on the effects of noise on cancer, respiratory disorders, mental health, sleep disturbance and annoyance. These studies are thus summarized in Chapter 3.2.6 (other outcomes). Outcomes that are primarily prevalent in adults or elderly (e.g. dementia, ischaemic heart disease, myocardial infarction, and stroke) are not evaluated for children or adolescents.

3.1.2 Study Eligibility

We used the PECOS approach by Morgan et al. (2018) to define inclusion and exclusion criteria for each element (population, exposures, comparators, outcomes and study design). We included reviews that conducted a systematic search with clear search terms, and meta-analyses as well as original studies analysing at least one exposure-outcome combination in children and/or adolescents in Europe. Exposures of interests are the transportation noise sources road traffic, railway and aircraft. Outcomes of interest includes adverse birth outcomes, behavioural problems, blood pressure, cognition and obesity, as well as annoyance, sleep disturbance, mental health, respiratory disorders and cancer. We also included original studies published after the most recent eligible systematic reviews. To be eligible, original studies needed to apply a cohort or case-control design for incidence diseases like adverse birth outcomes. For prevalent health outcomes, which may be reversible, such as changes in blood pressure, body weight, cognition, and behavioural problems, we also considered cross-sectional studies, if they were population based. All original studies had to apply established methods for outcome and exposure assessment and to adjust for the most relevant confounding factors in their analysis. Further, we only included literature written in the English language and published after the search period of the 2018 *Environmental Noise Guidelines for the European Region* by the WHO. The inclusion and exclusion criteria are shown in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1 Criteria for inclusion and exclusion of literature based on population, exposure, comparator, outcome, and study design

PECOS	Inclusion	Exclusion
Population	Children and adolescents (i.e., individuals under 18 years of age) in Europe	General human population, adults, non-human populations (in vivo, in vitro, other)
Exposure	Transportation noise exposure from road traffic, railways, and aircraft at school and at home	Occupational, leisure or industrial noise studies or studies with noise annoyance as exposure metric
Comparator	Different levels of noise noise exposure (i.e., sound pressure level) as measured in decibel.	
Outcome	Adverse birth outcomes (preterm birth, low birth weight, birth defects), cardiovascular outcomes (blood pressure), metabolic diseases (obesity, changes in body mass index, changes in waist circumference), behavioural problems (aggression, hyperactivity), cognitive impairment (reading and oral comprehension), annoyance, sleep disturbance, mental health, respiratory disorders, cancer	Health outcomes with primarily prevalence in adults or elderly, outcomes of unclear clinical health relevance, e.g., epigenetics, DNA methylation
Study type	<p>Key reports, systematic reviews with and without meta-analysis or major pooled analyses representative for Europe.</p> <p>Umbrella reviews, scoping reviews, and burden of disease studies.</p> <p>Reviews that are published (or accepted for publication i.e., in press) between 1 January 2015 and 5 March 2024 and written in English.</p> <p>In case of insufficient evidence from systematic reviews, original studies of high quality not included in a review might be included.</p>	<p>Narrative reviews, qualitative studies, studies reporting only unadjusted results, studies with clear evidence of an analytical error, and studies using noise annoyance as a surrogate for noise exposure or no assessment of noise exposure.</p> <p>Intervention studies, controlled exposure studies as well as studies with focus on exposure only.</p> <p>Grey literature, notes, editorials, letters and unpublished data.</p>

3.1.3 Literature Search

We searched PubMed to identify peer-reviewed reviews, meta-analyses and key reports as well as peer-reviewed original studies investigating the association between transportation noise and at least one health outcome selected during scoping and prioritization. Keywords and search terms used for the search included terms like “road traffic noise”, “railway noise”, “aircraft noise” and “transportation noise” for the exposure and “preterm birth”, “behaviour”, “blood pressure”, “Cogniti*”, and “overweight” for health outcomes. A detailed list of the search terms are shown in Table 8.1 in Annex 1. Since the first search conducted in 2023 studied the general population and a broader range of health outcomes, the search terms used for this review were not as specific. However, in the process of title

and abstract screening as well as full-text review, we applied the eligibility criteria and therefore excluded studies not fulfilling these criteria, e.g. studies only assessing an adult population.

The literature search consisted of two stages. The first search, which included the health outcomes behavioural problems, cardiovascular outcomes, cognition, mental health and obesity, was conducted in July 2023 for the 2023 report (Engelmann et al., 2023) while a second search was conducted in March 2024. The second search was an update on the first search to: a) identify the newest evidence, and b) capture additional health outcomes including adverse birth outcomes, annoyance, sleep disturbance, respiratory disorders and cancer. Thus, for each selected health outcome the search period was from 1 January 2015 to 5 March 2024.

In addition to searching PubMed, reference lists of identified articles and high-level reports from international environmental and health authorities including the WHO, European Environment Agency (EEA), and the European Environment Information and Observation Network (EIONET) were used to identify further eligible studies. The results of the literature search were presented in PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses) flow diagrams (Page et al., 2021).

3.1.4 Data Extraction

Data were extracted for reviews and original studies fulfilling the eligibility criteria. The extraction was conducted by one researcher (NE) and subsequently checked by two other researchers (DV, MR). The following information were extracted for eligible reviews: first author, year of publication, journal, search period, considered health outcomes and noise sources, included populations, tools used to assess the quality of each study and the evidence rating for each health outcome, the number of studies identified, a summary of locations for included studies, the minimum and maximum sample size, and the pooled relative risk (RR) estimates if a meta-analysis was conducted. Further, extracted information for eligible original studies included first author, year of publication, journal, location and cohort, follow-up period, sex, age, outcomes, number of participants, main noise sources including type (modelled, measured), metric, effect estimates and increment, and adjustment for other exposures (noise and air pollution).

3.1.5 Quality Assessment Criteria for Reviews

As described in the 2023 report (Engelmann et al., 2023), we evaluated the quality of selected systematic reviews using criteria inspired by AMSTAR 2 (A Measurement Tool to Assess Systematic Reviews) (Shea et al., 2017). The focus was on the three areas literature search, risk of bias assessment, and methodology for meta-analysis. A detailed description of the criteria can be found in Table 3.2. For the derivation of the exposure-response functions, we only considered reviews fulfilling all criteria.

Table 3.2 Criteria for quality assessment for reviews (Engelmann et al., 2023)

Literature search
a) At least one relevant database (PubMed/Medline, Scopus/Embase) was considered in the literature search.
b) The author clearly and adequately defined the search terms or keywords. Thus, they are representative of the exposure as well as the health outcome considered in the review. If further inclusion criteria were defined, e.g. for the population or study design, these should also be included in the search terms.
c) The author adequately defined and explained the inclusion and exclusion criteria for all key PECOS elements, but at least for exposure and health outcome.
d) There were no critical studies missing (to our knowledge).

Risk of bias assessment
e) A risk of bias assessment was conducted using an adequate tool with adequate criteria e.g. ROBINS-E, Newcastle Ottawa Scale, or checklist of WHO.
f) If the review authors identified a risk of bias in individual studies, adequate action was taken in the review and meta-analysis. These include, for instance, conducting a sensitivity analysis, considering the risk of bias assessment in the evidence rating, or stratification of the forest plot.

Methodology of meta-analysis
g) The data extraction was adequately performed and appropriate transformation methods were used to ensure the comparability of the data between studies. Hence, the correct risk estimates were extracted, the exposure metric was coherent between studies, the same increment was used, and the conversion of categorical estimates to linear estimates was performed using a reasonable method.
h) The data pooling was done in an appropriate way, e.g. separately for noise metric or with appropriate conversions into a single noise measurement or if necessary, separately for different population groups or geographical areas, and no cohort was included twice in the meta-analysis.
i) The authors used an adequate statistical method for the meta-analysis, e.g. a random effect model.

3.1.6 Certainty of Evidence

For each exposure-outcome pair we rated the certainty of evidence including the newest review of high quality and the additionally identified original studies of high quality published after the selected review. If the selected review included an evidence rating, we transferred the rating to the WHO ENG classification terminology, which was based on the GRADE (Grading of Recommendations, Assessment, Development and Evaluations) approach (Morgan et al., 2016; Guyatt et al., 2008). If no rating was available or additional studies were identified, we rated the evidence using the same criteria as in the WHO ENG with ratings of *high*, *moderate*, *low* and *very low*. The certainty of evidence of an exposure-outcome pair was rated as *high* if at least two cohort studies were identified that showed a low risk of bias and an increased risk of the corresponding association. If only one high-quality cohort study was found, the certainty of evidence was rated as *moderate*. For the 'environmental burden of disease' (EBD) assessment, we considered health outcomes with a *high* or *moderate* quality of evidence rating as critical.

3.1.7 Deriving Exposure-Response Functions

For each selected exposure-outcomes pair we conducted a separate meta-analysis to derive the relative risk per 10 dB L_{DEN} increase (i.e. providing source-specific exposure-response functions).

Further, we conducted a pooled meta-analysis across exposure sources to obtain an estimate for transportation noise for each health outcome separately. To do so, we used random effect meta-analysis weighted according to the inverse variance of the effect estimates. As starting points we either used the WHO ENG or the selected more recent review; and added the estimates from the selected original studies. The meta-analyses were conducted using the following measures:

- If a study population was included in multiple selected studies, the most recent and/or the most comprehensive analysis was included in the meta-analysis.
- If estimates were reported in noise metrics other than L_{DEN} , they were converted to L_{DEN} using the approach by Brink et al. (2018).
- If categorical noise exposure measures were reported, the estimates were converted to continuous measures by using random meta-analysis with weighting according to the inverse variance of the effect estimates (weight for reference category: estimated from distribution of sample size across all noise categories).
- If continuous and dichotomous outcome measures were reported in different studies for the same health outcome, the effect estimates of the continuous outcome measures were converted to odds ratios (OR, dichotomous outcome measures) following the method described by Hasselblad and Hedges (1995) and Chinn (2000).

3.2 Results of Literature Review

3.2.1 Adverse Birth Outcomes

The literature search resulted in 83 records, of which 71 were excluded after title and abstract screening. The full-text review of the remaining six reviews and six studies resulted in a further exclusion of two reviews (Vincens and Persson Waye, 2023; Stansfeld and Clark, 2015), which were not systematic reviews. Therefore, four reviews (Lee et al., 2023; Clark et al., 2020; Dzhambov and Lercher, 2019; Nieuwenhuijsen et al., 2017) and six original studies (Graafland et al., 2023; Wallas et al., 2019; Nieuwenhuijsen et al., 2019; Dzhambov et al., 2019; Pedersen et al., 2017; Hjortebjerg et al., 2016a) were selected for further consideration. The PRISMA-flow diagram is shown in Figure 9.1 of Annex 2. The characteristics of the reviews and their quality assessment are shown in Table 3.3 and Table 3.4, respectively. For adverse birth outcomes, noise exposure refers to maternal noise exposure during pregnancy at home.

The WHO ENG review addressing adverse birth outcomes (Nieuwenhuijsen et al., 2017) found evidence for an association between aircraft noise and preterm birth, low birth weight, and congenital anomalies as well as between road traffic noise and preterm birth, low birth weight, and small for gestational age (SGA). The quality of evidence for all adverse birth outcomes, however, was rated as *low* for road traffic noise and *very low* for aircraft noise.

Table 3.3 Characteristics of the identified reviews investigating the effect of transportation noise on incidence of adverse birth outcomes

Review	Outcome ^a	Noise Source	End of search period	Studies			Individual study quality ^c	Evidence rating ^d	Effect estimates (95% confidence interval) ^e
				No	N	Countries ^b			
Lee (2023)	Preterm birth	Road, Rail	July 2022	1	1,506	FR	-	-	-
Clark (2020)	Congenital anomalies, Low birth weight, SGA, Preterm birth	Road, Rail	Mar 2019	7	1,091 - 540,365	DK, KR, UK, AT, IT, SE	WHO	GRADE	-
Dzhambov and Lercher (2019)	Birth weight, Low birth weight, SGA, Preterm birth	Road	May 2019 (WHO Review as baseline)	9	518 - 540,365	AT, LT, ES, FR, UK, SE, IT, DE, DK, GR, CA, NO	WHO	GRADE	<i>Road at residence:</i> Birthweight (g): -8.26 (-20.61, 4.10) [£] Low birthweight: 1.06 (0.91, 1.23) [§] SGA: 1.02 (0.86, 1.21) [§] Preterm birth: 1.00 (0.79, 1.27) [§]
Nieuwenhuijsen (2017)	Congenital anomalies, Low birth weight, SGA, Preterm birth	Road, Air, Ambient (likely traffic noise)	Dec 2016	14	115 - 298,705	JP, NL, USA, TW, CA, DK, ES	NOS	GRADE	-

^a SGA = Small for gestational age

^b AT = Austria, CA = Canada, DE = Germany, DK = Denmark, ES = Spain, FR = France, GR = Greece, IT = Italy, JP = Japan, KR = South Korea, LT = Lithuania, NL = Netherlands, NO = Norway, SE = Sweden, TW = Taiwan, UK = United Kingdom, USA = United States of America

^c NOS = Newcastle-Ottawa Scale, WHO = WHO checklist

^d GRADE = Grading of Recommendations Assessment, Development and Evaluation

^e If not otherwise indicated, effect estimate refers to a 10 dB increase in noise levels.

[§] Odds Ratio

[£] Beta

Abbreviations: No = Number of papers, N = Number of participants

Table 3.4 Quality assessment of the reviews investigating the effect of transportation noise on incidence of adverse birth outcomes

Review	Literature search				Risk of Bias		Methodology for meta-analysis			Comment	Selected for outcome ^j
	a	b	c	d	e	f	g	h	i		
Lee (2023)	✓	✓	✓	X	X	X	X	X	X	No meta-analysis conducted	-
Clark (2020)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	X	X	No meta-analysis conducted	-
Dzhambov and Lercher (2019)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		Preterm birth, SGA, low birth weight, birth weight
Nieuwenhuijsen (2017)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	X	X	No meta-analysis conducted	-

- ^a Relevant data base considered
- ^b Clearly and adequately defined search terms/keywords
- ^c Inclusion/exclusion criteria adequately defined and explained
- ^d No critical studies missed
- ^e Risk of Bias conducted using adequate Tool
- ^f If Risk of Bias in single studies identified, then adequate actions taken in meta-analysis
- ^g Appropriateness of data extraction and transformations
- ^h Data pooling done in appropriate way
- ⁱ Adequate statistical method used
- ^j SGA = Small for gestational age

A detailed description of the criteria for the quality assessment of the reviews is provided in Table 3.2.

Dzhambov and Lercher (2019) conducted an update of the WHO ENG review on adverse birth outcomes (Nieuwenhuijsen et al., 2017) and performed a meta-analysis. They conducted a systematic search for the period between 2016 and 2019, which resulted in the identification of nine eligible studies. The focus of this review was on the association between road traffic noise and birth weight, low birth weight, small for gestational age (SGA) and preterm birth. A meta-analysis of seven estimates found that a 10 dB increase in road traffic noise at the place of residence is non-significantly associated with a -8.26 (95%-confidence interval (CI): -20.61 to 4.10) grams lower birth weight. Further, based on five to seven studies, road traffic noise was not associated with low birth weight (OR: 1.06, 95%-CI: 0.91 to 1.23 per 10 dB noise increase, n=7), SGA (OR: 1.02, 95%-CI: 0.86 to 1.21, n=5), and preterm birth (OR: 1.00, 95%-CI: 0.79 to 1.27, n=5). In this review, the quality of evidence was evaluated using the GRADE approach and resulted in a rating of *moderate* for birth weight and *very low* for the other birth outcomes. The other two reviews that were identified (Lee et al., 2023; Clark et al., 2020), did not conduct a meta-analysis (Table 3.4) and were thus not included in the Umbrella+ review.

One original study was published after Dzhambov and Lercher (2019), for which the characteristics are shown in Table 3.5. This study (Graafland et al., 2023) analysed the association between road traffic and railway noise with foetal growth, neonatal anthropometrics at birth, and adverse birth outcomes (low birth weight, term low birth weight, preterm birth, and SGA). Per 10 dB increase in road traffic noise at home, the odds for low birth weight (OR: 1.07, 95%-CI: 0.93 to 1.22), term low birth weight (OR: 1.06, 95%-CI: 0.86 to 1.31), preterm birth (OR: 1.04, 95%-CI: 0.91 to 1.18) and SGA (OR: 0.92, 95%-CI: 0.84 to 1.02) were non-significant. For railway noise, the associations were also non-significant. Further, the birth weight for neonates showed a non-significant 10.9 (95%-CI: -1.2 to 23.0) gram increase per 10 dB increase in road traffic noise and 21 (95%-CI: -0.7 to 42.7) gram increase per 10 dB increase in railway noise.

The results of the meta-analyses combining results from Graafland et al. (2023) with Dzhambov and Lercher (2019) for preterm birth, SGA, low birth weight, and birth weight are shown in Figure 3.1 to Figure 3.4. The pooled RR for road traffic noise and preterm birth was 1.03 (95%-CI: 0.92 to 1.16), for SGA 0.95 (95%-CI: 0.87 to 1.03) and for low birth weight 1.07 (95%-CI: 0.96 to 1.18). Change in birth weight was 1.4 (95%-CI: -17.4 to 20.1) grams per 10 dB increase in L_{DEN} road traffic noise. The combined RRs for transportation noise were 1.04 (95%-CI: 0.94 to 1.15) for preterm birth, 0.98 (95%-CI: 0.89 to 1.08) for SGA and 1.07 (95%-CI: 0.97 to 1.17) for low birth weight. Change in birth weight was 6.4 (95%-CI: -10.03 to 22.85) gram per 10 dB L_{DEN} transportation noise.

Although a new cohort study of almost 8,000 participants was included (Graafland et al., 2023), the associations remained non-significant; thus, the evidence rating from Dzhambov and Lercher (2019) was retained as *very low* for an association between road traffic noise and preterm birth, SGA and low birth weight. In addition, studies that analysed birth weight on a continuous scale did not provide indications for an association. Only one study addressed railway noise and no study aircraft noise. For these noise sources, the certainty evidence rating is also rated to be *very low*. Therefore, none of the adverse birth outcomes were considered for the estimation of the burden of transportation noise on children's and adolescent's health.

Table 3.5 Characteristics of the identified original study investigating the effects of transportation noise on adverse birth outcomes

Paper	Cohort (Country) ^a	Study type	Study population			Noise source (setting)	Exposure characterization	Adjustment for air pollution	Exposure metric	Effect estimates (95% confidence interval) ^b	Comment ^c
			N	Sex / Age	Follow-up						
Graafland (2023)	Generation R (NL)	Cohort	7,947	Both / embryo, newborn	Apr 2002 - Jan 2006	Road, Rail, Both combined (residence)	Noise maps developed in 2012 for Rotterdam	-	L _{DEN}	<i>Road at residence:</i> Low birth weight: 1.07 (0.93, 1.22) [§] Term low birth weight: 1.06 (0.86, 1.31) [§] Small for gest. Age: 0.92 (0.84, 1.02) [§] Preterm birth: 1.04 (0.91, 1.18) [§] Birth weight: 10.88 (-1.20, 22.96) [£] <i>Rail at residence:</i> Low birth weight: 1.06 (0.83, 1.34) [§] Term low birth weight: 1.03 (0.71, 1.49) [§] Small for gest. Age: 1.07 (0.90, 1.27) [§] Preterm birth: 1.07 (0.85, 1.35) [§] Birth weight: 21.01 (-0.73, 42.74) [£]	Additionally: NB: head circumference, length, abdominal circumference E/F: crown-rump length, head circumference, length, weight

^a NL = Netherlands

^b If not otherwise indicated, relative risks refers to a 10 dB increase in noise levels.

^c NB = New-born, E/F = Embryo/Foetus

[£] Beta

[§] Odds Ratio

Abbreviations: N = Number of participants

Figure 3.1 Meta-analysis of the most recent systematic review (Dzhambov and Lercher, 2019) with one subsequent cohort study on the relative risk for *preterm birth* in relation to transportation noise, stratified by source. Relative risks refer to a 10 dB increase in L_{DEN} .

Random-effects REML model

Figure 3.2 Meta-analysis of the most recent systematic review (Dzhambov and Lercher, 2019) with one subsequent cohort study on the relative risk for *SGA* in relation to transportation noise, stratified by source. Relative risks refer to a 10 dB increase in L_{DEN} .

Random-effects REML model

Figure 3.3 Meta-analysis of the most recent systematic review (Dzhambov and Lercher, 2019) with one subsequent cohort study on the relative risk for *low birth weight* in relation to transportation noise, stratified by source. Relative risks refer to a 10 dB increase in L_{DEN} .

Random-effects REML model

Figure 3.4 Meta-analysis of the most recent systematic review (Dzhambov and Lercher, 2019) with one subsequent cohort study on *birth weight in grams* in relation to transportation noise, stratified by source. Beta refers to a 10 dB increase in L_{DEN} .

Random-effects REML model

3.2.2 Behavioural Problems

Behaviour in children and adolescents is often quantified in epidemiological research using the Strength and Difficulties Questionnaire (SDQ) or a comparable tool. The SDQ consists of 25 attributes that can be divided in five scales with five items each (score for each item: 0-2). The scales include hyperactivity/inattention, emotional symptoms, conduct problems and peer relationship problems, which can be combined into the total difficulties score. To categorize participants in “normal”, “borderline” and “abnormal” difficulties scores, Goodman (1997) recommended to group as follows: approximately 80% of the community are “normal”, 10% are “borderline” and 10% are “abnormal”. Thus, for the parent rating in the UK study (Goodman, 1997), the sum score of 14 to 16 was considered to be borderline and a score of 17 to 40 to be of abnormal behaviour, whereas “borderline” was defined as a sum score of 15 to 16 in a Germany study (Becker et al., 2018), 17 to 18 in a Chinese study (Gao et al., 2013), and 15 to 17 in a Dutch study (Hoofs et al., 2015). Further, the SDQ consists of one positive scale, prosocial behaviour (Goodman, 1997). In this report we focus on total behavioural difficulties, which are based on the total difficulties score, and hyperactivity/inattention in relation to noise exposure at school or at home.

In the initial literature search, 158 records were identified, in the search update an additional eight papers plus one paper through a manual search were identified. During the screening of titles and abstracts, one duplicate and 154 further records were excluded. Four reviews (Baird et al., 2023; Schubert et al., 2019; Clark and Paunovic, 2018b; Zare Sakhvidi et al., 2018) and eight original studies (Bao et al., 2022; Essers et al., 2022; Raess et al., 2022; Tangermann et al., 2022; Yuchi et al., 2022; Zijlema et al., 2021; Forns et al., 2016; Hjortebjerg et al., 2016b) were eligible for this review. The PRISMA flow diagram is shown in Figure 9.2 in Annex 2. The characteristics of the review and their quality assessment are shown in Table 3.6 and Table 3.7, respectively. For behavioural problems, noise exposure was either assigned to the school or home of each child/adolescent.

The WHO ENG review addressing quality of life, wellbeing and mental health (Clark and Paunovic, 2018b) identified *low* certainty evidence for an *absence of association* between aircraft noise and emotional and conduct disorders. For road traffic and railway noise certainty of the evidence was rated *moderate* for an association with emotional and conduct disorders. Further, Clark and Paunovic (2018b) concluded that there is evidence for an association between transportation noise and hyperactivity symptoms with an evidence rating of *low* for aircraft noise and *moderate* for railway and road traffic noise. In all their evidence ratings they did not distinguish between noise exposure at home or at school. This review did not conduct a meta-analysis.

Table 3.6 Characteristics of the identified reviews investigating the effect of transportation noise on behavioural problems

Review	Outcome ^a	Outcome Assessment ^b	Noise Source	End of search period	Studies				Individual study quality ^d	Evidence rating ^e	Effect estimates (95% confidence interval) ^f
					No	N	Countries ^c	Setting			
Baird (2023)	All included in SDQ, other	SDQ, CBCL, self-report questionnaire	Road, Rail, Air	Jun 2022	11	275 - 7,958	CN, UK, ES, NL, FR, DE	Residence, School	PR	GRADE	-
Schubert (2019)	All included in SDQ	SDQ, CBCL, RSDBD, Adapted ADD Questionnaire, CDI, CMAS, ADHD-DSM-IV	Road, Rail, Air	Feb 2019	10	311 - 46,940	RS, UK, DK, ES, NL, DE, KR, NO	Residence, School	SIGN, CASP	-	<i>Road at school and residence:</i> * Total behavioural difficulties: 1.09 (1.02, 1.16) [§] Hyperactivity/inattention: 1.11 (1.04, 1.19) [§] Emotional symptoms: 1.00 (0.94, 1.07) [§] Conduct problems: 1.05 (0.98, 1.12) [§] Peer relationship problems: 1.05 (0.99, 1.12) [§]
Clark and Paunovic (2018b)	Emotional and Conduct Disorders, Hyperactivity, other	SDQ, other	Road, Rail, Air	Oct 2015	13	N/A	N/A (Europe)	Residence, School	WHO	GRADE	-
Zare Sakhvidi (2018)	All included in SDQ	SDQ, RSDBD, Toulouse Pieron test, Attention Deficit Disorder Questionnaire, GHQ, KINDL	Road, Rail, Air	Mar 2018	12	399 - 46,940	NO, DK, ES, DE, EU countries, UK, MK, BG, AT	Residence, School	PR	GRADE	-

^a SQD = Strength and Difficulties Questionnaire (Included outcomes: conduct problems, emotional symptoms, hyperactivity/inattention, peer relationship problems)

^b ADD = Attention Deficit Disorder, ADHD-DSM-IV = Attention deficit/hyperactivity disorder criteria of the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders - Fourth Edition list, CBCL = Child Behavioural Checklist, CDI = Child Depression Inventory, CMAS = Child Manifest Anxiety Scale, GHQ = General Health Questionnaire, KINDL = Index of children's quality of life, RSDBD = Rating Scale for Disruptive Behaviour Disorders, SQD = Strength and Difficulties Questionnaire

^c AT = Austria, BG = Bulgaria, CN = China, DE = Germany, DK = Denmark, ES = Spain, EU = European Union, FR = France, KR = South Korea, MK = Macedonia, N/A = Not applicable, NL = Netherlands, NO = Norway, RS = Serbia, UK = United Kingdom

^d CASP = Critical Appraisal Skills Program, PR = previously used checklist, SIGN = Scottish Intercollegiate Guidelines Network, WHO = WHO checklist

^e GRADE = Grading of Recommendations Assessment, Development and Evaluation

^f If not otherwise indicated, effect estimate refers to a 10 dB increase in noise levels.

^{*} The meta-analysis was only based on studies using dichotomized outcomes measures; studies with a continuous outcome measure were excluded.

[§] Odds Ratio

Abbreviations: No = Number of studies, N = Number of participants, N/A = Not applicable

Table 3.7 Quality assessment of the reviews investigating the effect of transportation noise of behavioural problems

Review	Literature search				Risk of Bias		Methodology for meta-analysis			Comment	Selected for outcome
	a	b	c	d	e	f	g	h	i		
Baird (2023)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	No meta-analysis conducted	-
Schubert (2019)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	Sensitivity analysis was planned, but too few studies	Studies identified in this review were used for meta-analysis
Clark and Paunovic (2018b)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	No meta-analysis conducted	-
Zare Sakhvidi (2018)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	No meta-analysis conducted	-

^a Relevant data base considered

^b Clearly and adequately defined search terms/keywords

^c Inclusion/exclusion criteria adequately defined and explained

^d No critical studies missed

^e Risk of Bias conducted using adequate Tool

^f If Risk of Bias in single studies identified, then adequate actions taken in meta-analysis

^g Appropriateness of data extraction and transformations

^h Data pooling done in appropriate way

ⁱ Adequate statistical method used

A detailed description of the criteria for the quality assessment of the reviews is provided in Table 3.2.

After Clark and Paunovic (2018b) three additional reviews were identified, but two of them (Baird et al., 2023; Zare Sakhvidi et al., 2018) were without a meta-analysis and thus not eligible for this Umbrella+ review (Table 3.7). The only review with meta-analysis published after the WHO ENG report was from Schubert et al. (2019). This review identified ten studies investigating the association between transportation noise and behavioural problems in children and adolescents. The details of these studies are presented in Table 3.8. Most studies use SDQ to assess behavioural disorders including emotional symptoms, conduct problems, hyperactivity/inattention and peer relationship problems as well as prosocial behaviour. However, multiple studies use a continuous scoring, whereas three studies use a dichotomized outcomes measure. Schubert et al. (2019) decided to focus on abnormal behavioural scores and, thus, excluded the studies with a continuous outcomes measure from their meta-analysis. This left three cross-sectional studies to be included in the meta-analysis, of which two studies solely focussed on road traffic noise and one study investigated road traffic noise and railway noise at home. The meta-analysis indicated a significantly higher odds for “abnormal” scores for total behavioural difficulties (OR: 1.09, 95%-CI: 1.02 to 1.16) and hyperactivity/inattention (OR: 1.11, 95%-CI: 1.04 to 1.19) per 10 dB increase in road traffic noise at home, whereas the odds for conduct problems, emotional symptoms and peer relationship problems were non-significantly increased (see Table 3.6). However, due to the exclusion of studies with continuous outcomes measures, the loss of information in this meta-analysis was substantial.

The characteristics of the six original studies published after the search period of Schubert et al. (2019) are shown in Table 3.9. Three studies (Bao et al., 2022; Raess et al., 2022; Yuchi et al., 2022) analysed non-European populations and were thus excluded from further considerations in this review. Tangermann et al. (2022) investigated the association between road traffic noise at home and school and behaviour and behavioural change in a longitudinal and cross-sectional design. The cross-sectional analysis indicated a significant increase by 0.15 units (95%-CI: 0.02 to 0.27; scale range 0-10) in the SQD score for peer relationship problems per 10 dB increase in road traffic noise. The longitudinal study did not indicate an association between road traffic noise and the increases in SDQ scores between baseline and follow-up. The study used continuous and categorical outcome measures. Essers et al. (2022) analysed the association between parental and childhood noise exposure at home and emotional, aggressive and Attention deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD)-related symptoms in children using continuous outcomes measures. They did not identify strong indications of an association between behavioural problems and road traffic noise and total noise (road, aircraft, railway, and industry) at home for two European cohorts. Zijlema et al. (2021) analysed the cross-sectional association between symptoms and diagnosis of ADHD and road traffic noise exposure at home and school. The study showed that road traffic noise was not significantly associated with continuously measured ADHD symptoms, but with ADHD diagnosis.

Since Schubert et al. (2019) did not consider studies reporting continuous behaviour changes in their meta-analysis, we re-checked all 10 studies identified through their literature search for eligibility in this meta-analysis. These were combined with the results of studies published after Schubert et al. (2019), which are described in Table 3.8 and Table 3.9, respectively. Of the ten studies identified by Schubert et al., we excluded five from the meta-analyses on the basis that one investigated a non-European study population (Lim et al., 2018), one studied cognitive outcomes (Belojevic et al., 2012), one did not use a comparable method to obtain the estimates (Weyde et al., 2017b), and two (Clark et al., 2013; Crombie et al., 2011) used a study population that was also analysed by other studies already included in the meta-analysis. Further, as described above, three of the new studies (Bao et al., 2022; Raess et al., 2022; Yuchi et al., 2022) analysed non-European populations and were thus also excluded from further consideration.

Table 3.8 Characteristics of the original studies on behavioural problems identified by Schubert et al. (2019)

Paper	Cohort ^a (Country) ^b	Study type	Study population		Noise source (setting)	Exposure character- ization	Outcome Assessment ^c	Adjustment for air pollution	Expo- sure metric	Effect estimates (95% confidence interval) ^{d,e}	Comment
			N	Sex / Age							
Lim (2018)	Seoul, Ulsan (KR)	Cross- sectional	918	Both / mean 11.5 years	Road (residence)	Noise map	CBCL	-	L _{DN}	<i>Road at residence:</i> Internalizing problems: 1.02 (0.98-1.06) [§] per 1 dB Externalizing problems: 1.03 (0.98-1.08) [§] per 1 dB Total problems: 1.07 (1.01- 1.14) [§] per 1 dB	Excluded from meta-analysis due to non- European study population
Weyde (2017b)	MoBa (NO)	Cross- sectional	1,384	Both / 8 years	Road (residence)	Nordic Prediction Method	RSDBD	-	L _{DEN}	<i>Road at residence:</i> Inattention (fraction score): 0.009 (0.002, 0.016) (Coef. from fractional logit response models)	Excluded from meta-analysis due to use of non-compatible model
Forns (2016)	BREATHE (ES)	Cross- sectional	2,897	Both / 7-11 years	Traffic (school)	Measured	SDQ, ADHD- DSM-IV	NO ₂	N/A	<i>Traffic noise at school:</i> Total behavioural difficulties: 1.01 (0.94, 1.07) ^ϕ per 7.6 dB ADHD symptoms: 1.24 (1.12, 1.38) ^ϕ per 7.6 dB	
Hjortebjerg (2016b)	DNBC (DK)	Cross- sectional	46,940	Both / 7 years	Road, Rail (residence)	Nordic prediction method	SDQ	-	L _{DEN}	<i>Road at residence:</i> Total behavioural difficulties (abnormal): 1.07 (1.00, 1.14) [§] Hyperactivity/inattention (abnormal): 1.10 (1.03, 1.18) [§] <i>Rail at residence:</i> Total behavioural difficulties (abnormal): 1.13 (1.02, 1.25) [§] Hyperactivity/inattention (abnormal):	Additional: Sub- outcomes of SDQ

Paper	Cohort ^a (Country) ^b	Study type	Study population		Noise source (setting)	Exposure character- ization	Outcome Assessment ^c	Adjustment for air pollution	Expo- sure metric	Effect estimates (95% confidence interval) ^{d,e}	Comment
			N	Sex / Age							
										1.09 (0.97, 1.22) [§]	
Clark (2013)	RANCH (UK)	Cross- sectional	461	Both / 15-17 years	Air (school)	Contours from the UK Civil Aviation Authority	SDQ	-	L _{Aeq,16h}	<i>Air at school (score):</i> Follow-up: Total behavioural difficulties: -0.018 (-0.076, 0.039) [£] per 1 dB Hyperactivity: 0.010 (-0.029, 0.002) [£] per 1 dB	Excluded from meta-analysis due to same study population; Additional: Sub- outcomes of SDQ
Tiesler (2013)	LISApplus, GINIplus (DE)	Cross- sectional	872	Both / 10 years	Road (residence)	Munich noise map	SDQ	-	L _{DEN}	<i>Road at residence:</i> Total behavioural difficulties: 1.16 (0.95, 1.40) ^{§§} per 9 dB Hyperactivity/inattention: 1.28 (1.03, 1.58) ^{§§} per 9 dB	Additional: Sub- outcomes of SDQ
Belojevic (2012)	Belgrade centre (RS)	Cross- sectional	311	Both / 7-11 years	Road (residence)	Measured	Adapted ADD Question- naire	-	L _{Aeq,24h}	<i>Road at residence:</i> Executive functioning (score): -0.09 (-0.17, -0.01) [£]	Excluded from meta-analysis due to outcomes investigated (cognitive outcome)
Crombie (2011)	RANCH (UK, ES, NL)	Cross- sectional	1,900	Both / mean 10.6 years	Road, Air (school)	Modelled , m	SDQ	-	L _{Aeq,16h}	<i>Road at school:</i> Total behavioural difficulties: -0.02 (-0.05, 0.01) [£] per 1 dB Hyperactivity: 0.00 (-0.01, 0.01) [£] per 1 dB <i>Air at school:</i> Total behavioural difficulties: 0.01 (-0.02, 0.04) [£] per 1 dB Hyperactivity: 0.01 (0.00, 0.02) [£] per 1 dB	Excluded from meta-analysis due to same study population; Additional: Sub- outcomes of SDQ
Stansfeld (2009)	Heathrow airport, London	Cross- sectional	2,014	Both / 9-10 years	Road, Air (school)	Modelled , calculated	SDQ	-	L _{Aeq,16h}	<i>Air at school:</i> Total behavioural difficulties: 0.013 (-0.012, 0.038) [£] per 1 dB	Our assumption: per 1 dB

Paper	Cohort ^a (Country) ^b	Study type	Study population		Noise source (setting)	Exposure character- ization	Outcome Assessment ^c	Adjustment for air pollution	Expo- sure metric	Effect estimates (95% confidence interval) ^{d,e}	Comment
			N	Sex / Age							
	(UK), Schiphol airport, Amsterdam (NL), Barajas airport, Madrid (ES)									Hyperactivity/inattention: 0.013 (0.001, 0.024) ^f per 1 dB <i>Road at school:</i> Total behavioural difficulties: -0.018 (-0.049, 0.013) ^f per 1 dB Hyperactivity/inattention: 0.0002 (-0.014, 0.014) ^f	Additional: Sub- outcomes of SDQ OR derived for meta-analysis (per 10 dB): <i>Air at school:</i> Total behavioural difficulties: 1.265 (0.805, 1.989) Hyperactivity/ina ttention: 1.265 (1.018, 1.544) <i>Road at school:</i> Total behavioural difficulties: 0.722 (0.412, 1.265) Hyperactivity/ina ttention: 1.004 (0.776, 1.288)
Haines (2001)	Heathrow Airport, West London (UK)	Cross- sectional	451	Both / mean 8.6 years	Air (school)	Measured	SDQ	-	L _{Aeq,16h}	<i>Air at school:</i> Total behavioural difficulties: -1.08 (-2.20, 0.04) ^f Hyperactivity/inattention: -0.65 (-1.06, -0.25) ^f	High (>63 dB) vs. low (<57 dB) noise level. Our assumption: 10 dB difference between groups;

Paper	Cohort ^a (Country) ^b	Study type	Study population		Noise source (setting)	Exposure character- ization	Outcome Assessment ^c	Adjustment for air pollution	Expo- sure metric	Effect estimates (95% confidence interval) ^{d,e}	Comment
			N	Sex / Age							
											Additional: Sub- outcomes of SDQ
											OR derived for meta-analysis (per 10 dB): <i>Air at school:</i> Total behavioural difficulties: 0.142 (0.019, 1.075) Hyperactivity/ina ttention: 0.308 (0.147, 0.636)

^a BREATH = BRain dEvelopment and Air polluTion ultrafine particles in sChool children, DNBC = Danish National Birth Cohort, GINIplus = German Infant Study on the influence of Nutrition Intervention Plus environmental and genetic influences on allergy development, LISAplus = Life-style factors on the development of the Immune System and Allergies in East and West Germany Plus the influence of traffic emissions and genetics , MoMa = Mother and Child Cohort Study, RANCH = Road traffic noise and Aircraft Noise exposure and children’s Cognition and Health

^b DE = Germany, DK = Denmark, ES = Spain, KR = South Korea, NL = Netherlands, NO = Norway, RS = Serbia, UK = United Kingdom

^c ADD = Attention Deficit Disorder, ADHD-DSM-IV = Attention deficit/hyperactivity disorder criteria of the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders - Fourth Edition list, CBCL = Child Behavioural Checklist, RSDBD = Rating Scale for Disruptive Behavior Disorders, SQD = Strength and Difficulties Questionnaire

^d If not otherwise indicated, relative risks refers to a 10 dB increase in noise levels.

^e ADHA = Attention Deficit/Hyperactivity Disorder

§ Odds Ratio

§§ Continuation Odds Ratio from Continuation ratio models

£ Beta

^c Mean (standard error)

φ Mean Ratio

Abbreviations: N = Number of participants, N/A = Not applicable

Table 3.9 Characteristics of the identified original studies investigating the effects of transportation noise on behavioural problems

Paper	Cohort ^a (Country) ^b	Study type	Study population			Noise source (setting)	Exposure characterization	Outcome Assessment ^c	Adjustment for air pollution	Exposure metric	Effect estimates (95% confidence interval) ^{d,e}	Comment
			N	Sex / Age	Follow-up							
Bao (2022)	Guangzhou (CN)	Cross-sectional	3,236	Both / 7-13 years	-	Road (residence)	Modelled maps with a resolution of 8.0 × 8.0 m	SDQ	NO ₂	L _{DN}	<i>Road at residence:</i> Total behavioural difficulties (abnormal): Dichotomous outcomes measure: 1.25 (1.01, 1.55) [§]	Excluded from meta-analyses due to non-European study population; Additional: Sub-outcomes of SDQ
Essers (2022)	INMA (ES), Generation R (NL)	Cross-sectional	534 (ES), 7,424 (NL)	Both / 4, 7, 9 years (ES), Both / 18 months, 3, 5, 9 years (NL)	-	Road (residence)	Noise maps developed in 2012 for Rotterdam and 2006 and 2012 for Sabadell	CBCL (ES, NL), SDQ, ADHD-DSM-IV, CPRS (ES)	-	L _{DEN}	<i>Road at residence (score):</i> Aggressive: 0.00 (-0.02, 0.01) [€] per 5 dB Emotional: -0.01 (-0.03, 0.00) [€] per 5 dB ADHD: 0.00 (-0.02, 0.02) [€] per 5 dB	OR derived for meta-analysis (per 10 dB): ADHD: 1.000 (0.930, 1.075)
Raess (2022)	SPROC (BR)	Cohort, Cross-sectional	3,385 (3 years) / 1,546 (6 years)	Both / 3, 6 years	2015-2020	Community (residence)	LUR model	SDQ (3 years), CBCL (6 years)	-	L _{DEN}	<i>Road at residence:</i> Behavioural development: Cross-sectional: 3-year olds: 1.32 (1.04, 1.68) [§] 6-year olds (score): 0.72 (0.55, 0.88) [€] Longitudinal: 3-year olds: 0.62 (0.38, 0.87) [§] 6-year olds: 0.52 (0.28, 0.77) [€]	Excluded from meta-analyses due to non-European study population
Tangermann (2022)	HERMES (CH)	Cohort, Cross-sectional	899	Both / 10-17 years	2012-2016	Road (residence)	SonBase	SDQ	PM ₁₀	L _{DEN}	<i>Road at residence:</i> Total behavioural difficulties: Cross-sectional: 0.98 (0.93, 1.02) [§] Longitudinal:	Additional: Sub-outcomes of SDQ

Paper	Cohort ^a (Country) ^b	Study type	Study population			Noise source (setting)	Exposure character- ization	Outcome Assessment ^c	Adjustment for air pollution	Expo- sure metric	Effect estimates (95% confidence interval) ^{d,e}	Comment
			N	Sex / Age	Follow- up							
Yuchi (2022)	Metro Vancouver (CA)	Cohort	28,797	Both / 3-10 years	2003 - 2010	Env (residence)	CadnaA	Diagnosis in medical records	-	L _{DEN}	1.01 (0.96, 1.06) [§] <i>Env at residence:</i> ADHD: 1.00 (0.95, 1.05) [ⓧ] per 6.91 dB	Excluded from meta- analyses due to non- European study population
Zijlema (2021)	TRAILS (DK)	Cross- sectional	1,710	Both / mean 10.6 years	-	Road (residence, school)	STAMINA	DISC-IV, CBCL, TRF	-	L _{DEN}	<i>Road at residence:</i> ADHD diagnosis: 0.929 (0.893, 0.965) [¥] per 1 dB ADHD symptoms: 0.994 (0.969, 1.019) [¥] per 1 dB <i>Road at school:</i> ADHD diagnosis: 0.945 (0.910, 0.981) [¥] per 1 dB ADHD symptoms: 0.997 (0.972, 1.022) [¥] per 1 dB	

^a HERMES = Health effects related to mobile phone use in adolescents, INMA = INfancia y Medio Ambiente, Environment and Childhood, SPROC = Sao Paulo Western Region Birth Cohort, TRAILS = Tracking Adolescents' Individual Lives Survey

^b BR = Brazil, CA = Canada, CH = Switzerland, CN = China, DK = Denmark, ES = Spain, NL = Netherlands

^c ADHD-DSM-IV = Attention deficit/hyperactivity disorder criteria of the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders - Fourth Edition list, CBCL = Child Behavioural Checklist, CPRS = Conner's Parent Rating Scale-Revised, DISC-IV = Diagnostic Interview Schedule for Children, SQD = Strength and Difficulties Questionnaire, TRF = Teacher Rating Form

^d If not otherwise indicated, relative risks refers to a 10 dB increase in noise levels.

^e ADHA = Attention Deficit/Hyperactivity Disorder

[ⓧ] Hazard Ratio

[£] Beta

[§] Odds Ratio

[¥] Relative Risk

Abbreviations: N = Number of participants

The results of the meta-analyses for the total behavioural difficulties and hyperactivity/inattention are shown in Figure 3.5 to Figure 3.8 separately for noise exposure at home or at school. Three studies looked at residential road traffic noise in relation to total behavioural difficulties and five studies for hyperactivity/inattention resulting in RRs of 1.07 (95%-CI: 1.01 to 1.14) and 1.05 (95%-CI: 0.95 to 1.16) per 10 dB increase, respectively. Only one study addressed railway noise. The pooled meta-analysis for railway and road noise at home showed a significantly increased risk for total behavioural difficulties with a RR of 1.09 (95%-CI: 1.03 to 1.15), and a non-significant risk increase for hyperactivity/inattention with a RR of 1.06 (95%-CI: 0.99 to 1.13). For road traffic noise at school, the pooled RR per 10 dB increase was 0.96 (95%-CI: 0.76 to 1.22) for total behavioural difficulties based on two studies and 1.12 (95%-CI: 0.90 to 1.38) for hyperactivity/inattention based on three studies. The pooled RRs from two English studies on aircraft noise exposure at school and behavioural problems or hyperactivity/inattention were not elevated. Strikingly, one study showed a significantly increased and the other a significantly decreased association with hyperactivity/inattention. The pooled RRs for aircraft and road noise exposure at school were close to unity for total behavioural difficulties (RR: 1.01, 95%-CI: 0.93 to 1.10) and for hyperactivity/inattention (RR: 0.97, 95%-CI: 0.66 to 1.41).

Based on these study results the certainty of evidence for an association between road traffic noise exposure at home and total behavioural difficulties was rated to be *moderate* and for hyperactivity/inattention to be *low*. Corresponding evidence for an association with railway and aircraft noise was rated to be *low* and *very low*. Exposure at school from road and aircraft noise was not found to be related to total behavioural problems and hyperactivity/inattention with *low* and *very low* certainty of evidence. We considered thus behavioural problems in relation to road traffic noise at home for the risk assessment.

Figure 3.5 Meta-analysis of original studies on *total behavioural difficulties* of the SDQ in relation to transportation noise at home, stratified by source. Relative risks refer to a 10 dB increase in L_{DEN}.

Random-effects REML model

Figure 3.6 Meta-analysis of original studies on *total behavioural difficulties* of the SDQ in relation to transportation noise *at school*, stratified by source. Relative risks refer to a 10 dB increase in L_{DEN}.

Random-effects REML model

Figure 3.7 Meta-analysis of original studies on *hyperactivity/inattention* in relation to transportation noise *at home*, stratified by source. Relative risks refer to a 10 dB increase in L_{DEN}.

Random-effects REML model

Figure 3.8 Meta-analysis of original studies on *hyperactivity/inattention* in relation to transportation noise *at school*, stratified by source. Relative risks refer to a 10 dB increase in L_{DEN}.

Random-effects REML model

3.2.3 Blood Pressure

The initial literature search for cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) in all population groups resulted in 232 records and the search update identified 25 further papers. While screening titles and abstracts for CVDs five duplicates and 166 papers were excluded, and while assessing the full-text for CVDs a further 32 papers were excluded. Out of the 54 remaining CVD papers, 39 papers did not analyse blood pressure and were excluded. Thus, 15 papers investigating blood pressure were left, including three reviews and twelve original studies. However, seven original studies focused on an adult population only (Kourieh et al., 2022; Petri et al., 2021; Carugno et al., 2018; Pitchika et al., 2017; Halonen et al., 2017; Evrard et al., 2017; Zijlema et al., 2016). Therefore, three reviews (Sivakumaran et al., 2022; van Kempen et al., 2018; Dzhambov and Dimitrova, 2017) and five original studies (Warembourg et al., 2021, 2019; Pedersen et al., 2019; Enoksson Wallas et al., 2019; Bloemsmas et al., 2019a) were selected for further consideration. The PRISMA flow diagram is shown in Figure 9.3 in Annex 2. The characteristics of the reviews and their quality assessment are shown in Table 3.10 and Table 3.11, respectively. In these studies on blood pressure, noise exposure was either assigned to the school or home of each study participant.

Table 3.10 Characteristics of the identified reviews investigating the effect of transportation noise on blood pressure

Review	Outcome ^a	Noise Source	End of search period	Studies				Individual study quality ^c	Evidence rating ^d	Effect estimates (95% confidence interval) ^e
				No	N	Countries ^b	Setting			
Sivakumaran (2022)	Blood pressure, others	Road, Rail, Air	Dec 2021	12	115-4,279	DE, RS, IT, NL, AT, SE, ES, UK, EG, SK	Residence, School	RCTs, ROBINS-E	GRADE	<i>Road at school and residence:</i> Cross-sectional: Preschool - SBP: 4.58 (3.43, 5.73) ^{c**} Preschool - DBP: 1.05 (-3.28, 5.37) ^{c**} 8-14 years - SBP: -0.02 (-0.43, 0.40) ^c 8-14 years - DBP: -0.19 (-0.81, 0.43) ^c Cohort/Case-control: 16 years - SBP: -0.13 (-0.60, 0.35) ^c 9-12 years - SBP: -0.11 (-0.21, 0.00) ^c 9-12 years - DBP: -0.04 (-0.14, 0.05) ^c
Van Kempen (2018)	Blood pressure, others	Road, Air	Aug 2015	8	2,013-4,520*	NL, UK, AU, DE, HR, RS, USA	Residential, School	WHO	GRADE	Cross-sectional: <i>Road at school (mmHg):</i> SBP: -0.60 (-1.51, 0.30) ^f DBP: 0.46 (-0.60, 1.53) ^f <i>Road at residence (mmHg):</i> SBP: 0.08 (-0.48, 0.64) ^f DBP: 0.47 (-0.30, 1.24) ^f
Dzhambov and Dimitrova (2017)	Blood pressure	Road	Jul 2016	13	115 - 1,726	SK, NL, RS, DE, IN, PK, UK, AT, USA	Residence, School	PR	GRADE	Cross-sectional: <i>Road at school (mmHg):</i> SBP: 0.48 (-0.87, 1.83) ^f per 5 dB DBP: 0.22 (-0.64, 1.07) ^f per 5 dB <i>Road at residence (mmHg):</i> SBP: 0.20 (-0.30, 0.71) ^f per 5 dB DBP: 0.03 (-0.18, 0.25) ^f per 5 dB

^a Others = further health outcomes (mainly cardiovascular outcomes)

^b AT = Austria, AU = Australia, DE = Germany, EG = Egypt, ES = Spain, HR = Croatia, IN = India, IT = Italy, NL = Netherlands, PK = Pakistan, RS = Serbia, SE = Sweden, SK = Slovakia, UK = United Kingdom, USA = United States of America

^c PR = previously used checklist, RCTs = Cochrane Risk of Bias tool for randomized controlled trials, ROBINS-E = Risk of Bias Instrument for Non-randomized Studies of Exposures, WHO = WHO checklist

- d GRADE = Grading of Recommendations Assessment, Development and Evaluation
 e If not otherwise indicated, effect estimate refers to a 10 dB increase in noise levels.
 * Minimum and maximum number of study participants included per meta-analysis (source, outcome and study design specific)
 ** <65 vs. >=65 dB
 f Beta
 c Mean difference

Abbreviations: No = Number of papers, N = Number of participants

Table 3.11 Quality assessment of the reviews investigating the effect of transportation noise on blood pressure

Review	Literature search				Risk of Bias		Methodology for meta-analysis			Comment	Selected for outcome
	a	b	c	d	e	f	g	h	i		
Sivakumaran (2022)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	No separate meta-analysis for noise at school and noise at residence	-
Van Kempen (2018)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	WHO ENG	-
Dzhambov and Dimitrova (2017)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		Systolic and diastolic blood pressure

- a Relevant data base considered
 b Clearly and adequately defined search terms/keywords
 c Inclusion/exclusion criteria adequately defined and explained
 d No critical studies missed
 e Risk of Bias conducted using adequate Tool
 f If Risk of Bias in single studies identified, then adequate actions taken in meta-analysis
 g Appropriateness of data extraction and transformations
 h Data pooling done in appropriate way
 i Adequate statistical method used

A detailed description of the criteria for the quality assessment of the reviews is provided in Table 3.2.

The WHO ENG review (van Kempen et al., 2018) identified non-significant associations between road traffic noise and blood pressure in children with a *very low* certainty of evidence rating. The most recent review investigating the association between transportation noise and blood pressure in children and adolescents was published by Sivakumaran et al. (2022). However, the meta-analysis conducted in that review combined study results of noise exposure at home and in schools and did not conduct a meta-analysis for each exposure group separately. Dzhambov and Dimitrova (2017) included in their meta-analysis the same studies as Sivakumaran et al. (2022) and conducted separate meta-analyses for transportation noise exposure at home and school. Therefore, Dzhambov and Dimitrova (2017) was selected as starting point for our evaluation. In this review the associations between road traffic noise at home/at school and systolic blood pressure (SBP)/diastolic blood pressure (DBP) were all non-significant. For residential road traffic noise the SBP increased by 0.2 mmHg (95%-CI: -0.30 to 0.71) per 5 dB increase in noise based on 10 estimates and DBP by 0.03 mmHg (95%-CI: -0.18 to 0.25) per 5 dB increase in noise based on nine estimates. Further, based on nine estimates the SBP increased by 0.48 mmHg (95%-CI: -0.87 to 1.83) and the DBP by 0.22 mmHg (95%-CI: -0.64 to 1.07) per 5 dB increase in road traffic noise at school. The quality of evidence was based on the GRADE system and was rated as *low* for all four exposure-outcomes combinations.

Since the end of the search period of Dzhambov and Dimitrova (2017), five new studies were published (details see Table 3.12). These studies investigated the association between road traffic noise at home and/or school and blood pressure in children and adolescents. Additionally, one of the studies also analysed the association between railway noise at home and/or school and blood pressure in adolescents. Warembourg et al. (2021, 2019) did not find any significant associations between the different road traffic noise categories and blood pressure (see Table 3.12) in children at 4 to 5 years of age as well as children at 6 to 11 years of age. Pedersen et al. (2019) identified a significant decrease in SBP after adjusting for NO₂ (β : -1.36 mmHg, 95%-CI: -2.62 to -0.11) and a non-significant increase in DBP (β : 0.10 mmHg, 95%-CI: -0.81 to 1.01) per 10 dB increase road traffic noise at home for adolescents at 10 to 15 years of age. Enoksson Wallas et al. (2019) found non-significant associations between a 10 dB increase in residential road traffic noise exposure and SBP (β : -0.41 mmHg, 95%-CI: -1.04 to 0.21) or DBP (β : 0.05 mmHg, 95%-CI: -0.38 to 0.48) at 16 years of age. Bloemsmas et al. (2019a) did not observe consistent patterns of associations between railway or road traffic noise at home and SBP or DBP at 12 or 16 years of age (see Table 3.12).

The results of the meta-analyses for systolic and diastolic blood pressure and noise at home and school are shown in Figure 3.9 to Figure 3.12. For noise at school the results from the review were combined with an original study resulting in non-significant effect estimates of 0.55 mmHg (95%-CI: -0.45 to 1.55) and -0.40 mmHg (95%-CI: -2.25 to 1.45) per 10 dB increase in road traffic noise at school for DBP and SBP, respectively. The meta-analyses for residential noise and DBP resulted in a non-significant increase of 0.044 mmHg (95%-CI: -0.37 to 0.46) per 10 dB increase in railway noise and by 0.026 mmHg (95%-CI: -0.19 to 0.24) per 10 dB increase in road traffic noise. For residential noise the SBP decreased by 0.16 mmHg (95%-CI: -0.75 to 0.43) per 10 dB increase in railway noise and by 0.16 mmHg (95%-CI: -0.48 to 0.17) per 10 dB increase in road traffic noise. The combined estimates for residential transportation noise were 0.03 mmHg (95%-CI: -0.19 to 0.24) for DBP and -0.16 mmHg (95%-CI: -0.48 to 0.17) for SBP.

In line with the evidence rating by Dzhambov and Dimitrova (2017), certainty of evidence for associations between road and railway noise at home and at school with DBP and SBP was considered to be *low*. No study on aircraft noise was found and corresponding certainty of evidence is regarded as *very low*. Therefore, blood pressure will not be considered in the estimation of the burden of transportation noise on children's and adolescent's health. Note that Warembourg (2021) included a larger sample than Warembourg (2019) for exposure at noise exposure at home. But since they did not consider exposure at school, we included the former study in our meta-analysis for both locations. Using the newer study for evaluation the association between blood pressure and road traffic noise exposure at home would produce a similar pooled estimate and not change the corresponding evidence rating.

Table 3.12 Characteristics of the identified original studies investigating the effects of transportation noise on blood pressure

Paper	Cohort ^a (Count Study type) ^b	Study type	Study population		Noise source (setting)	Exposure characterization	Adjustment for air pollution	Exposure metric	Effect estimates (95% confidence interval) ^c	Comment
			N	Sex / Age						
Warembourg (2021)	BIB, EDEN, INMA, RHEA (UK, FR, ES, GR)	Cross-sectional	4,279	Both / mean 4.8 years	Road (residence)	Local and governmental maps, Fieldwork	-	L _{DEN}	<i>Road at residence (mmHg):</i> 55-60 vs. <55 dB - SBP: -0.57 (-1.79, 0.64) ^f 60-65 vs. <55 dB - SBP: -0.16 (-1.20, 0.88) ^f 65-70 vs. <55 dB - SBP: 0.00 (-1.47, 1.31) ^f >70 vs. <55 dB - SBP: 0.08 (-1.84, 1.99) ^f 55-60 vs. <55 dB - DBP: -0.10 (-0.91, 0.71) ^f 60-65 vs. <55 dB - DBP: 0.53 (-0.61, 1.67) ^f 65-70 vs. <55 dB - DBP: -0.03 (-1.43, 1.37) ^f >70 vs. <55 dB - DBP: 1.00 (-1.24, 3.22) ^f	Excluded since study population overlapping with Warembourg (2019) and the earlier paper also includes exposure at school)
Bloemsma (2019a)	PIAMA (NL)	Cross-sectional	1,505 / 797 (diff. age)	Both / 12/16 years	Road, Rail (residence)	STAMINA	-	L _{DEN}	<i>Road at residence (mmHg):</i> 12 years - SBP: 0.18 (-0.45, 0.81) ^f per 6.9 dB 16 years - SBP: 0.29 (-0.58, 1.15) ^f per 6.7 dB 12 years - DBP: -0.07 (-0.50, 0.37) ^f per 6.9 dB 16 years - DBP: -0.10 (-0.71, 0.51) ^f per 6.7 dB <i>Rail at residence (mmHg):</i> 12 years - SBP: -0.15 (-0.77, 0.46) ^f per 8.45 dB 16 years - SBP: -0.09 (-0.85, 0.67) ^f per 7.6 dB 12 years - DBP: 0.01 (-0.42, 0.44) ^f per 8.45 dB 16 years - DBP: 0.08 (-0.46, 0.62) ^f per 7.6 dB	-
Enoksson Wallas (2019)	BAMSE (ES)	Cross-sectional	2,597	Both / 16 years	Road (residence)	Nordic Prediction Method	-	L _{DEN}	<i>Road at residence (mmHg):</i> SBP: -0.41 (-1.04, 0.21) ^f DBP: 0.05 (-0.38, 0.48) ^f	-
Pedersen (2019)	DNBC (DK)	Cross-sectional	629	Both / mean 12.7 years	Road (residence)	Nordic Prediction Method	NO ₂	L _{DEN}	<i>Road at residence (mmHg):</i> SBP: -1.36 (-2.62, -0.11) ^f DBP: 0.10 (-0.81, 1.01) ^f	-
Warembourg (2019)	HELIX (BIB, EDEN, INMA,	Cross-sectional	1,277	Both / 6-11 years	Road (residence, school)	Local and governmental maps, Fieldwork	-	L _{DEN}	<i>Road at residence (mmHg):</i> 55-59 vs. <55 dB - SBP: -0.02 (-2.04, 2.00) ^f 60-64 vs. <55 dB - SBP: -0.28 (-2.62, 2.07) ^f >=65 vs. <55 - SBP: -0.21 (-2.89, 2.48) ^f	

Paper	Cohort ^a (Count ry) ^b	Study type	Study population		Noise source (setting)	Exposure character- ization	Adjustme nt for air pollution	Expo- sure metric	Effect estimates (95% confidence interval) ^c	Comment
			N	Sex / Age						
	KANC, MoBa, RHEA) (UK, FR, ES, LI, GR, NO)								55-59 vs. <55 dB - DBP: 0.20 (-1.94, 2.34) [£] 60-64 vs. <55 dB - DBP: 0.38 (-1.77, 2.53) [£] >=65 vs. <55 - DBP: -0.04 (-2.410, 2.32) [£] <i>Road at school (mmHg):</i> 55-59 vs. <55 dB - SBP: -0.12 (-2.27, 2.02) [£] 60-64 vs. <55 dB - SBP: -0.74 (-3.56, 2.09) [£] >=65 vs. <55 - SBP: -2.69 (-5.61, 0.23) [£] 55-59 vs. <55 dB - DBP: 0.01 (-1.98, 2.01) [£] 60-64 vs. <55 dB - DBP: -0.70 (-3.34, 1.95) [£] >=65 vs. <55 - DBP: -1.40 (-4.03, 1.22) [£]	

^a BAMSE = Swedish population-based birth cohort, BIB = Born in Bradford, DNBC = Danish National Birth Cohort, EDEN = Etude des Déterminants Pré et postnataux du Développement et de la Santé de l'Enfant, HELIX = Human Early-life Exposome project, INMA = Infancia y Medio Ambiente, Environment and Childhood, KANC = Kaunus Cohort, MoBa = Norwegian Mother and Child Cohort Study, PIAMA = Dutch Prevention and Incidence of Asthma and Mite Allergy birth cohort study, RHEA = Mother Child Cohort study in Crete

^b DK = Denmark, ES = Spain, FR = France, GR = Greece, LI = Lithuania, NL = Netherlands, NO = Norway, UK = United Kingdom

^c If not otherwise indicated, relative risks refers to a 10 dB increase in noise levels.

[£] Beta

Abbreviations: N = Number of participants

Figure 3.9 Meta-analysis of the most recent systematic review (Dzhambov and Dimitrova, 2017) with subsequent original studies on SBP in mmHg in relation to transportation noise at home, stratified by source. Beta refers to a 10 dB increase in L_{DEN} .

Random-effects REML model

Figure 3.10 Meta-analysis of the most recent systematic review (Dzhambov and Dimitrova, 2017) with one subsequent original study on SBP in mmHg in relation to transportation noise at school, stratified by source. Beta refers to a 10 dB increase in L_{DEN} .

Random-effects REML model

Figure 3.11 Meta-analysis of the most recent systematic review (Dzhambov and Dimitrova, 2017) with subsequent original studies on *DBP in mmHg* in relation to transportation noise *at home*, stratified by source. Beta refers to a 10 dB increase in L_{DEN} .

Random-effects REML model

Figure 3.12 Meta-analysis of the most recent systematic review (Dzhambov and Dimitrova, 2017) with one subsequent original study on *DBP in mmHg* in relation to transportation noise *at school*, stratified by source. Beta refers to a 10 dB increase in L_{DEN} .

Random-effects REML model

3.2.4 Cognition

Cognition refers to the faculties involved in acquiring, processing, using, and producing information and understanding, and includes attention, memory, learning, memory, executive function, reasoning, computation, and language (Harvey, 2019). Noise studies in children address typically a wide range of cognitive aspects including standardised academic tests on reading, language ability and math.

The initial literature search revealed 177 records and the update a further 26 records. By screening titles and abstracts four duplicates and 176 papers were excluded, leaving 13 reviews and 10 original studies for full-text reviewing. During the full-text evaluation three reviews (Roche et al., 2024; Lee et al., 2023; Basner et al., 2017) were excluded due to not being systematic or a scoping review, three reviews (Tzivian et al., 2015; Stansfeld and Clark, 2015; Stansfeld, 2015) were published before the end of the search period of the WHO ENG review (Clark and Paunovic, 2018a) and two reviews were excluded because they did not investigate children and adolescents (Zaman et al., 2022; Zhao et al., 2021). Further, one original study (Seabi et al., 2015) was included in the WHO ENG review, one paper (Julvez et al., 2021) did not present any results on noise and four studies analysed adults (Mac Domhnaill et al., 2021; Fuks et al., 2019; Tzivian et al., 2016a, 2016b), which led to their exclusion. Therefore, five reviews (Clark et al., 2020; Dohmen et al., 2022; Terzakis et al., 2022; Thompson et al., 2022; Clark and Paunovic, 2018a) and four original papers (Pérez-Crespo et al., 2024; Tangermann et al., 2023; Foraster et al., 2022; Raess et al., 2022) were selected for further consideration. The PRISMA flow diagram is shown in Figure 9.4 in Annex 2. The characteristics of the review and their quality assessment are shown in Table 3.13 and Table 3.14, respectively. For cognition, noise exposure was either assigned to the school or home of each child/adolescent.

The WHO ENG review (Clark and Paunovic, 2018a) identified *moderate* evidence pointing to an effect of aircraft noise on reading and oral comprehension, standardized assessment tests and long-term and short-term memory, and to an effect of railway noise on standardised assessment tests. The quality of evidence for all other combinations of transportation noise (aircraft, road traffic, and railway) and cognitive outcomes (reading and oral comprehension, standardised assessment tests, long-term and short-term memory, attention, and executive function) was rated *low* or *very low*. Further, they described the pool of evidence as having a lack of homogeneity of methods and reporting between studies, for which reason no meta-analysis was conducted.

The most recent review (Thompson et al., 2022) addressing the association between transportation noise and cognitive outcomes is an update of the WHO ENG review (Clark and Paunovic, 2018a), and is also the only review including a meta-analysis (Table 3.14). Using the WHO ENG review as baseline, Thompson et al. (2022) identified 16 new studies in addition to the 32 studies identified by Clark and Paunovic (2018a). For most outcomes including academic ability, attention, memory and learning, and fluid intelligence and general cognition Thompson et al. (2022) rated the evidence as *low* or *very low*. Therefore, only for reading, verbal and language ability, for which an effect was identified, the evidence was rated as *moderate* a meta-analysis was conducted. A meta-analysis based on four studies showed that a 1 dB increase in environmental noise was associated with a non-significant reduction in reading and language ability by -0.11 (95%-CI: -0.32 to 0.10) points. A second meta-analysis of three studies found that reading test scores in quiet class rooms (average L_{eq} 59-69.9dB) were 0.80 (95%-CI: 0.40 to 1.20) points higher than in noisier class rooms (average L_{eq} 54.4-57 dB) considering railway or aircraft noise.

Table 3.13 Characteristics of the identified reviews investigating the effect of transportation noise on cognition

Review	Outcome	Noise Source ^a	End of search period	Studies			Individual study quality ^c	Evidence rating ^d	Effect estimate (95% confidence interval)
				No	N	Countries ^b			
Dohmen (2022)	Reading, Attention, Reaction time, Memory	Air, Env	2022	8	123 - 340	USA, DE, UK,AT	WHO	-	-
Terzakis (2022)	Cognitive development, Cognitive performance	Road, Air, Env	2020	30	236 - 11,000	N/A	WHO	-	-
Thompson (2022)	Different measures of cognitive function	Road, Rail, Air, Env	Jul 2021	48	54 - 191,054	DE, CN, NO, KR, UK, FR, ES, LT, GR, TH, USA, IR, other	OHAT	GRADE	<i>Environmental noise at school:</i> Reading comprehension (score): 0.8 (0.4, 1.2) ^{£*} Reading and language abilities (score): -0.11 (-0.32, 0.10) [£] per 1 dB
Clark (2020)	Reading comprehension, Mathematics, Memory, Attention, Distraction	Road, Rail, Air	Mar 2019	9	134 - 4,814	DE, GR, ES, ZA, USA	Own measure	GRADE	-
Clark and Paunovic (2018a)	Reading and oral comprehension, Memory, Executive function deficit	Road, Rail, Air, Env	Jun 2015	35	N/A	N/A (Europe)	WHO	GRADE	-

^a Env = Environmental

^b AT = Austria, CN = China, DE = Germany, ES = Spain, FR = France, GR = Greece, IR = Iran, KR = South Korea, LT = Lithuania, N/A = Not applicable, NO = Norway, TH = Thailand, UK = United Kingdom, USA = United States of America, ZA = South Africa; others = not named

^c OHAT = Office of Health Assessment and Translation Risk of Bias Rating Tool for Human and Animal Studies, WHO = WHO checklist

^d GRADE = Grading of Recommendations Assessment, Development and Evaluation

* Leq: 59-69.9 dB vs. 54.4-57 dB

[£] Beta

Abbreviations: No = Number of papers, N = Number of participants, N/A = Not applicable

Table 3.14 Quality assessment of the reviews investigating the effect of transportation noise on cognition

Review	Literature search				Risk of Bias		Methodology for meta-analysis			Comment	Selected for outcome
	a	b	c	d	e	f	g	h	i		
Dohmen (2022)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	No meta-analysis conducted	-
Terzakis (2022)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	No meta-analysis conducted	-
Thompson (2022)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	Reading and language abilities, reading comprehension
Clark (2020)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	No meta-analysis conducted	-
Clark and Paunovic (2018a)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	No meta-analysis conducted	-

- a Relevant data base considered
- b Clearly and adequately defined search terms/keywords
- c Inclusion/exclusion criteria adequately defined and explained
- d No critical studies missed
- e Risk of Bias conducted using adequate Tool
- f If Risk of Bias in single studies identified, then adequate actions taken in meta-analysis
- g Appropriateness of data extraction and transformations
- h Data pooling done in appropriate way
- i Adequate statistical method used

A detailed description of the criteria for the quality assessment of the reviews is provided in Table 3.2.

Since the end of the search period of Thompson et al. (2022) four new studies were published. However, one study (Raess et al., 2022) analysed a non-European population and was therefore excluded. The characteristics for the remaining three studies are shown in Table 3.15. These studies analysed the association between road traffic noise at home and/or school and multiple cognitive outcomes excluding reading comprehension. Pérez-Crespo et al. (2024) did not find an association between road traffic noise exposure during pregnancy or childhood and any of the cognitive outcomes, e.g., memory (β : -0.92, 95%-CI: -2.08 to 0.24) or processing speed (β : 0.45, 95%-CI: -0.22 to 1.14) per 10 dB increase in road traffic noise pooled for both cohorts. Tangermann et al. (2023) found mostly no associations between various cognitive outcomes and noise exposure at home or at school, although in a cross-sectional analysis a significant decrease in figural memory with -0.27 (95%-CI: -0.49 to -0.04) units per 10 dB road traffic noise increase at home was found. Further, a significant reduction of -0.13 (95%-CI: -0.25 to 0.00) units per 10 dB road traffic noise at home for concentration constancy z-scores in a longitudinal analysis with one year of follow-up. Foraster et al. (2022) identified a statistically significant association between the cognitive outcomes slower development of working memory, complex working memory, and slower improvement of inattentiveness over 12 months and school-outdoor road traffic noise levels. Associations of various cognitive outcomes with road traffic noise at home were not significant.

In summary, these new studies provide further evidence for a link between cognition and transportation noise in children and adolescents. However, the authors applied different tests for each cognitive domain and even within a single domain. Therefore, a pooling of the studies by means of a meta-analysis was not possible. The WHO ENG review (Clark and Paunovic, 2018a) and the most recent review (Thompson et al., 2022) rated the evidence for an association of aircraft noise and transportation noise with reading and oral comprehension to be *moderate*. Therefore, reading and oral comprehension is considered in the estimation of the burden of transportation noise on children's and adolescent's health using the same exposure-response function as previously used (EEA, 2020).

Table 3.15 Characteristics of the identified original studies investigating the effects of transportation noise on cognition

Paper	Cohort ^a (Country) ^b	Study type	Study population			Noise source (setting)	Exposure character- ization	Outcome Assessment ^c	Adjustment for air pollution	Exposure metric	Effect estimates (95% confidence interval) ^d	Comment
			N	Sex / Age	Follow-up							
Pérez-Crespo (2024)	INMA (ES) / Generation R (NL)	Cohort	619 (ES) / 7,115 (NL)	Both / 4-13 years	2002-2019	Road (residence)	Noise maps developed in 2006 and 2012 for Sabadell and in 2012 for Rotterdam	Many different tests including FTT, K-CPT, MSCA, NEPSY-II, SON-R, TMTA, TMTB, TVK, WISC-IV, WISC V, ...	-	L _{DEN}	<i>Road at residence:</i> Non-verbal intelligence: INMA: -0.18 (-1.98, 1.62) [£] Gen. R: 0.01 (-0.44, 0.47) [£] <i>Verbal intelligence:</i> INMA: -0.95 (-2.70, 0.80) [£] Gen. R: 0.08 (-0.39, 0.54) [£] <i>Memory:</i> INMA: -1.18 (-3.39, 1.03) [£] Gen. R: -0.82 (-2.20, 0.55) [£] <i>Processing speed:</i> INMA: 0.09 (-2.59, 2.76) [£] Gen. R: 0.48 (-0.24, 1.19) [£]	Additional: Attention (Commission errors, Omission errors, Visuomotor attention)
Tangermann (2023)	HERMES (CH)	Cohort, cross-sectional	899	Both / 10-17 years	2012-2014; 2014-2016	Road (residence, school)	SonBase	Intelligenz-Struktur-Test, FAKT-II-test, d2-test	PM ₁₀	L _{DEN} (residence) L _{DAY} (school)	<i>Road at residence:</i> Cross-sectional: Total memory: -0.09 (-0.43, 0.25) [£] Concentration constancy: 0.09 (-0.43, 0.25) [£] Longitudinal: Total memory: -0.09 (-0.58, 0.41) [£] Concentration constancy: -0.13 (-0.25, 0.00) [£] <i>Road at school:</i> Cross-sectional: Total memory: 0.06 (-0.35, 0.48) [£] Concentration constancy: 0.06 (-0.04, 0.16) [£]	Additional: Verbal and figural memory, concentration accuracy

Paper	Cohort ^a (Country) ^b	Study type	Study population			Noise source (setting)	Exposure character- ization	Outcome Assessment ^c	Adjustment for air pollution	Exposure metric	Effect estimates (95% confidence interval) ^d	Comment
			N	Sex / Age	Follow -up							
										Longitudinal: Total memory: 0.09 (-0.53, 0.72) ^f Concentration constancy: -0.07 (-0.08, 0.23) ^f		
Foraster (2022)	BREATHE (ES)	Cohort	2,680 (2,346 residence, 24 school)	Both / 7-10 years	2012- 2013	Road (residence, school)	Strategic Noise Map for Barcelona	n-back task, Attentional Network Test	NO ₂	L _{DEN} (resi- dence) L _{DAY} (school)	Road at residence: Working memory: 1.35 (-0.83, 3.53) ^f per 5dB Complex working memory: 0.40 (-1.32, 2.12) ^f per 5 dB Inattentiveness: -0.52 (-2.06, 1.01) ^f per 5dB Road at school: Working memory: -6.17 (-8.84, -3.49) ^f per 5dB Complex working memory: -4.91 (-7.03, -2.78) ^f per 5 dB Inattentiveness: 2.81 (0.89, 4.74) ^f per 5dB	-
Raess (2022)	SPROC (BR)	Cohort, cross- sectio- nal	3,385 (3 years) / 1,546 (6 years)	Both / 3, 6 years	2015- 2020	Community (residence)	LUR model	PRIDI, IDELA	-	L _{DEN}	Community noise at residence: Cognitive development problems: Cross-sectional: 3-year olds z-score: 0.08 (-0.04, 0.19) ^f 6-year olds: -0.49 (-2.71, 1.74) ^f Longitudinal: 3-year olds (z-score): -0.27 (-0.55, 0.00) ^f 6-year olds (z-score): -0.27 (-0.55, 0.00) ^f	Non- European study population

^a HERMES = Health effects related to mobile phone use in adolescents, INMA = Infancia y Medio Ambiente, Environment and Childhood, SPROC = Sao Paulo Western Region Birth Cohort, BREATHE = Brain Development and Air Pollution Ultrafine Particles in School Children

^b BR = Brazil, CH = Switzerland, ES = Spain, NL=Netherlands

^c FTT = Finger Tapping Test, IDELA = International Development and Early Learning Assessment, K-CPT = Conners' Kiddie Continuous Performance Test, MSCA = McCarthy Scales of Children's Ability, NEPSY-II = Developmental NEuroPSYchological Assessment Second Edition, PRIDI = Regional Project on Child Development Indicators, SON-R = Snijders-Oomen Niet-verbale intelligentie Test – Revisie, TMTA = Trail Making Test Part A, TMTB = Trail Making Test Part B, TVK = Talltest voor Kinderen, WISC-IV = 4th edition of Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children-IV, WISC V = 5th edition of Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children

^d If not otherwise indicated, relative risks refers to a 10 dB increase in noise levels.

^e Beta

Abbreviations: N = Number of participants

3.2.5 Obesity

After identifying 79 records during the initial literature review, one paper through manual search and six additional papers during the search update, 66 records were excluded by screening titles and abstracts. During the full-text evaluation one review (Belojević and Paunović, 2016) was excluded as obesity was covered very briefly, one review (van Kempen et al., 2018) was excluded since it only identified papers with an adult population, one original study (Huang et al., 2020) was excluded as they analysed noise perception and not measured or modelled noise levels, and eight studies (Cai et al., 2020; Cramer et al., 2019; Foraster et al., 2018; Pyko et al., 2017, 2015; Christensen et al., 2016b, 2015; Oftedal et al., 2015) were excluded because they did not analyse children or adolescents. This left four reviews (Gui et al., 2022; Malacarne et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2021; An et al., 2018) and five original studies (de Bont et al., 2021; Wallas et al., 2019; Bloemsma et al., 2019a, 2019b; Christensen et al., 2016a) for further consideration. The PRISMA flow diagram is shown in Figure 9.5 in Annex 2. The characteristics of the review and their quality assessment are shown in Table 3.16 and Table 3.17, respectively. For obesity, noise exposure refers to residential noise exposure of each child/adolescent.

The WHO ENG review (van Kempen et al., 2018) only identified papers analysing the association between transportation noise and obesity markers (body mass index (BMI) and waist circumference (WC)) in adult populations. Although two reviews mentioned above included papers analysing only child populations, they did not include any meta-analysis and were therefore not selected (Malacarne et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2021). The other two reviews included both child and adult populations (Gui et al., 2022; An et al., 2018), however, neither conducted a meta-analysis for each population group separately. Thus, none of the reviews were selected for further consideration.

The characteristics of the five original studies published after the end of the search period of van Kempen et al. (2018) are shown in Table 3.18. The most recent study (de Bont et al., 2021) showed no statistically significant associations between road traffic noise and overweight (OR: 1.08, 95%-CI: 0.97 to 1.22), waist circumference z-score (β : 0.02, 95%-CI: -0.03 to 0.08), Body fat % z-score (β : 0.02, 95%-CI: -0.03 to 0.07) or zBMI (β : 0.06, 95%-CI: -0.00 to 0.12) per 8 dB increase in L_{den} . Wallas et al. (2019) found an association between residential road traffic noise and an increase in BMI from school age to adolescences, but not at earlier age. For children between 8 and 11 years of age the BMI increments were 0.11 (95% CI 0.08 to 0.13) kg/m² per 10 dB noise increase and for those between 12 to 16 the BMI increments were 0.20 (95% CI 0.17 to 0.22) kg/m² per 10 dB noise increase. Bloemsma et al. (2019a, 2019b) and Christensen (2016a) did not identify a significant association between transportation noise and overweight, waist circumference or BMI z-scores.

Table 3.16 Characteristics of the identified reviews investigating the effect of transportation noise on overweight

Review	Outcome ^a	Noise Source ^b	End of search period	Studies				Individual study quality ^d	Evidence rating ^e	Effect estimate (95% confidence interval)
				No	N	Countries ^c	Pop			
Gui (2022)	BMI, WC, WHR, obesity, overweight, body fat, weight	Road, Rail, Air, Env	Feb 2021	13	484 - 412,934	SE, DK, UK, NO, BG, SK, CH, NL	Adults, Children	NTP/OHAT	GRADE	No estimates solely for children and adolescents
Malacarne (2022)	BMI, overweight	Traffic	Feb 2020	4	3,403 - 40,974	SE, DK, NL, NO	Children	NOS	-	-
Wang (2021)	BMI, obesity, overweight	Traffic	Jan 2019	6	115 - 40,974	NL, DK, AT, DE, SE, NO	Children	NIH	-	-
An (2018)	BMI, WC, WHR, body fat, weight	Road, Rail, Air	Feb 2018	11	132 - 52,456	SE, IT, DK, BG, NO, USA, SK	Adults, Children	Self-developed	GRADE	No estimates solely for children and adolescents

^a BMI = Body mass index, WC = Waist circumference, WHR = Waist-hip-ratio

^b Env = Environmental

^c AT = Austria, BG = Bulgaria, CH = Switzerland, DE = Germany, DK = Denmark, IT = Italy, NL = Netherlands, NO = Norway, SE = Sweden, SK = Slovakia, UK = United Kingdom, USA = United States of America

^d NIH = National Institutes of Health's Quality Assessment Tool for Observational Cohort and Cross-Sectional Studies, NOS = Newcastle-Ottawa Scale, NTP/OHAT = National Toxicology Program/Office of Health Assessment and Translation Risk of Bias Rating Tool for Human and Animal Studies

^e GRADE = Grading of Recommendations Assessment, Development and Evaluation

Abbreviations: No = Number of studies, N = Number of participants, Pop = Population

Table 3.17 Quality assessment of the reviews investigating the effect of transportation noise on overweight

Review	Literature search				Risk of Bias		Methodology for meta-analysis			Comment	Selected for outcome
	a	b	c	d	e	f	g	h	i		
Gui (2022)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	No meta-analysis solely for children and adolescents conducted. Possibly data from SPDD cohort have been used multiple times in the same meta-analysis (Pyko 2015, Eriksson 2014, Pyko 2017)	-
Malacarne (2022)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	X	X	X	No meta-analysis conducted	-
Wang (2021)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	X	X	X	X	No meta-analysis conducted	-
An (2018)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	No meta-analysis solely for children and adolescents conducted. Newer Review on WC and BMI available	-

- a Relevant data base considered
- b Clearly and adequately defined search terms/keywords
- c Inclusion/exclusion criteria adequately defined and explained
- d No critical studies missed
- e Risk of Bias conducted using adequate Tool
- f If Risk of Bias in single studies identified, then adequate actions taken in meta-analysis
- g Appropriateness of data extraction and transformations
- h Data pooling done in appropriate way
- i Adequate statistical method used

A detailed description of the criteria for the quality assessment of the reviews is provided in Table 3.2.

Table 3.18 Characteristics of the identified original studies investigating the effects of transportation noise on overweight

Paper	Cohort ^a (Country) ^b	Study type	Study population			Noise source (setting)	Exposure characterization ^c	Adjustment for air pollution	Exposure metric	Effect estimates (95% confidence interval) ^{d,e}
			N	Sex / Age	Follow-up					
de Bont (2021)	ECHOCAT, INMA (ES)	Cross-sectional	2,213	Both / 9-12 years	-	Road (residence)	GENCAT	-	L _{DEN}	<i>Road at residence:</i> BMI (z-score): 0.06 (0.00, 0.12) ^f per 8 dB WC (z-score): 0.02 (-0.03, 0.08) ^f per 8 dB Body fat % (z-score): 0.02 (-0.03, 0.07) ^f per 8 dB Overweight: 1.08 (0.97, 1.22) ^g per 8 dB
Bloemsma (2019a)	PIAMA (NL)	Cross-sectional	1,505 (12 years) / 707 (16 years)	Both / 12 and 16 years	-	Road, Rail (residence)	STAMINA	-	L _{DEN}	Waist circumference (cm): <i>Road at residence:</i> 12-year olds: 0.06 (-0.38, 0.50) ^f per 6.9 dB 16-year olds: -0.06 (-0.62, 0.51) ^f per 6.7 dB <i>Rail at residence:</i> 12-year olds: -0.27 (-0.70, 0.16) ^f per 8.45 dB 16-year olds: -0.28 (-0.78, 0.22) ^f per 7.6 dB
Bloemsma (2019b)	PIAMA (NL)	Cohort	3,680	Both / 3-17 years	1996 - 2016	Road, Rail (residence)	STAMINA	-	L _{DEN}	<i>Road at residence:</i> Overweight: 1.02 (0.90, 1.16) ^g per 6.9 dB <i>Rail at residence:</i> Overweight: 0.91 (0.79, 1.04) ^g per 8.9 dB
Wallas (2019)	BAMSE (SE)	Cohort	4,089	Both / 0-16 years	1994 - 2012	Road (residence)	Nordic prediction method	-	L _{DEN}	<i>Road at residence:</i> Change in BMI (kg/m ²): <1-year olds: -0.03 (-0.11, 0.06) ^f 1-3-year olds: -0.01 (-0.11, 0.09) ^f 4-7-year olds: -0.06 (-0.08, -0.04) ^f 8-11-year olds: 0.11 (0.08, 0.13) ^f 12-16-year olds: 0.20 (0.17, 0.22) ^f
Christensen (2016a)	DNBC (DK)	Cross-sectional	40,974	Both / 7 years	-	Road, Rail (residence)	SoundPLAN (Nordic Prediction Method)	-	L _{DEN}	<i>Road at residence:</i> BMI (z-score): 0.011 (-0.0058, 0.028) ^f Overweight: 1.06 (0.99, 1.12) ^g <i>Rail at residence:</i> BMI (z-score): -0.00037 (-0.019, 0.018) ^f Overweight: 1.01 (0.95, 1.09) ^g

^a BAMSE = Swedish population-based birth cohort, DNBC = Danish National Birth Cohort, ECHOCAT = Urban built environment and childhood obesity in Catalonia, INMA = Infancia y Medio Ambiente, Environment and Childhood, PIAMA = Dutch Prevention and Incidence of Asthma and Mite Allergy birth cohort study

^b DK = Denmark, ES = Spain, NL = Netherlands, SE = Sweden

^c GENCAT = Generalitat of Catalonia, STAMINA = Standard Model Instrumentation for Noise Assessments

^d BMI = Body Mass Index, WC = Waist Circumference

^e If not otherwise indicated, relative risks refers to a 10 dB increase in noise levels.

^f Beta

[§] Odds Ratio

Abbreviations: N = Number of participants

Multiple obesity markers including BMI, WC and overweight were investigated by the identified studies. The meta-analysis focuses on the risk for overweight, as most commonly quantified. In the included studies overweight was either defined according to reference charts from the International Obesity Task Force (Christensen et al., 2016a; Bloemsma et al., 2019b) or an one z-score deviation from the World Health Organization Growth Reference (de Bont et al., 2021). The results of the meta-analysis stratified by transportation noise is shown in Figure 3.13. The RR for being overweight in relation to residential road traffic noise was based on three studies and is statistically significant (RR: 1.06, 95%-CI: 1.01 to 1.12 per 10 dB increase in L_{DEN}). For railway noise, a non-significant association (RR: 0.97, 95%-CI: 0.850 to 1.103, per 10 dB) was identified based on two estimates. Considering both noise sources in a combined meta-analysis, a pooled RR of 1.03 (95%-CI: 0.99 to 1.08) per 10 dB increase in transportation noise in relation to overweight was detected. No study on aircraft noise was identified.

Two of the studies included in the meta-analysis were of a longitudinal design and, since the pooled risk for road traffic noise was significantly increased, the certainty of evidence for an association between road traffic noise and obesity was rated as *moderate*. Corresponding evidence for railway and aircraft noise was rated to be *very low*. Thus, overweight will be considered for the estimation of the burden of transportation noise on children’s and adolescent’s health.

Figure 3.13 Meta-analysis of original studies on *overweight* in relation to transportation noise at home, stratified by source. Relative risks refer to a 10 dB increase in L_{DEN} .

Random-effects REML model

3.2.6 Other Outcomes

In addition to the five health outcomes described in Subsection 3.2.1 to 3.2.5, we also conducted a literature search for annoyance, cancer, mental health, respiratory disorders and sleep disturbance.

However, in our search we found that most research on these health outcomes focussed on adult populations and very little research was conducted on children's and adolescent's health. The evidence for children and adolescents is summarised below.

Annoyance

For annoyance in children and adolescents, we identified one review (Stansfeld and Clark, 2015) and one original study (Grelat et al., 2016) in the literature search and three additional studies (Babisch et al., 2012; Quehl et al., 2021; van Kempen et al., 2009) by manual hand search. These studies indicate that children and adolescents are less annoyed by transportation noise than adults. A German study (Babisch et al., 2012) showed that 7.3 % (dichotomous scale) of 8 to 10 year old children and 16.4 % (collapsed 5-point scale) of 11 to 14 year old adolescents were annoyed or slightly annoyed by road traffic noise during daytime, which is less than in representative data in adults (Umweltbundesamt, 2009). A cross-sectional study by van Kempen et al. (2009) presented exposure-response curves for the association between severely annoyed children aged 9 to 12 years and aircraft noise at school and home. Compared to the exposure-response curve of the parents, the shape of the curves were comparable, however, children were less annoyed at levels above 55 dB with an increasing difference between the percentage of children and adults severely annoyed by noise. At noise levels of 60 dB 15% of the children and 17% percent of the parents were severely annoyed by aircraft noise at home. At 70 dB however, approximately 35% of the children were severely annoyed, whereas almost half of the adults were severely annoyed. A German study (Quehl et al., 2021) analysed the effect of nocturnal aircraft noise on short-term annoyance in primary school children and concluded that this noise source did not affect short-term annoyance in children. From this literature it seems plausible that children and adolescents are also annoyed by transportation noise. However, surveys may not be the adequate research methods to capture the degree of annoyance as this requires considerable reflection. It is well possible that noise creates anger in children and adolescents, which manifests as behavioural problems or aggressive behaviour.

Sleep Disturbance

The literature search resulted in the identification of one review (Basner and McGuire, 2018) and six original studies (Dzhambov et al., 2024; Pérez-Crespo et al., 2023; Blume et al., 2022; Arregi et al., 2022; Weyde et al., 2017a; Skrzypek et al., 2017). Based on the four papers identified by Basner and McGuire (2018), the review conducted for the WHO ENG, it was concluded that noise might lead to poorer self-reported sleep in children and adolescents, but that additional research was needed to examine the effect of noise on both subjective and objective measures of sleep in children and adolescents. Since then multiple new studies have been published of which only some indicate a significant association between transportation noise and different sleep measures, possibly depending on age. While Dzhambov et al. (2024) showed that a higher level of traffic noise exposure was associated with sleep problems in 8 to 12 year old children/adolescents, Blume et al. (2022) did not find indications of a significant association between night-time transportation noise and sleep composition in infants across the first year of life, except in children without siblings. Pérez-Crespo et al. (2023) observed that road traffic noise was related to a reduced total sleep time and longer wake time after sleep onset when collected with wrist-actigraphy. However, they did not find a significant association between road traffic noise and maternal-reported sleep disturbance in adolescents with a mean age of 12.3 years. Overall, the studies are inconsistent and further use different measures of sleep disturbance including sleep duration, time being awake after sleep onset, awakenings, parental-reported sleep disturbance, total sleeping problems or sleep composition. It is conceivable that children's sleep is less easily disturbed by noise compared to the sleep of adults. However, the literature is still too premature to draw any firm conclusions.

Mental Health

The literature search identified two reviews (Clark et al., 2020; Zare Sakhvidi et al., 2018) and two original studies (Zeng et al., 2023; Bloemsmas et al., 2022). One additional study (Newbury et al., 2024) was identified through manual search. These papers investigated different aspects of mental health including overall mental health, external problems e.g. aggression or delinquency, internal problems e.g. depression and anxiety, mental wellbeing, quality of life, and psychotic experiences, as well as behavioural problems, which we analysed separately (Subsection 3.2.2). Zare Sakhvidi et al. (2018) identified three studies of which none showed significant associations while Clark et al. (2020) concluded that the existing evidence does suggest a harmful effects at noise on mental health for children and adolescents, but that further research will help to understand whether this holds for the wide variety of mental health outcomes. Bloemsmas et al. (2022) did not find a significant association between road traffic and railway noise and poor mental wellbeing from the age 11 to 20 years. Zeng et al. (2023) did identify a significant association between transportation noise and external (β : 0.094, 95%-CI: 0.042 to 0.145) and internal problems (β : 0.076, 95%-CI: 0.028 to 0.125). The most recent study (Newbury et al., 2024) also did not find a significant association between residential noise exposure during childhood or adolescence and psychotic experiences or depression. However, they identified a significantly increased odds for anxiety by 1.19 (95%-CI: 1.03 to 1.38) for childhood noise exposure and by 1.22 (95%-CI: 1.02 to 1.45) for noise exposure during adolescence. Thus, the evidence might point to an association between transportation noise and multiple mental health outcomes, but further research is needed to understand the extent to which transportation noise affects mental health of children and adolescents.

Respiratory Disorders

For respiratory disorders only one original study (Wallas et al., 2020) was identified with children and adolescents as the study population, focusing on categorical road traffic noise during infancy and ever asthma up to age 16. The odds of ever having had asthma symptoms was non-significantly increased by 1.17 (95%-CI: 0.92 to 1.50) in the exposure group 45-54 vs. <45 dB and by 1.22 (95%-CI: 0.90 to 1.65) in the exposure group ≥ 55 vs. <45 dB. Having only identified one paper, further research is required to understand if transportation noise is associated with respiratory disorders in children and adolescents.

Cancer

During the literature search on cancer in children and adolescents we identified one review (Abbasi et al., 2023) and one original study (Erdmann et al., 2022), which was also the only study identified by the review. The nationwide Danish case-control study investigated the association between residential railway and road traffic noise and childhood cancer in children/adolescents aged 0 to 19. They concluded that their study did not indicate a strong role of transportation noise in the development of childhood cancer. However, for railway noise exposure evaluated at the least exposed façade, they identified an increased odds to develop lymphoma (OR: 1.46, 95%-CI: 1.02 to 2.09) per 10 dB increase. Thus, more research is needed to confirm these first observations of the association between transportation noise and childhood cancer.

3.3 Summary of Literature Review

3.3.1 Selection of Outcomes

An overview of the evidence rating and the selection for the EBD assessment for all evaluated health outcomes in relation to aircraft, railway and road traffic noise is presented in Table 3.19. For all markers of adverse birth outcomes and blood pressure, the evidence was rated as *very low* and thus, were not

considered for the EBD assessment. For cognition, no meta-analysis was conducted, because available studies used different tests for each cognitive marker and even within single domains of cognition (Section 3.2.4). However, given the biological plausibility and compelling evidence for an association of aircraft noise and reading and language comprehension, it will be considered for the estimation of the burden of transportation noise on children’s and adolescent’s health using the same ERF as in the previous assessment in 2020 (EEA, 2020). In the literature review we also identified compelling evidence for an association of residential road traffic noise and overweight as well as behavioural problems. Overweight and behavioural problems will therefore be considered for the EBD assessment. Behavioural problems is assessed with different scales that typically include hyperactivity/inattention, emotional symptoms, conduct problems and peer relationship problems. Studies that focussed exclusively on hyperactivity and inattention did not find consistent associations with noise and thus were not separately considered. For the outcomes describes in Section 3.2.6 (annoyance, sleep disturbance, mental health, respiratory disorders and cancer), too little research was found to derive exposure response functions and evidence rating.

Table 3.19 Overview of the updated evidence rating and selection of outcomes

Outcome	Road	Railway	Aircraft	Selected for EBD assessment
Adverse birth outcomes				
<i>Preterm birth</i>	<i>Very low</i>	<i>Very low</i>	<i>-*</i>	No
<i>Small for gestational age</i>	<i>Very low</i>	<i>Very low</i>	<i>-</i>	No
<i>Low birthweight</i>	<i>Very low</i>	<i>Very low</i>	<i>-</i>	No
<i>Continuous birthweight</i>	<i>Very low</i>	<i>Very low</i>	<i>-</i>	No
Behavioural problems				Yes
<i>noise at home:</i>	<i>Moderate</i>	<i>Low</i>	<i>Very low</i>	
<i>... noise at school:</i>	<i>Low</i>	<i>-</i>	<i>Very low</i>	
Hyperactivity/inattention				No ^{&}
<i>noise at home:</i>	<i>Low</i>	<i>Low</i>	<i>Very low</i>	
<i>noise at school</i>	<i>Low</i>	<i>-</i>	<i>Very low</i>	
Blood pressure				
<i>SBP/DBP (noise at school)</i>	<i>Low</i>	<i>-</i>	<i>-</i>	No
<i>SBP/DBP (noise at home)</i>	<i>Low</i>	<i>Low</i>	<i>-</i>	No
Cognition				
<i>Reading and language in children</i>	<i>-</i>	<i>-</i>	<i>Moderate[§]</i>	Yes
Overweight	<i>Moderate</i>	<i>Very low</i>	<i>-</i>	Yes

[§] Not evaluated in this literature review, evidence rating according to WHO ENG; * (-) indicates that no study was identified; & this domain is included in behavioural problems

3.3.2 Exposure-Response Functions

The proposed exposure-response functions (ERFs) of outcomes to be considered in the risk assessment of transportation noise on children’s and adolescent’s health are shown in Table 3.20. The proposed ERFs are based on the evidence and results of the review and meta-analyses presented in the previous chapters of this report. The literature review revealed that for some noise sources, only very few studies were available, which prevents from deriving source specific ERFs. For behavioural problems

and overweight, very few studies addressed railway noise and aircraft noise and thus we used the ERF for residential road traffic noise for all three sources. Conversely, for cognition, most studies addressed aircraft noise and thus the aircraft noise ERF is used for all three transportation noise sources. The underlying biological pathways involved for the different noise sources are presumed to be similar. Of note, around the airports, aircraft is the most dominant noise source, and in urban setting road traffic noise is most dominant. This implies that available studies focussing on these settings are unlikely to provide meaningful results for railway noise or other background noise sources (in particular in the lower exposure range), as they would be mostly masked by the dominant noise source. In this situation absence of data/evidence should not be confused with evidence for absence of an association.

The available research in children and adolescents is very limited when it comes to the question at which levels the negative health effects start to occur. In a previous systematic assessments of the effect threshold using studies on cardiometabolic outcomes in adults (Engelmann et al., 2023), a values of 45 dB (L_{den}) was identified as the most plausible effect threshold. This reference value is also taken for behavioural problems and overweight in children and adolescents as little conflicting evidence was found. For reading and oral comprehension, we chose the same relationship previously used in the Noise in Europe Report by the EEA (2020) with an effect threshold of 50 dB (L_{den}).

Table 3.20 Overview of the proposed ERFs and outcomes to be considered in EBD assessments on children’s and adolescent’s health

Outcome	Source	ERF	Reference
Behavioural problems (prevalence)	Road, Rail, Air at home	Relative risk derived from residential road traffic noise RR = 1.073 (95%-CI: 1.009, 1.142) per 10 dB with reference $L_{DEN} = 45$ dB	Meta-analyses Chapter 3.2.2, Figure 3.5
Overweight (prevalence)	Road, Rail, Air at home	Relative risk derived from residential road traffic noise RR = 1.063 (95%-CI: 1.007, 1.122) per 10 dB with reference $L_{DEN} = 45$ dB	Meta-analyses Chapter 3.2.5, Figure 3.13
Reading and oral comprehension (prevalence)	Road, Rail, Air at school	$P(\text{reading}) = 1 / (1 + \exp(-(\ln(0.1/0.9) + (\ln(1.38)/10 \cdot (L_{DEN} - 50))))$ if $L_{DEN} \geq 50$ dB and 0.1 if $L_{DEN} < 50$ dB	Clark et al. (2006) and van Kempen (2008)

4 PART II: Estimation of the Burden of Environmental Noise on the Health of Children and Adolescents

4.1 Environmental Burden of Disease: Methodology

The environmental burden of disease (EBD) refers to the health impact of an environmental exposure of interest assessed through various indicators that may combine the effects of both, mortality and morbidity. The burden is commonly expressed using disability-adjusted life years (DALYs), a metric that integrates two components: years of life lost (YLL) due to premature death, calculated as the number of deaths multiplied by the remaining life expectancy at the age of death, and years lived with disability (YLD) due to diseases or injury, determined by multiplying the number of cases (prevalence) by a disability weight (DW) reflecting the severity of the disease. Three inputs are needed for this calculation: the *exposure distribution* of the population, which combined with the *ERF* allows to calculate the population attributable fraction (PAF). Multiplying the PAF with the *baseline health state* of the population yields the attributable burden (Prüss-Üstün et al., 2003). Baseline health state is either directly available as YLL, YLD or DALY or otherwise calculated by multiplying the prevalence (or incidence) with the disability weight.

In this assessment, the environmental health burden due to noise exposure for children and adolescents follows the same methods as described for adult outcomes in detail in the report from Engelmann et al (2023). We estimated the burden of disease for three different quantification thresholds. Note that the quantification threshold refers to the level used for quantifying the burden of disease whereas the effect threshold (chapter 3.3.2) refers to the reference value used for calculating the relative risk:

1. The reporting threshold for the END is 55 dB and thus, only the health burden above the END reporting threshold was quantified in our main analysis. This implies that effects from noise exposure between the reference value (45 dB) and the END reporting threshold are not quantified in our main analysis.
2. As a comparison scenario, we calculated the burden of disease using the WHO ENG thresholds of 53 dB L_{den} for road traffic noise, 54 dB L_{den} for railway noise and 45 dB L_{den} for aircraft noise.
3. Since our literature review suggests that transportation noise can affect health and well-being even below the WHO ENG guideline levels, we also estimated the number of children and adolescents using the effect threshold of 45 dB as quantification threshold. For reading and oral comprehension, we used 50 dB as the reference value in scenario 3 due to the threshold given by the ERF.

The calculation is based on the following assumptions and input data:

Exposure distribution: Distribution of noise exposure at the place of residence in each country was derived from the END. The END is an European Union (EU) legislation, which requires EU countries to prepare and publish noise maps for road, rail and air traffic inside agglomerations of more than 100,000 inhabitants as well as for major roads, railways and airports outside agglomerations. Major roads are defined as roads with a traffic of at least 3 million vehicle passes a year, major railways as railways with a traffic of at least 30,000 train passes a year, and major airports as airports with a traffic of at least 50,000 take-offs or landings a year (European Commission, 2024). The 2022 data on population exposed to noise from road, rail and aircraft includes data from the 27 EU countries and four additional EEA countries (Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Iceland, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Liechtenstein, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia,

Spain, Sweden, and Switzerland). Thus, the burden due to transportation noise with focus on the health effects in children and adolescents was calculated for 31 countries (EEA-31). Due to the incomplete data reporting for certain countries, gap-filling was undertaken to address any missing information and provide a comprehensive assessment. Information on completeness of the countries can be found on the EEA Datahub webpage (EEA, 2024).

Exposure assessment for all scenarios is based on noise data reported for 2021 and extrapolations described in the 2023 report (Engelmann et al., 2023). Briefly, relative fractions of population exposed to lower END thresholds were estimated based on the number of people exposed above the END thresholds considering: 1) a normal distribution for road traffic noise exposure inside agglomerations – individual values for each EEA member country – and 2) an exponential distribution for major road traffic, railway and aircraft noise exposure outside agglomerations as well as for railway and aircraft noise exposure inside agglomerations. Once the relative fractions below the END thresholds were obtained per each noise source, a non-uniform distribution across the 5 dB noise bands was calculated to obtain the number of people exposed to the different noise sources at 1 dB resolution, using the mean gradient in % per dB per each 5 dB interval.

ERF: The ERF for behavioural problems, overweight, reading and oral comprehension for all three noise sources (road, railway, and aircraft) are shown in Table 3.20. A reference value of $L_{den} = 45$ dB was used for behavioural problems and overweight and 50 dB for reading and oral comprehension.

Baseline health state: As most children in Europe start school at the age of 6, and to stay consistent between health outcomes, the age range for this EBD assessment was chosen to be 6 to 17 years. Regarding health input data for behavioural problems we used age specific YLD rates provided by the Global Burden of Disease (GBD) study (IHME, 2023) from 2019 for each considered country. In the absence of an outcome “total behavioural problems”, we used age-specific YLDs rates provided by the GBD study for “attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder” and “conduct disorder”, which are shown in Table 10.2 in Annex 3. We conducted separate burden of disease calculations for these two outcomes and the final number of children and adolescents with behavioural problems attributable to transportation noise was obtained by summing up the results of these two outcomes.

The prevalence rates for overweight were obtained from the Global Health Observatory (GHO) data (WHO, 2017) provided by the WHO. Here, the newest data were from 2016 and the prevalence rates for Czech Republic were not available, which therefore had to be excluded from the EBD assessment for overweight. The rates used for this report are shown in Table 10.1 in Annex 3. For overweight there is no DW to calculate corresponding YLDs or DALYs. However, the number of overweight children and adolescents related to noise exposure (attributable prevalent cases) can be estimated.

For reading and oral comprehension, no baseline YLD are available from (IHME, 2023). The prevalence is directly obtained from the ERF (as described in Engelmann et al. (2023)) and thus provides the prevalence rate. To obtain DALYs for reading and oral comprehension the prevalent cases attributable to noise exposure were multiplied by the DW for mild cognitive impairments with a value of 0.013, according to the update on DWs for noise-related health states in Europe (Charalampous et al., 2024; WHO Europe, 2024).

Calculation of the PAF was conducted for each 1-dB exposure category and summed up to obtain the total PAF attributable to noise. We assumed that the number of YLL for the selected outcomes is negligible and thus did not include this in the calculations. by considering the and the was obtained by multiplying the ERF with the mean

4.2 Environmental Burden of Disease: Results

The EBD analyses revealed that, irrespective of the noise environment (inside or outside urban areas), road noise was the primary source of health impairment in children and adolescents across all outcomes and comparison scenarios. Overall, the greatest impact on health was estimated to be on reading and oral comprehension, followed by behavioural problems and overweight. The EBD assessment for scenario 1 showed that of the children and adolescents aged 6 to 17 years living in agglomerations or near major transportation noise sources with noise levels above L_{den} 55 dB in Europe in 2021, 63,193 children/adolescents had an increased risk of suffering behavioural problems, 563,774 children/adolescents had increased reading and oral comprehension impairments and 271,561 children/adolescents had a higher risk of being overweight. Table 4.1 summarizes the number of children and adolescents affected by each outcome due to all three transportation noise sources inside and outside agglomeration areas. Furthermore, Table 4.2 summarizes the corresponding DALYs from behavioural problems and reading and oral comprehension for all three transportation noise sources inside and outside agglomeration areas. DALYs due to behavioural problems were equivalent to 3,884 years and for reading and oral comprehension to 7,329 years. More detailed tables including numbers per country can be found in Annex 4 (Table 11.1 to Table 11.3). The number of children and adolescents affected by behavioural problems and overweight for the lower and upper CI of the RR are shown in Annex 5 in Table 12.1.

Table 4.1 Number of children and adolescents (6-17 years) with behavioural problems, reading impairments and overweight attributable to transportation noise above the END threshold (55 dB) in 2021, EEA-31 (for 95% confidence interval, see Appendix 5, Table 12.1)

		Behavioural problems	Reading and oral Comprehension	Overweight
Inside urban areas	Road	41,740	355,837	173,514
	Rail	4,608	41,807	20,440
	Air	508	5,547	2,249
Outside urban areas	Road	11,143	116,532	48,576
	Rail	4,961	41,086	25,704
	Air	233	2,965	1,078
Total		63,193	563,774	271,561

Table 4.2 Estimated DALYs attributable to transportation noise above the END threshold (55 dB) for children and adolescents (6-17 years) in 2021, EEA-31

		Behavioural problems	Reading and oral Comprehension
Inside urban areas	Road	2,520	4,626
	Rail	294	543
	Air	30	72
Outside urban areas	Road	698	1,515
	Rail	330	534
	Air	12	39
Total		3,884	7,329

According to comparison scenario 2 (WHO guideline values) 80,264 children/adolescents had increased risk of suffering behavioural problems, 607,391 children/adolescents had increased reading and oral comprehension impairments and 344,219 children/adolescents had a higher risks to be overweight due to transportation noise (Table 4.3). Corresponding estimated DALYs were 4,950 for behavioural problems and 7,896 for reading and oral comprehension impairments (Table 4.4). The number of children and adolescents affected by behavioural problems and overweight for the lower and upper CI of the RR are shown in Annex 5 in Table 12.2.

Table 4.3 Number of children and adolescents (6-17 years) a behavioural problems, reading impairments and overweight attributable to transportation noise above the WHO guideline values in 2021, EEA-31 (for 95% confidence interval, see Appendix 5, Table 12.2)

		Behavioural problems	Reading and oral Comprehension	Overweight
Inside urban areas	Road	52,726	385,696	219,318
	Rail	5,276	44,101	23,384
	Air	2,421	7,641	10,587
Outside urban areas	Road	13,178	123,683	57,558
	Rail	5,141	41,846	26,433
	Air	1,522	4,424	6,939
Total		80,264	607,391	344,219

Note: WHO guideline value for road, rail and air are 53 dB, 54 dB, and 45 dB, respectively.

Table 4.4 Estimated DALYs attributable to transportation noise above the WHO guideline values for children and adolescents (6-17 years) in 2021, EEA-31

		Behavioural problems	Reading and oral Comprehension
Inside urban areas	Road	3,193	5,014
	Rail	337	573
	Air	152	99
Outside urban areas	Road	828	1,608
	Rail	343	544
	Air	97	58
Total		4,950	7,896

Note: WHO guideline value for road, rail and air are 53 dB, 54 dB, and 45 dB, respectively.

Finally, applying an effect threshold equal to the reference value (scenario 3) resulted in 127,272 children/adolescents with behavioural problems, 633,290 children/adolescents with reading and oral comprehension impairment and 545,295 children/adolescents being overweight due to transportation noise. As a consequence, 7,920 and 8,233 DALYs from behavioural problems and reading and oral comprehension, respectively, were attributed to transportation noise. The number of children and adolescents affected by behavioural problems and overweight for the lower and upper CI of the RR are shown in Annex 5 in Table 12.3.

Table 4.5 Number of children and adolescents (6-17 years) a behavioural problems, reading impairments and overweight attributable to transportation noise above the Scenario 3 thresholds* in 2021, EEA-31 (for 95% confidence interval, see Appendix 5, Table 12.3)

		Behavioural problems	Reading and oral Comprehension	Overweight
Inside urban areas	Road	80,543	401,469	336,607
	Rail	9,781	48,109	43,265
	Air	2,421	7,641	10,587
Outside urban areas	Road	25,498	128,288	111,399
	Rail	7,507	43,359	36,498
	Air	1,522	4,424	6,939
Total		127,272	633,290	545,295

* Scenario 3 thresholds are $L_{DEN}=45$ dB for behavioural problems and overweight and 50 dB for reading and oral comprehension.

Table 4.6 Estimated DALYs attributable to transportation noise above the Scenario 3 thresholds* for children and adolescents (6-17 years) in 2021, EEA-31W

		Behavioural problems	Reading and oral Comprehension
Inside urban areas	Road	4,903	5,219
	Rail	626	625
	Air	152	99
Outside urban areas	Road	1,640	1,668
	Rail	502	564
	Air	97	58
Total		7,920	8,233

* Scenario 3 thresholds are $L_{DEN}=45$ dB for behavioural problems and 50 dB for reading and oral comprehension.

5 PART III: Evaluating the Scientific Evidence on Interventions to Reduce the Risk and Impact from Environmental Noise on the Health of Children and Adolescents in Europe

5.1 Method of Literature Review

This research employs an Umbrella+ review framework to systematically collect and evaluate the interventions designed to reduce environmental noise exposure among children and adolescents in Europe. The starting point for this review is the "*WHO Environmental Noise Guidelines for the European Region: A Systematic Review of Transport Noise Interventions and Their Impacts on Health*" by Brown and van Kamp (2017), which covered the search period from 1980 to 2014.

Brown and van Kamp (2017) provided a comprehensive analysis on the impact of transport noise interventions on health in children and adults. Their review systematically examined interventions against noise from road traffic, railways, and air traffic with evaluated outcomes including annoyance, sleep disturbance, cognitive impairment in children, and cardiovascular effects. The authors introduced a novel conceptual framework to classify the types of noise interventions, which facilitated the evaluation and comparison of interventions across various noise sources and health outcomes. Their framework was influenced by models used in air pollution research and adapted to the specifics of noise control, which heavily depends on the propagation paths from the source to the receivers. Five broad categories of interventions were defined (Figure 5.1):

- Type A (Source Interventions): These involve changes at the noise origin, such as regulations reducing emissions from vehicles or operational restrictions at airports.
- Type B (Path Interventions): These are measures taken to alter the path of noise transmission, including the use of barriers and insulation improvements in buildings to protect inhabitants from external noise.
- Type C (New/Closed Infrastructure): This category includes changes due to the construction of new transport infrastructure or the closure of existing ones, significantly altering noise exposure levels in nearby areas.
- Type D (Other Physical Interventions): These interventions encompass modifications to the built environment that indirectly affect noise exposure, such as urban planning decisions that increase the distance between noise sources and residential areas.
- Type E (Education/Communication Interventions): These strategies aim to change individual or group behaviours and perceptions about noise, potentially mitigating the health impacts of noise exposure without physically altering noise levels.

Figure 5.1 Types of intervention that impact on noise exposure and/or community health outcomes (adapted from Brown and van Kamp (2017))

Out of 43 individual transport noise intervention studies analysed in their systematic review, the majority addressed traffic noise (77%), with fewer focusing on aircraft (16%) and railway noise (7%) (Brown and van Kamp, 2017). Annoyance was the primary health outcome evaluated, followed by assessments of sleep disturbance, cardiovascular effects, and children’s cognitive development. The review emphasized the challenge in conducting meta-analyses due to the diverse methods used in individual studies and the magnitudes of noise exposure changes involved. Despite the variability in study designs and outcomes, several interventions showed significant associations with changes in health outcomes, suggesting potential benefits regardless of the intervention or noise source type. While the review primarily targeted the general population, the availability of interventional studies specifically focusing on children and adolescents was notably scarce. Among the examined studies, only one explicitly addressed this target population.

5.1.1 Study Eligibility

In addition to the information provided by the review undertaken by Brown and van Kamp (2017), we conducted a systematic search in PubMed to identify eligible peer-reviewed reviews or original studies published after 2014. We utilized the PICOS approach by Morgan et al. (2018) to define inclusion and exclusion for each element (population, interventions, comparators, outcomes and study design), which are described in Table 5.1. Eligible studies focused on interventional research involving children and adolescents under 18 years of age in Europe. These studies targeted transportation noise sources including road traffic, railways, and air traffic, examining various interventions to reduce noise, strategies for managing noise, actions for noise control, or relevant educational or community campaigns (Figure 5.1). The outcomes of interest included annoyance, sleep disturbance, cognitive development, behavioural problems, cardiovascular disease, and adverse birth outcomes. Eligible studies were required to evaluate the intervention by comparing the conditions before and after implementation and reporting changes in noise exposure outcomes, health outcomes, or outcomes related to knowledge, attitude, or behaviour. The search was limited to English published articles after 2014.

Table 5.1 Criteria for inclusion and exclusion of literature based on population, intervention, comparator, outcome and study design

PECOS	Inclusion	Exclusion
Population	Children and adolescents (i.e., individuals under 18 years of age) in Europe	Adults, non-human populations (in vivo, in vitro, other)
Intervention	Various noise-reducing interventions targeting transportation noise exposure from road, rail, and aircraft	
Comparator	No intervention, a different intervention, unexposed or less exposed control groups, or conventional or existing interventions	
Outcome	Change in noise exposure (i.e., sound pressure level measured in decibel), noise annoyance, sleep disturbance, cognitive impairment, behavioural problems, cardiovascular disease, adverse birth outcomes	Outcomes of unclear clinical health relevance, e.g., epigenetics, DNA methylation
Study type	<p>Systematic reviews with and without meta-analysis or major pooled analyses representative for Europe or high-quality original studies</p> <p>Umbrella reviews, scoping reviews, key reports</p> <p>In case of insufficient evidence from systematic reviews, original studies from Europe of high quality not included in a review can be included.</p>	
Time period	1 January 2015 to 29 February 2024	

5.1.2 Literature Search

The detailed search terms used in the PubMed search are provided in

Table 8.2 in Annex 1. Additionally, we searched the reference lists of retrieved eligible publications to identify additional relevant studies. The results of the literature search are presented using the PRISMA flow diagram.

5.1.3 Data Extraction and Findings Synthesis

Data were extracted from reviews and original studies that met the predetermined eligibility criteria. The extraction process was performed by one researcher (XJ) and subsequently reviewed by two others (DV, MR).

The findings from each study were collected and organized based on both the noise source and health outcomes they addressed. These findings were then classified into five main types of interventions, as suggested by Brown and van Kamp (2017): A) Source interventions, B) Path interventions, C) New/closed infrastructure, D) Other physical interventions, and E) Education or communication interventions.

5.2 Results of Literature Review

The search strategy performed in PubMed yielded 1,379 publications. Of these, 74 adhered to systematic review methodologies, including 47 strictly classified as systematic reviews. An additional five original studies were identified through a manual search, bringing the total number of publications to 1,384. After screening titles and abstracts, six publications were deemed eligible and included in this Umbrella+ review, in addition to the review by Brown and van Kamp (2017). These comprised one systematic review and five original studies. The PRISMA flow diagram is shown in Figure 9.6 in Annex 2.

The one systematic review, conducted by Fernandes et al. (2023), explored the effects of school-based interventions on mitigating exposure from both indoor and outdoor stressors, including traffic noise, among primary school-aged children in urban areas of Europe and other high-income countries. This review, however, did not identify any interventional studies specifically aimed at reducing transportation noise at schools. Consequently, the review by Brown and van Kamp (2017) remains the most recent systematic review on interventions related to transportation noise.

In total, five original studies meeting the eligibility criteria were identified (Table 5.2). The study by Hygge et al. (2002), which was previously included in the review by Brown and van Kamp (2017), focused on a Type C intervention related to the relocation of Munich International Airport in Germany. Additionally, four new studies were discovered through manual search. These included another paper on the Munich Airport relocation study, which assessed the physiological and psychological impacts of increased noise levels on local communities, also classified as a Type C intervention. The remaining studies consist of two that explore Type E educational interventions and one that examines Type D interventions, specifically acoustic treatments in schools.

Hygge et al. (2002) investigated the impact of aircraft noise resulting from the relocation of Munich International Airport on children's cognition. Utilizing a natural experimental design, the study implemented a prospective cohort approach with controls matched based on socioeconomic status. Three data collection waves were conducted: baseline (6 months prior to the airport changeover), and two follow-ups at one and two years post-change. The study included 326 children with a mean age of 10 years at baseline. Exposure levels were measured using $L_{Aeq,24h}$ at school only. Following the relocation, an increase in noise exposure (+9 dB) was observed for children near the new airport ($n = 111$), while a decrease (-14 dB) was noted for those near the old airport ($n = 65$). Control participants ($n = 107$) experienced no change in exposure level. Outcome measures included various cognitive assessments such as short- and long-term memory, reading, attention, and speech perception. High response rates were maintained throughout the study. Various statistical tests, including interactions,

were conducted to analyse the data. The results indicated that children exposed to noise near the old airport had reduced long-term memory and reading comprehension compared to their unexposed peers when the airport was operational. However, these deficits disappeared two years after the airport's closure. Conversely, children near the new airport exhibited reduced memory performance and reading comprehension two years after the new airport opened, compared to their control group. These cognitive deficits were particularly pronounced in the most challenging segments of the word-list reading test and the long-term recall task.

In addition to the cognitive impact analysis of the Munich Airport relocation by Hygge et al. (2002), Evans et al. (1998) studied the physiological stress effects of increased aircraft noise on 217 children aged 9 to 11. This longitudinal study compared children in noise-impaired areas near the airport with those in quieter controlled areas, matched based on socioeconomic status. Measurements were taken six months before, six months after, and 18 months after the airport opened. Noise exposure was quantified using 24-hr dB(A) L_{eq} and peak noise levels (dB(A) L_{01}). Prior to the airport's inauguration, noise levels were similar in both areas (dB(A) L_{eq} 53, dB(A) L_{01} 63), but post-inauguration, levels rose to dB(A) L_{eq} 62 and dB(A) L_{01} 73 near the airport, higher than in the control area (dB(A) L_{eq} 55, dB(A) L_{01} 64). The analysis, utilizing repeated measures MANOVA, showed significant increases in systolic blood pressure, which rose from an average of 97.2 mmHg to 102.4 mmHg in noise-impacted children. Significant rises were also observed in epinephrine, from 229.2 ng/hr to 341.9 ng/hr, and norepinephrine. Changes in diastolic blood pressure were marginal, and cortisol levels showed no systematic changes. Quality of life, measured on a scale from 40 to 200 where higher values indicate better perceived quality, significantly declined in noise-impacted communities from 110.3 to 104.8 over 18 months post-airport opening, while it remained relatively stable in quieter areas, changing from 112.5 to 109.6.

An educational intervention, conducted by Christidou et al. (2015), explored the efficacy of the 'Young Noise Researchers' educational scenario aimed at enhancing noise awareness among preschool children in Greece in a pretest-posttest design with 52 children. The intervention was conducted in public kindergarten classes. Over a four-week period, teachers implemented nine activities designed according to principles of context-based, socio-cognitive, and multimodal teaching. These activities ranged from identifying everyday noises to discussions about noise annoyance and health impacts. The assessment involved interviews conducted before and after the intervention, with questions exploring children's definition of noise, their experiences of noise annoyance, and their awareness of the health implications of noise (e.g. "Do you know what noise is?" and "How do you feel when you hear a noise?"). Statistical tests such as chi-squared and dependent samples t-tests were performed to compare pre- and post-intervention responses. This analysis revealed improvements in children's understanding of noise, including recognition of traffic noise as part of their daily noise exposure, understanding the subjective and annoying nature of noise, and acknowledging its health effects. Despite these gains, children's overall noise awareness did not significantly increase in all areas, such as distinguishing between sound and noise. The authors emphasized the importance of systematic education on noise from an early age to foster effective noise-awareness and coping strategies among children, suggesting that these educational approaches may require further refinement.

Similarly, the study by Gilles and Paul (2014) evaluated the effectiveness of a governmental public health campaign in Belgium called 'Iets Minder is de Max' ('Anything less is the max'). Although this campaign focused on recreational noise, its intervention demonstrated broader benefits. The campaign targeted high school students aged 14 to 18 years, raising awareness about the dangers of recreational noise. It was widely advertised through television and radio advertisements, social media platforms, posters, and a specialized website. The study utilized pre- and post-campaign questionnaires to measure shifts in attitudes towards noise among 547 Flemish high school students. Results indicated a significant improvement in attitudes towards noise, as assessed by the Youth Attitudes to Noise Scale (YANS) and the Beliefs About Hearing Protection and Hearing Loss (BAHPHL).

While the campaign primarily focused on recreational noise, it also addressed attitudes towards daily noises, including traffic noise, as part of the YANS. This demonstrates the effectiveness of the campaign in altering attitudes towards noise in general, including traffic noise.

An additional study, by Polewczyk and Jarosz (2020), evaluated the impact of acoustic treatments in classrooms on the performance and well-being of primary school children in Poland. These treatments involved the installation of sound-absorbing materials in classrooms, corridors, and other school spaces to enhance the learning environment by reducing noise levels and improving speech intelligibility. Originally, the school had poor acoustic conditions due to its size and construction materials, characterized by excessive noise levels and low speech intelligibility. The study utilized pre- and post-treatment measurements of sound levels and speech transmission indexes to quantify the improvement in acoustic conditions. Additionally, surveys were conducted among 378 students and 44 teachers to assess perceived changes in the auditory environment and its effects on their activities. The results demonstrated that these acoustic treatments significantly improved various aspects of children's performance, including enhanced listening skills and concentration. Furthermore, the study noted improvements in children's well-being, evidenced by a decrease in levels of physical and mental aggression among students, as observed by their teachers. This suggests that better acoustic environments in schools can mitigate the effects of external noise disturbances, including traffic noise, thereby supporting both educational outcomes and student health.

Table 5.2 Characteristics of the identified original studies investigating interventions on environmental noise interventions in children and adolescents in Europe

Authors	Intervention	Population, study design	Change in noise exposure levels ^a	Health outcome measure(s)	Change in health outcomes	Outcome changed with exposure change? (statistical significance)	Confounders adjusted for in analyses
Evans et al. (1998)	Airport relocation (Type C)	217 children (mean age 9.9 years) living near the new airport or in nearby quiet communities, longitudinal study with three waves	Increase in 24-hr dB(A) L_{eq} from 53 to 62 and 24-hr dB(A) L_{01} from 63 to 73 in impacted areas near the new airport ^(a)	Physiological stress (blood pressure, epinephrine, norepinephrine, cortisol), quality of life (KINDL index)	Increase in stress markers and decrease in quality of life	Yes (significant)	Socioeconomic status, age, family size, parental occupation and education, baseline hearing ability, attrition
Hygge et al. (2002)	Airport relocation (Type C)	326 children (mean age 10.4 years) living near both old and new airports or in controlled quiet areas, longitudinal study with three waves	Measured at school only. Old airport: decrease in 24-hr dB(A) L_{eq} from 68 to 54. New airport: Increase in 24-hr dB(A) L_{eq} from 53 to 62	Cognitive performance tests (memory, reading comprehension)	Improved cognitive outcomes at old airport post-closure, impaired at new airport	Yes (significant)	Socioeconomic status, age, ethnicity, number of family members, parental occupation, and education
Christidou et al. (2015)	Educational scenario (Type E)	52 preschool children aged 4.5-5.5 years, pre- and post-	Not directly measured; educational context	Noise awareness and understanding, assessed through content analysis of semi-structured	Improvements in noise awareness and understanding post-intervention	Yes (varied significance)	Methodological controls for data consistency and intervention standardization

Authors	Intervention	Population, study design	Change in noise exposure levels ^a	Health outcome measure(s)	Change in health outcomes	Outcome changed with exposure change? (statistical significance)	Confounders adjusted for in analyses
		intervention measurements		interviews with the children			
Gilles and Paul (2014)	Public health campaign (Type E)	547 high school students aged 14-18 years, survey-based study before and after campaign	Not directly measured; campaign context	Self-reported attitudes towards noise, measured using surveys	Improvement in attitudes towards noise post-campaign	Yes (significant)	Confounders not specified
Polewczyk and Jarosz (2020)	Classroom acoustic treatments (Type D)	378 primary school students aged 6-14 years, pre- and post-intervention measurements	L _{Aeq} reduced by 6-10 dB across various school environments: canteen (~10 dB), corridors (~9 dB), sport hall (~7 dB), and after-school clubs (~6 dB)	Student and teacher assessments of performance and well-being, focusing on concentration, fatigue, aggression, and speech communication	Significant improvements noted by teachers in concentration, reduced fatigue, and aggression. Students reported improved concentration and reduced sound levels, no change in self-perceived fatigue	Yes (significant)	Confounders not specified

^a dB(A) = A-weighted equivalent continuous sound level; dB(A) L₀₁ = the dB(A) level exceeded 1% of the time over the 24-hr sampling period.

6 Discussion

The previous reports on environmental noise in Europe (EEA, 2020, 2014) focused their EBD assessments mainly on the adult population and included only one outcome for children (reading and oral comprehension). Emerging evidence indicates, however, that transportation noise affects further outcomes in children. In our Umbrella+ review combining high quality systematic reviews with recent original research, we found also moderate evidence for an association between transportation noise with behavioural problems and overweight. Thus, this EBD assessment not only focused on reading and oral comprehension, but also included the outcomes behavioural problems and overweight in children and adolescents. It has to be emphasized that research on health effects of noise in children and adolescents is still scarce. This implies that for the three main outcomes certainty of evidence was rated to be moderate for one transportation noise source but not for the two others. Further, evidence for many other outcomes is missing, although to some extent plausible from a distress pathway point of view.

Our assessment shows that children's and adolescent's health and well-being are affected by transportation noise and that the overall impact across Europe is substantial. Based on the noise exposure situation in Europe in 2021, 63,193 children/adolescents with noise-induced behavioural problems, 563,774 children/adolescents with reading and oral comprehension impairments and 271,561 children/adolescents with overweight are attributable to noise above the END reporting limit of 55 dB L_{DEN} . This translated to 3,884 DALYs for behavioural problems and 7,329 DALYs for reading and oral comprehension. As most likely effects of noise on children start to occur below the END thresholds, these numbers are likely an underestimation the true impact.

6.1 Uncertainty considerations

This assessment is based on assumptions and thus also subject to uncertainty. The highest uncertainty comes from the lack of research. It is conceivable that with further research the evidence for other health outcomes might also be compelling pointing to further noise-related health outcomes in children and adolescents. Nevertheless, we can also not exclude that the current ERF are overestimating certain risk. For instance, only few source specific studies were available and thus we used the same ERF for all three sources even in the absence of direct evidence of an association for certain noise sources.

One key limitation of the EBD assessment is the underestimation of the number of children and adolescents affected by transportation noise. This is due to two main factors. First, the noise data reported under the END only report big agglomerations and major roads, railways and airports. This leads to areas outside the scope of the Environmental Noise Directive not being assessed in this study. There are children/adolescents living outside the areas included in END, which are not included in the present results even though they would be affected by noise. Further, the countries only report data above the END threshold of 55 dB and this was used as the threshold for quantification in our main EBD assessment. We conducted two comparison scenarios with lower quantification thresholds. For these calculations we had to rely on extrapolated exposure values, which introduces some uncertainty that could produce under or overestimation. Furthermore, the numbers for children/adolescents affected by aircraft noise might not be fully representative for the situation today since the late effects of the Covid pandemic resulted in sustained restricted air traffic in 2021 for which the noise data were modelled. The data reported by each country were based on the same model. However, differences might still occur between countries due to the selection of areas, for example including only the busiest roads or all roads within agglomerations (EEA, 2020). Further, differences might occur due to the input data used by each country, for example the traffic flow data. The data reported under the END are based on noise at the most exposed home façade and do not take noise at school into account,

whereas the studies on reading and oral comprehension considered exposure at school. We thus relied on residential exposure, which may be on average lower than schools that are often centrally located.

The EBD assessment relies on baseline health state data. These data may have some uncertainty for all three outcomes. For instance, we could not find data on the prevalence of behavioural problems and thus relied on only two out of several domains related to behavioural problems in children and adolescents: ADHD and conduct problems. Thus, we most likely underestimated the burden of behavioural problems. Uncertainty regarding the prevalence of overweight and reading impairment may result in an over- or underestimation of the corresponding burden of disease.

Umbrella+ review is an efficient methods for reviewing the literature and deriving ERF. However, using reviews as a starting point in our meta-analysis, we partly relied on decisions made by other authors e.g. eligibility of studies or evidence rating. Although prospective cohort studies are considered most reliable, we analysed mostly prevalent outcomes, which are most often analysed with cross-sectional designs. Therefore, we not only included cohort studies, but also cross-sectional studies. Another important point is the potential of double counting. In our search we identified multiple cohorts from the same country. Although we ensured that no cohort was included twice in the same meta-analysis, we did include different cohorts from the same country. Therefore, we were not able to ensure that no individual was included in multiple cohorts. However, overall the proportion of the potential of double counted individuals is very low. On the level of single studies there may be several uncertainties. For instance, road traffic noise is correlated with air pollution. However, most of the noise studies adjusted in their analysis for air pollution and thus we would not expect bias from co-exposure to air pollution.

For all assumptions in this assessment we made the most realistic assumptions. In case of doubts, we preferred a conservative choice. Thus, the overall result is more likely an underestimation of the true burden of noise for children and adolescents. Note that this assessment only considers transportation noise and neither other environmental noise sources such as industry or military noise nor leisure noise from personal music player or sport events. Future noise research in this age group is warranted to better understand the impact of noise.

6.2 Noise interventions

Given the burden of disease in children/adolescents from transportation noise, interventions to minimize the health impact are warranted. Our Umbrella+ review on intervention reveals a spectrum of strategies, from educational initiatives to infrastructural modifications, each demonstrating potential to mitigate noise exposure and improve educational and well-being outcomes. However, the review identifies significant research gaps, particularly in studies focused specifically on the impacts of transportation noise on children and adolescents where some exposure-outcome pairs are missing, most likely reflecting the low priority of this public health problem in general. The lack of intervention studies may also owed to the fact that from a physiological point of view it is well understood how effective noise protection measures are to reduce noise exposure. T

To effectively minimise noise exposure from transportation sources, particularly for vulnerable populations such as children, it is crucial to focus on upstream measures aimed at reducing noise at source. Implementing strategies such as lowering speed limits, reducing motor and tyre noise, and targeting high-emission noise sources significantly reduces noise exposure to the benefit of the population at large. In contrast, localised interventions like constructing noise barriers primarily benefit those in a specific area. A long-term strategy to reduce exposure to transport noise should also consider improved urban and transportation planning. This includes developing buffer zones, orienting buildings to minimise exposure and designing noise-sensitive areas within structures. Some measures, like the creation of green quiet areas, may have clear co-benefits in terms of air quality improvement,

climate change adaptation and wellbeing and have shown to reduce noise annoyance in adults (jiang et al., 2025).

7 Conclusions and Outlook

A very large proportion of children and adolescents in Europe is exposed to high levels of noise with substantial impact on their development. Given the high burden from noise in Europe implementing policies to reduce transport noise in residential environments and at schools will help in mitigating the detrimental effects of noise on learning. This is particularly relevant as development effects in children may have long lasting consequences into adulthood and contribute to inequality in the society since noise exposure is most prevalent among disadvantaged populations. There is a wide range of noise mitigation measures that can be applied to reduce noise exposure.

Given the existing uncertainty there is a need for longitudinal research to evaluate the long-term effects of noise exposure as well as enduring effects of interventions on health and educational achievement. Future research should focus on methodologically robust studies that assess both short and long-term outcomes of noise reduction interventions, including a life course perspective. Better knowledge and data about the benefits of noise interventions in children/adolescents would enable more reliable cost-benefits analyses for policymaker to make informed decisions on noise interventions. Future environmental burden of disease estimation would also profit from more comprehensive noise exposure that covers the whole exposure range and all areas in Europe.

List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Name	Reference
95%-CI	95% confidence interval	
ADHD	Attention deficit/hyperactivity disorder	
BAHPHL	Beliefs About Hearing Protection and Hearing Loss	
BMI	Body mass index (BMI)	
CVD	Cardiovascular disease	
DALY	Disability-adjusted life years	
dB	Decibel	
DBP	Diastolic blood pressure	
DW	Disability weight	
EBD	Environmental burden of disease	
EEA	European Environment Agency	www.eea.europa.eu
EIONET	European Environment Information and Observation Network	https://www.eionet.europa.eu/
END	Environmental Noise Directive	https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/noise/environmental-noisedirective_en
ERF	Exposure-response function	
ETC HE	European Topic Centre on Human Health and the Environment	https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he
EU	European Union	https://european-union.europa.eu/index_en
GBD	Global Burden of Disease	
GHO	Global Health Observatory of the WHO	
GRADE	Grading of Recommendations Assessment, Development and Evaluation	
Hz	Hertz	
kHz	Kilohertz	
IHME	Institute For Health Metrics and Evaluation	https://www.healthdata.org/
L_{Aeq}	Equivalent continuous sound level	
$L_{Aeq,24h}$	L_{Aeq} averaged over 24 hours	
$L_{DAY}, L_{Aeq,16h}$	L_{Aeq} averaged over 16 hours (during daytime)	
L_{DEN}	L_{Aeq} averaged over 8 hours (during night-time)	
$L_{NIGHT}, L_{Aeq,8h}$	Time-weighted $L_{Aeq,24 h}$ with a penalty of 5 dB(A) for evening-time and 10 dB(A) for night-time	
OR	Odds ratio	
PECOS	Population, Exposures, Comparators, Outcomes and Study design	
PICOS	Population, Intervention, Comparators, Outcomes and Study design	
PRISMA	Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses	
RR	Relative risk	
SBP	Systolic blood pressure	

Abbreviation	Name	Reference
SDQ	Strength and Difficulties Questionnaire	
SGA	Small for gestational age	
WC	Waist circumference	
WHO	World Health Organization	https://www.who.int/
WHO ENG	Environmental Noise Guidelines from the World Health Organization	https://www.who.int/europe/publications/i/item/9789289053563
YANS	Youth Attitudes to Noise Scale	
YLD	Years lived with disability	
YLL	Years of life lost	

References

- Abbasi, M., et al., 2023, 'Noise exposure and the risk of cancer: a comprehensive systematic review', *Reviews on Environmental Health* 38(4), pp. 713-726 (DOI: 10.1515/reveh-2022-0021).
- An, R., et al., 2018, 'Chronic Noise Exposure and Adiposity: A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis', *American Journal of Preventive Medicine* 55(3), pp. 403-411 (DOI: 10.1016/j.amepre.2018.04.040).
- Arregi, A., et al., 2022, 'Environmental Noise Exposure and Sleep Habits among Children in a Cohort from Northern Spain', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 19(23), p. 16321 (DOI: 10.3390/ijerph192316321).
- Babisch, W., 2002, 'The Noise/Stress Concept, Risk Assessment and Research Needs', *Noise & Health* 4(16), pp. 1-11.
- Babisch, W., et al., 2012, 'Noise Annoyance As Reported by 8- to 14-Year-Old Children', *Environment and Behavior* 44(1), pp. 68-86 (DOI: 10.1177/0013916510387400).
- Baird, A., et al., 2023, 'The Association between Physical Environment and Externalising Problems in Typically Developing and Neurodiverse Children and Young People: A Narrative Review', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 20(3), p. 2549 (DOI: 10.3390/ijerph20032549).
- Bao, W.-W., et al., 2022, 'Exposure to road traffic noise and behavioral problems in Chinese schoolchildren: A cross-sectional study', *The Science of the Total Environment* 837, p. 155806 (DOI: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.155806).
- Basner, M., et al., 2017, 'Aviation Noise Impacts: State of the Science', *Noise & Health* 19(87), pp. 41-50 (DOI: 10.4103/nah.NAH_104_16).
- Basner, M. and McGuire, S., 2018, 'WHO Environmental Noise Guidelines for the European Region: A Systematic Review on Environmental Noise and Effects on Sleep', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 15(3), p. 519 (DOI: 10.3390/ijerph15030519).
- Becker, A., et al., 2018, 'Normative Data of the Self-Report Version of the German Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire in an Epidemiological Setting', *Zeitschrift für Kinder- und Jugendpsychiatrie und Psychotherapie* 46(6), pp. 523-533 (DOI: 10.1024/1422-4917/a000589).
- Belojevic, G., et al., 2012, 'Traffic noise and executive functioning in urban primary school children: The moderating role of gender', *Journal of Environmental Psychology* 32(4), pp. 337-341 (DOI: 10.1016/j.jenvp.2012.05.005).
- Belojević, G. and Paunović, K., 2016, 'Recent advances in research on non-auditory effects of community noise', *Srpski Arhiv Za Celokupno Lekarstvo* 144(1-2), pp. 94-98 (DOI: 10.2298/sarh1602094b).
- Bessems, J., et al., 2023, *Environmental health risks to children and adolescents: an umbrella review on chemicals*, EIONET Report No ETC/HE 2023/14, European Topic Centre on Human Health and the Environment (<https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2023-14-environmental-health-risks-to-children-and-adolescents-an-umbrella-review-on-chemicals>) accessed 19 May 2024.

Bloemsma, L. D., et al., 2019a, 'Green space, air pollution, traffic noise and cardiometabolic health in adolescents: The PIAMA birth cohort', *Environment International* 131, p. 104991 (DOI: 10.1016/j.envint.2019.104991).

Bloemsma, L. D., et al., 2019b, 'The associations of air pollution, traffic noise and green space with overweight throughout childhood: The PIAMA birth cohort study', *Environmental Research* 169, pp. 348-356 (DOI: 10.1016/j.envres.2018.11.026).

Bloemsma, L. D., et al., 2022, 'Green space, air pollution, traffic noise and mental wellbeing throughout adolescence: Findings from the PIAMA study', *Environment International* 163, p. 107197 (DOI: 10.1016/j.envint.2022.107197).

Blume, C., et al., 2022, 'Association of transportation noise with sleep during the first year of life: A longitudinal study', *Environmental Research* 203, p. 111776 (DOI: 10.1016/j.envres.2021.111776).

Brink, M., et al., 2018, 'Conversion between noise exposure indicators Leq24h, LDay, LEvening, LNight, Ldn and Lden: Principles and practical guidance', *International Journal of Hygiene and Environmental Health* 221(1), pp. 54-63 (DOI: 10.1016/j.ijheh.2017.10.003).

Brown, A. L. and van Kamp, I., 2017, 'WHO Environmental Noise Guidelines for the European Region: A Systematic Review of Transport Noise Interventions and Their Impacts on Health', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 14(8), p. 873 (DOI: 10.3390/ijerph14080873).

Cai, Y., et al., 2020, 'Impact of road traffic noise on obesity measures: Observational study of three European cohorts', *Environmental Research* 191, p. 110013 (DOI: 10.1016/j.envres.2020.110013).

Carugno, M., et al., 2018, 'Effects of aircraft noise on annoyance, sleep disorders, and blood pressure among adult residents near the Orio al Serio International Airport (BGY), Italy', *La Medicina Del Lavoro* 109(4), pp. 253-263 (DOI: 10.23749/mdl.v109i4.7271).

Castro, A., et al., 2022, 'Environmental health risks to children and adolescents: an umbrella review on indoor and outdoor air pollution', *European Topic Centre on Human Health and the Environment Eionet Report – ETC HE 2022/22*.

Charalampous, P., et al., 2024, 'Disability weights for environmental noise-related health states: results of a disability weights measurement study in Europe', *BMJ Public Health* 2(1) (DOI: 10.1136/bmjph-2023-000470).

Chinn, S., 2000, 'A simple method for converting an odds ratio to effect size for use in meta-analysis', *Statistics in Medicine* 19(22), pp. 3127-3131 (DOI: 10.1002/1097-0258(20001130)19:22<3127::AID-SIM784>3.0.CO;2-M).

Christensen, J. S., et al., 2015, 'Long-term exposure to residential traffic noise and changes in body weight and waist circumference: A cohort study', *Environmental Research* 143(Pt A), pp. 154-161 (DOI: 10.1016/j.envres.2015.10.007).

Christensen, J. S., et al., 2016a, 'Pregnancy and childhood exposure to residential traffic noise and overweight at 7 years of age', *Environment International* 94, pp. 170-176 (DOI: 10.1016/j.envint.2016.05.016).

Christensen, J. S., et al., 2016b, 'Road Traffic and Railway Noise Exposures and Adiposity in Adults: A Cross-Sectional Analysis of the Danish Diet, Cancer, and Health Cohort', *Environmental Health Perspectives* 124(3), pp. 329-335 (DOI: 10.1289/ehp.1409052).

Christidou, V., et al., 2015, “‘Young Noise Researchers’’: An Intervention to Promote Noise Awareness in Preschool Children’, *Journal of Baltic Science Education* 14(5), pp. 569-585 (DOI: 10.33225/jbse/15.14.569).

Clark, C., et al., 2006, ‘Exposure-Effect Relations between Aircraft and Road Traffic Noise Exposure at School and Reading Comprehension: The RANCH Project’, *American Journal of Epidemiology* 163(1), pp. 27-37 (DOI: 10.1093/aje/kwj001).

Clark, C., et al., 2013, ‘Longitudinal effects of aircraft noise exposure on children’s health and cognition: A six-year follow-up of the UK RANCH cohort’, *Journal of Environmental Psychology* 35, pp. 1-9 (DOI: 10.1016/j.jenvp.2013.03.002).

Clark, C., et al., 2020, ‘Evidence for Environmental Noise Effects on Health for the United Kingdom Policy Context: A Systematic Review of the Effects of Environmental Noise on Mental Health, Wellbeing, Quality of Life, Cancer, Dementia, Birth, Reproductive Outcomes, and Cognition’, *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 17(2), p. 393 (DOI: 10.3390/ijerph17020393).

Clark, C. and Paunovic, K., 2018a, ‘WHO Environmental Noise Guidelines for the European Region: A Systematic Review on Environmental Noise and Cognition’, *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 15(2), p. 285 (DOI: 10.3390/ijerph15020285).

Clark, C. and Paunovic, K., 2018b, ‘WHO Environmental Noise Guidelines for the European Region: A Systematic Review on Environmental Noise and Quality of Life, Wellbeing and Mental Health’, *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 15(11), p. 2400 (DOI: 10.3390/ijerph15112400).

Cramer, J., et al., 2019, ‘Road traffic noise and markers of adiposity in the Danish Nurse Cohort: A cross-sectional study’, *Environmental Research* 172, pp. 502-510 (DOI: 10.1016/j.envres.2019.03.001).

Crombie, R., et al., 2011, ‘Environmental noise exposure, early biological risk and mental health in nine to ten year old children: a cross-sectional field study’, *Environmental Health* 10(1), p. 39 (DOI: 10.1186/1476-069X-10-39).

de Bont, J., et al., 2021, ‘Urban environment and obesity and weight-related behaviours in primary school children’, *Environment International* 155, p. 106700 (DOI: 10.1016/j.envint.2021.106700).

De Jong, T. J., et al., 2024, ‘A systematic review on the impact of auditory functioning and language proficiency on psychosocial difficulties in children and adolescents with hearing loss’, *International Journal of Audiology* 63(9), pp. 675-685 (DOI: 10.1080/14992027.2023.2261074).

Dohmen, M., et al., 2022, ‘The Effects of Noise on Cognitive Performance and Helplessness in Childhood: A Review’, *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 20(1), p. 288 (DOI: 10.3390/ijerph20010288).

Dzhambov, A. M., et al., 2019, ‘Associations of residential greenness, traffic noise, and air pollution with birth outcomes across Alpine areas’, *The Science of the Total Environment* 678, pp. 399-408 (DOI: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.05.019).

Dzhambov, A. M., et al., 2024, ‘Childhood sound disturbance and sleep problems in Alpine valleys with high levels of traffic exposures and greenspace’, *Environmental Research* 242, p. 117642 (DOI: 10.1016/j.envres.2023.117642).

Dzhambov, A. M. and Dimitrova, D. D., 2017, 'Children's blood pressure and its association with road traffic noise exposure - A systematic review with meta-analysis', *Environmental Research* 152, pp. 244-255 (DOI: 10.1016/j.envres.2016.10.024).

Dzhambov, A. M. and Lercher, P., 2019, 'Road Traffic Noise Exposure and Birth Outcomes: An Updated Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 16(14), p. 2522 (DOI: 10.3390/ijerph16142522).

EEA, (European Environment Agency), 2014, *Noise in Europe 2014*, EEA Report No No 10/2014, Publications Office, Luxembourg (<http://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/noise-in-europe-2014>) accessed 18 September 2024.

EEA, (European Environment Agency), 2020, *Environmental noise in Europe - 2020*, Technical report No No 22/2019, Publications Office of the European Union, Copenhagen (<https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2800/686249>) accessed 2 October 2023.

EEA, (European Environment Agency), 2024, 'Noise data reported under Environmental Noise Directive (END)' (<https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/datahub/datahubitem-view/c952f520-8d71-42c9-b74c-b7eb002f939b>) accessed 19 December 2024.

Engelmann, N., et al., 2023, *Environmental noise health risk assessment: methodology for assessing health risks using data reported under the Environmental Noise Directive*, EIONET Report No ETC/HE 2023/11, European Topic Centre on Human Health and the Environment (<https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2023-11-environmental-noise-health-risk-assessment-methodology-for-assessing-health-risks-using-data-reported-under-the-environmental-noise-directive>) accessed 30 July 2024.

Enoksson Wallas, A., et al., 2019, 'Traffic noise and other determinants of blood pressure in adolescence', *International Journal of Hygiene and Environmental Health* 222(5), pp. 824-830 (DOI: 10.1016/j.ijheh.2019.04.012).

Erdmann, F., et al., 2022, 'Residential road traffic and railway noise and risk of childhood cancer: A nationwide register-based case-control study in Denmark', *Environmental Research* 212(Pt A), p. 113180 (DOI: 10.1016/j.envres.2022.113180).

Essers, E., et al., 2022, 'Environmental noise exposure and emotional, aggressive, and attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder-related symptoms in children from two European birth cohorts', *Environment International* 158, p. 106946 (DOI: 10.1016/j.envint.2021.106946).

European Commission, 2024, 'Environmental Noise Directive - The main EU law to identify and reduce noise pollution levels where necessary.' (https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/noise/environmental-noise-directive_en) accessed 31 October 2024.

Evans, G. W., et al., 1998, 'Chronic Noise Exposure and Physiological Response: A Prospective Study of Children Living under Environmental Stress', *Psychological Science* 9(1), pp. 75-77.

Evrard, A.-S., et al., 2017, 'Does aircraft noise exposure increase the risk of hypertension in the population living near airports in France?', *Occupational and Environmental Medicine* 74(2), pp. 123-129 (DOI: 10.1136/oemed-2016-103648).

Fernandes, A., et al., 2023, 'School-Based Interventions to Support Healthy Indoor and Outdoor Environments for Children: A Systematic Review', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 20(3), p. 1746 (DOI: 10.3390/ijerph20031746).

Fink, D., 2019, 'A new definition of noise: noise is unwanted and/or harmful sound. Noise is the new "secondhand smoke".', conference paper presented at: 178th Meeting of the Acoustical Society of America, San Diego, California, 2019.

Foraster, M., et al., 2018, 'Long-term exposure to transportation noise and its association with adiposity markers and development of obesity', *Environment International* 121(Pt 1), pp. 879-889 (DOI: 10.1016/j.envint.2018.09.057).

Foraster, M., et al., 2022, 'Exposure to road traffic noise and cognitive development in schoolchildren in Barcelona, Spain: A population-based cohort study', *PLoS medicine* 19(6), p. e1004001 (DOI: 10.1371/journal.pmed.1004001).

Forns, J., et al., 2016, 'Traffic-Related Air Pollution, Noise at School, and Behavioral Problems in Barcelona Schoolchildren: A Cross-Sectional Study', *Environmental Health Perspectives* 124(4), pp. 529-535 (DOI: 10.1289/ehp.1409449).

Fuks, K. B., et al., 2019, 'Road Traffic Noise at the Residence, Annoyance, and Cognitive Function in Elderly Women', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 16(10), p. 1790 (DOI: 10.3390/ijerph16101790).

Gao, X., et al., 2013, 'Results of the parent-rated Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire in 22,108 primary school students from 8 provinces of China', *Shanghai Archives of Psychiatry* 25(6), pp. 364-374 (DOI: 10.3969/j.issn.1002-0829.2013.06.005).

Gilles, A. and Paul, V. de H., 2014, 'Effectiveness of a preventive campaign for noise-induced hearing damage in adolescents', *International Journal of Pediatric Otorhinolaryngology* 78(4), pp. 604-609 (DOI: 10.1016/j.ijporl.2014.01.009).

Goodman, R., 1997, 'The Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire: A Research Note', *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry* 38(5), pp. 581-586 (DOI: 10.1111/j.1469-7610.1997.tb01545.x).

Graafland, N., et al., 2023, 'Exposure to outdoor residential noise during pregnancy, embryonic size, fetal growth, and birth outcomes', *Environment International* 171, p. 107730 (DOI: 10.1016/j.envint.2023.107730).

Graber, J., et al., 2024, *Climate health risks to children and adolescents: exposures, policy and practice interventions.*, Eionet Report No ETC HE Report 2024/8, European Topic Centre on Human Health and the Environment (<https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2024-8-climate-health-risks-to-children-and-adolescents-exposures-policy-and-practice-interventions>) accessed 4 November 2024.

Grelat, N., et al., 2016, 'Noise Annoyance in Urban Children: A Cross-Sectional Population-Based Study', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 13(11), p. 1056 (DOI: 10.3390/ijerph13111056).

Gui, S.-Y., et al., 2022, 'Traffic noise and adiposity: a systematic review and meta-analysis of epidemiological studies', *Environmental Science and Pollution Research International* 29(37), pp. 55707-55727 (DOI: 10.1007/s11356-022-19056-7).

Guyatt, G. H., et al., 2008, 'GRADE: an emerging consensus on rating quality of evidence and strength of recommendations', *BMJ* 336(7650), pp. 924-926 (DOI: 10.1136/bmj.39489.470347.AD).

Haines, M. M., et al., 2001, 'The West London Schools Study: the effects of chronic aircraft noise exposure on child health', *Psychological Medicine* 31(8), pp. 1385-1396 (DOI: 10.1017/S003329170100469X).

Halonen, J. I., et al., 2017, 'Associations of night-time road traffic noise with carotid intima-media thickness and blood pressure: The Whitehall II and SABRE study cohorts', *Environment International* 98, pp. 54-61 (DOI: 10.1016/j.envint.2016.09.023).

Harvey, P. D., 2019, 'Domains of cognition and their assessment', *Dialogues in Clinical Neuroscience* 21(3), pp. 227-237 (DOI: 10.31887/DCNS.2019.21.3/pharvey).

Hasselblad, V. and Hedges, L. V., 1995, 'Meta-analysis of screening and diagnostic tests', *Psychological Bulletin* 117(1), pp. 167-178 (DOI: 10.1037/0033-2909.117.1.167).

Hjortebjerg, D., et al., 2016a, 'Associations between maternal exposure to air pollution and traffic noise and newborn's size at birth: A cohort study', *Environment International* 95, pp. 1-7 (DOI: 10.1016/j.envint.2016.07.003).

Hjortebjerg, D., et al., 2016b, 'Exposure to Road Traffic Noise and Behavioral Problems in 7-Year-Old Children: A Cohort Study', *Environmental Health Perspectives* 124(2), pp. 228-234 (DOI: 10.1289/ehp.1409430).

Hoofs, H., et al., 2015, 'The Context Dependency of the Self-Report Version of the Strength and Difficulties Questionnaire (SDQ): A Cross-Sectional Study between Two Administration Settings', *PLOS ONE* 10(4), p. e0120930 (DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0120930).

Huang, T., et al., 2020, 'The Association between Noise Exposure and Metabolic Syndrome: A Longitudinal Cohort Study in Taiwan', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 17(12), p. 4236 (DOI: 10.3390/ijerph17124236).

Hygge, S., et al., 2002, 'A Prospective Study of Some Effects of Aircraft Noise on Cognitive Performance in Schoolchildren', *Psychological Science* 13(5), pp. 469-474 (DOI: 10.1111/1467-9280.00483).

IHME, (Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation), 2023, '2019 GBD Results', Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation (<https://vizhub.healthdata.org/gbd-results>) accessed 5 October 2023.

jiang, X., et al., 2025, *Evaluation of the benefits of green space on noise-related effects: a health impact assessment on annoyance*, Eionet Report – ETC HE No 2024/10, European Topic Centre on Human Health and the Environment. (<https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2024-10-evaluation-of-the-benefits-of-green-space-on-noise-related-effects-a-health-impact-assessment-on-annoyance>).

Julvez, J., et al., 2021, 'Early life multiple exposures and child cognitive function: A multi-centric birth cohort study in six European countries', *Environmental Pollution (Barking, Essex: 1987)* 284, p. 117404 (DOI: 10.1016/j.envpol.2021.117404).

Kourieh, A., et al., 2022, 'Incident hypertension in relation to aircraft noise exposure: results of the DEBATS longitudinal study in France', *Occupational and Environmental Medicine* 79(4), pp. 268-276 (DOI: 10.1136/oemed-2021-107921).

Le Clercq, C. M. P., et al., 2016, 'Music-induced Hearing Loss in Children, Adolescents, and Young Adults: A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis', *Otology & Neurotology* 37(9), pp. 1208-1216 (DOI: 10.1097/MAO.0000000000001163).

Lee, Y., et al., 2023, 'Occupational and Environmental Noise Exposure and Extra-Auditory Effects on Humans: A Systematic Literature Review', *GeoHealth* 7(6), p. e2023GH000805 (DOI: 10.1029/2023GH000805).

Lie, A., et al., 2016, 'Occupational noise exposure and hearing: a systematic review', *International Archives of Occupational and Environmental Health* 89(3), pp. 351-372 (DOI: 10.1007/s00420-015-1083-5).

Lim, J., et al., 2018, 'Negative impact of noise and noise sensitivity on mental health in childhood', *Noise & Health* 20(96), pp. 199-211 (DOI: 10.4103/nah.NAH_9_18).

Mac Domhnaill, C., et al., 2021, 'Road traffic noise and cognitive function in older adults: a cross-sectional investigation of The Irish Longitudinal Study on Ageing', *BMC public health* 21(1), p. 1814 (DOI: 10.1186/s12889-021-11853-y).

Malacarne, D., et al., 2022, 'The built environment as determinant of childhood obesity: A systematic literature review', *Obesity Reviews: An Official Journal of the International Association for the Study of Obesity* 23 Suppl 1, p. e13385 (DOI: 10.1111/obr.13385).

McEwen, B. S., 2006, 'Protective and damaging effects of stress mediators: central role of the brain', *Dialogues in Clinical Neuroscience* 8(4), p. 367 (DOI: 10.31887/DCNS.2006.8.4/bmcewen).

Morgan, R. L., et al., 2016, 'GRADE: Assessing the quality of evidence in environmental and occupational health', *Environment international* 92-93, pp. 611-616 (DOI: 10.1016/j.envint.2016.01.004).

Morgan, R. L., et al., 2018, 'Identifying the PECO: A framework for formulating good questions to explore the association of environmental and other exposures with health outcomes', *Environment international* 121(Pt 1), pp. 1027-1031 (DOI: 10.1016/j.envint.2018.07.015).

Newbury, J. B., et al., 2024, 'Air and Noise Pollution Exposure in Early Life and Mental Health From Adolescence to Young Adulthood', *JAMA Network Open* 7(5), p. e2412169 (DOI: 10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2024.12169).

Nieuwenhuijsen, M. J., et al., 2017, 'WHO Environmental Noise Guidelines for the European Region: A Systematic Review on Environmental Noise and Adverse Birth Outcomes', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 14(10), p. 1252 (DOI: 10.3390/ijerph14101252).

Nieuwenhuijsen, M. J., et al., 2019, 'Influence of the Urban Exposome on Birth Weight', *Environmental Health Perspectives* 127(4), p. 47007 (DOI: 10.1289/EHP3971).

Oftedal, B., et al., 2015, 'Road traffic noise and markers of obesity - a population-based study', *Environmental Research* 138, pp. 144-153 (DOI: 10.1016/j.envres.2015.01.011).

Page, M. J., et al., 2021, 'The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews', *BMJ* 372, p. n71 (DOI: 10.1136/bmj.n71).

Pedersen, M., et al., 2017, 'Exposure to air pollution and noise from road traffic and risk of congenital anomalies in the Danish National Birth Cohort', *Environmental Research* 159, pp. 39-45 (DOI: 10.1016/j.envres.2017.07.031).

Pedersen, M., et al., 2019, 'Associations between ambient air pollution and noise from road traffic with blood pressure and insulin resistance in children from Denmark', *Environmental Epidemiology (Philadelphia, Pa.)* 3(5), p. e069 (DOI: 10.1097/EE9.0000000000000069).

Pérez-Crespo, L., et al., 2023, 'Outdoor residential noise exposure and sleep in preadolescents from two European birth cohorts', *Environmental Research* 225, p. 115502 (DOI: 10.1016/j.envres.2023.115502).

Pérez-Crespo, L., et al., 2024, 'Association between residential exposure to road traffic noise and cognitive and motor function outcomes in children and preadolescents', *Environment International* 183, p. 108414 (DOI: 10.1016/j.envint.2023.108414).

Petri, D., et al., 2021, 'Effects of Exposure to Road, Railway, Airport and Recreational Noise on Blood Pressure and Hypertension', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 18(17), p. 9145 (DOI: 10.3390/ijerph18179145).

Pitchika, A., et al., 2017, 'Long-term associations of modeled and self-reported measures of exposure to air pollution and noise at residence on prevalent hypertension and blood pressure', *The Science of the Total Environment* 593-594, pp. 337-346 (DOI: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.03.156).

Polewczyk, I. and Jarosz, M., 2020, 'Teachers' and Students' Assessment of the Influence of School Rooms Acoustic Treatment on Their Performance and Wellbeing', *Archives of Acoustics* 45(3), p. 401 (DOI: 10.24425/aoa.2020.134057).

Prüss-Üstün, A., et al., 2003, *Introduction and methods: Assessing the environmental burden of disease at national and local levels*, Environmental Burden of Disease Series, No. 1, World Health Organization, Geneva (<https://iris.who.int/bitstream/handle/10665/42750/9241546204.pdf?sequence=1>).

Pyko, A., et al., 2015, 'Exposure to traffic noise and markers of obesity', *Occupational and Environmental Medicine* 72(8), pp. 594-601 (DOI: 10.1136/oemed-2014-102516).

Pyko, A., et al., 2017, 'Long-Term Exposure to Transportation Noise in Relation to Development of Obesity—a Cohort Study', *Environmental Health Perspectives* 125(11), p. 117005 (DOI: 10.1289/EHP1910).

Quehl, J., et al., 2021, 'Effects of Nocturnal Aircraft Noise and Non-Acoustical Factors on Short-Term Annoyance in Primary School Children', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 18(13), p. 6959 (DOI: 10.3390/ijerph18136959).

Raess, M., et al., 2022, 'Association between community noise and children's cognitive and behavioral development: A prospective cohort study', *Environment International* 158, p. 106961 (DOI: 10.1016/j.envint.2021.106961).

Roche, I. V., et al., 2024, 'The Health-Related and Learning Performance Effects of Air Pollution and Other Urban-Related Environmental Factors on School-Age Children and Adolescents-A Scoping Review of Systematic Reviews', *Current Environmental Health Reports* (DOI: 10.1007/s40572-024-00431-0).

Schubert, M., et al., 2019, 'Behavioral and Emotional Disorders and Transportation Noise among Children and Adolescents: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 16(18), p. 3336 (DOI: 10.3390/ijerph16183336).

Seabi, J., et al., 2015, 'A prospective follow-up study of the effects of chronic aircraft noise exposure on learners' reading comprehension in South Africa', *Journal of Exposure Science & Environmental Epidemiology* 25(1), pp. 84-88 (DOI: 10.1038/jes.2013.71).

Shea, B. J., et al., 2017, 'AMSTAR 2: a critical appraisal tool for systematic reviews that include randomised or non-randomised studies of healthcare interventions, or both', *BMJ* 358, p. j4008 (DOI: 10.1136/bmj.j4008).

Sivakumaran, K., et al., 2022, 'Impact of Noise Exposure on Risk of Developing Stress-Related Health Effects Related to the Cardiovascular System: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis', *Noise & Health* 24(114), pp. 107-129 (DOI: 10.4103/nah.nah_83_21).

Skrzypek, M., et al., 2017, 'Impact of road traffic noise on sleep disturbances and attention disorders amongst school children living in Upper Silesian Industrial Zone, Poland', *International Journal of Occupational Medicine and Environmental Health* 30(3), pp. 511-520 (DOI: 10.13075/ijomh.1896.00823).

Sørensen, M., et al., 2024, 'Health position paper and redox perspectives - Disease burden by transportation noise', *Redox Biology* 69, p. 102995 (DOI: 10.1016/j.redox.2023.102995).

Stansfeld, S., et al., 2005, 'Aircraft and road traffic noise and children's cognition and health: a cross-national study', *The Lancet* 365(9475), pp. 1942-1949 (DOI: 10.1016/S0140-6736(05)66660-3).

Stansfeld, S. A., et al., 2009, 'Aircraft and road traffic noise exposure and children's mental health', *Journal of Environmental Psychology* 29(2), pp. 203-207 (DOI: 10.1016/j.jenvp.2009.01.002).

Stansfeld, S. A., 2015, 'Noise Effects on Health in the Context of Air Pollution Exposure', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 12(10), pp. 12735-12760 (DOI: 10.3390/ijerph121012735).

Stansfeld, S. and Clark, C., 2015, 'Health Effects of Noise Exposure in Children', *Current Environmental Health Reports* 2(2), pp. 171-178 (DOI: 10.1007/s40572-015-0044-1).

Tangermann, L., et al., 2022, 'The association of road traffic noise with problem behaviour in adolescents: A cohort study', *Environmental Research* 207, p. 112645 (DOI: 10.1016/j.envres.2021.112645).

Tangermann, L., et al., 2023, 'The association of road traffic noise with cognition in adolescents: A cohort study in Switzerland', *Environmental Research* 218, p. 115031 (DOI: 10.1016/j.envres.2022.115031).

Terzakis, M. E., et al., 2022, 'Noise Indicators Relating to Non-Auditory Health Effects in Children-A Systematic Literature Review', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 19(23), p. 15633 (DOI: 10.3390/ijerph192315633).

Thompson, R., et al., 2022, 'Noise pollution and human cognition: An updated systematic review and meta-analysis of recent evidence', *Environment International* 158, p. 106905 (DOI: 10.1016/j.envint.2021.106905).

Tiesler, C. M. T., et al., 2013, 'Exposure to road traffic noise and children's behavioural problems and sleep disturbance: Results from the GINIplus and LISApplus studies', *Environmental Research* 123, pp. 1-8 (DOI: 10.1016/j.envres.2013.01.009).

Tzivian, L., et al., 2015, 'Effect of long-term outdoor air pollution and noise on cognitive and psychological functions in adults', *International Journal of Hygiene and Environmental Health* 218(1), pp. 1-11 (DOI: 10.1016/j.ijheh.2014.08.002).

Tzivian, L., et al., 2016a, 'Long-term air pollution and traffic noise exposures and cognitive function: A cross-sectional analysis of the Heinz Nixdorf Recall study', *Journal of Toxicology and Environmental Health. Part A* 79(22-23), pp. 1057-1069 (DOI: 10.1080/15287394.2016.1219570).

Tzivian, L., et al., 2016b, 'Long-Term Air Pollution and Traffic Noise Exposures and Mild Cognitive Impairment in Older Adults: A Cross-Sectional Analysis of the Heinz Nixdorf Recall Study', *Environmental Health Perspectives* 124(9), pp. 1361-1368 (DOI: 10.1289/ehp.1509824).

Umweltbundesamt, 2009, *Data on the Environment, Edition 2009*, Federal Environmental Agency (<https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/sites/default/files/medien/publikation/long/3877.pdf>).

Van Kempen, E., 2008, *Transportation noise exposure and children's health and cognition*, PhD thesis Utrecht University, Utrecht (<https://dspace.library.uu.nl/handle/1874/25891>).

van Kempen, E., et al., 2009, 'Children's annoyance reactions to aircraft and road traffic noise', *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America* 125(2), pp. 895-904 (DOI: 10.1121/1.3058635).

van Kempen, E., et al., 2018, 'WHO Environmental Noise Guidelines for the European Region: A Systematic Review on Environmental Noise and Cardiovascular and Metabolic Effects: A Summary', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 15(2), p. 379 (DOI: 10.3390/ijerph15020379).

Vincens, N. and Persson Waye, K., 2023, 'Occupational and environmental noise exposure during pregnancy and rare health outcomes of offspring: a scoping review focusing on congenital anomalies and perinatal mortality', *Reviews on Environmental Health* 38(3), pp. 423-438 (DOI: 10.1515/reveh-2021-0166).

Wallas, A., et al., 2019, 'Traffic noise exposure in relation to adverse birth outcomes and body mass between birth and adolescence', *Environmental Research* 169, pp. 362-367 (DOI: 10.1016/j.envres.2018.11.039).

Wallas, A. E., et al., 2020, 'Noise exposure and childhood asthma up to adolescence', *Environmental Research* 185, p. 109404 (DOI: 10.1016/j.envres.2020.109404).

Wang, Z., et al., 2021, 'Traffic-related environmental factors and childhood obesity: A systematic review and meta-analysis', *Obesity Reviews: An Official Journal of the International Association for the Study of Obesity* 22 Suppl 1(Suppl 1), p. e12995 (DOI: 10.1111/obr.12995).

Warembourg, C., et al., 2019, 'Early-Life Environmental Exposures and Blood Pressure in Children', *Journal of the American College of Cardiology* 74(10), pp. 1317-1328 (DOI: 10.1016/j.jacc.2019.06.069).

Warembourg, C., et al., 2021, 'Urban environment during early-life and blood pressure in young children', *Environment International* 146, p. 106174 (DOI: 10.1016/j.envint.2020.106174).

Weyde, K. V., et al., 2017a, 'Nocturnal Road Traffic Noise Exposure and Children's Sleep Duration and Sleep Problems', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 14(5), p. 491 (DOI: 10.3390/ijerph14050491).

Weyde, K. V., et al., 2017b, 'Road traffic noise and children's inattention', *Environmental Health* 16, p. 127 (DOI: 10.1186/s12940-017-0337-y).

WHO, 1999, Guidelines for community noise, (<https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/a68672>).

WHO Europe, (World Health Organization Europe), 2018, *Environmental noise guidelines for the European Region*, World Health Organization Regional Office for Europe, Copenhagen (http://www.euro.who.int/__data/assets/pdf_file/0008/383921/noise-guidelines-eng.pdf?ua=1) accessed 3 August 2022.

WHO Europe, (World Health Organization Europe), 2024, *Disability weights for noise-related health states in the WHO European Region*, No WHO/EURO:2024-9196-48968-72969, World Health Organization Regional Office for Europe, Copenhagen (<https://www.who.int/europe/publications/i/item/WHO-EURO-2024-9196-48968-72969>) accessed 31 October 2024.

WHO, (World Health Organization), 2017, 'Global Health Observatory' (<https://www.who.int/data/gho>) accessed 31 October 2024.

Yuchi, W., et al., 2022, 'Neighborhood environmental exposures and incidence of attention deficit/hyperactivity disorder: A population-based cohort study', *Environment International* 161, p. 107120 (DOI: 10.1016/j.envint.2022.107120).

Zaman, M., et al., 2022, 'Environmental noise-induced cardiovascular, metabolic and mental health disorders: a brief review', *Environmental Science and Pollution Research International* 29(51), pp. 76485-76500 (DOI: 10.1007/s11356-022-22351-y).

Zare Sakhvidi, F., et al., 2018, 'Environmental Noise Exposure and Neurodevelopmental and Mental Health Problems in Children: a Systematic Review', *Current Environmental Health Reports* 5(3), pp. 365-374 (DOI: 10.1007/s40572-018-0208-x).

Zeng, Y., et al., 2023, 'Longitudinal associations of neighbourhood environmental exposures with mental health problems during adolescence: Findings from the TRAILS study', *Environment International* 179, p. 108142 (DOI: 10.1016/j.envint.2023.108142).

Zhao, Y.-L., et al., 2021, 'Environmental factors and risks of cognitive impairment and dementia: A systematic review and meta-analysis', *Ageing Research Reviews* 72, p. 101504 (DOI: 10.1016/j.arr.2021.101504).

Zijlema, W., et al., 2016, 'Road traffic noise, blood pressure and heart rate: Pooled analyses of harmonized data from 88,336 participants', *Environmental Research* 151, pp. 804-813 (DOI: 10.1016/j.envres.2016.09.014).

Zijlema, W. L., et al., 2021, 'Associations between road traffic noise exposure at home and school and ADHD in school-aged children: the TRAILS study', *European Child & Adolescent Psychiatry* 30(1), pp. 155-167 (DOI: 10.1007/s00787-020-01521-8).

8 Annex 1 - Search Terms Used to Characterize Population, Exposure, Outcomes and Study Type for the Umbrella+ Review

Table 8.1 Search terms used for the Umbrella + review on the effect of environmental noise on the health of children and adolescents

PECOS criteria	Description	Query
Population	General population / adults (included due to review 2023)	"humans"[MeSH Terms] OR "adult"[tiab] OR "adults"[tiab] OR "adult"[MeSH Terms] OR "aged"[tiab] OR "aged"[MeSH Terms] OR "man"[tiab] OR "men"[tiab] OR "woman"[tiab] OR "women"[tiab]
Population	Infants / children / adolescents	"Child"[tiab] OR "children"[tiab] OR "pupils"[tiab] OR "preschooler"[tiab] OR "preschoolers"[tiab] OR "student"[tiab] OR "students"[tiab] OR "Adolescent"[tiab] OR "adolescents"[tiab] OR "Infant"[tiab] OR "infants"[tiab] OR "toddler"[tiab] OR "toddlers"[tiab] OR "newborn"[tiab] OR "baby"[tiab] OR "babies"[tiab] OR "boy"[tiab] OR "boys"[tiab] OR "girl"[tiab] OR "girls"[tiab] OR "postnatal*" [tiab] OR "post-natal" [tiab] OR "*school*" [tiab] OR "pediatric*" [tiab] OR "paediatric*" [tiab] OR "prenatal"[tiab] OR "preterm"[tiab] OR "birth"[tiab] OR "gestational"[tiab] OR "pregnancy"[tiab] OR "fetal"[tiab] OR "parturition"[MeSH Terms] OR "Adolescent"[MeSH Terms] OR "Birth Cohort"[MeSH Terms] OR "Child"[MeSH Terms] OR "Infant"[MeSH Terms]
Population	Unborn children	"foetus"[tiab] OR "fetus"[tiab] OR "embryo"[tiab] OR "unborn"[tiab] OR "pregnan*" [tiab]
Exposure	Noise	"Noise, Transportation" [Mesh terms] OR (noise [tiab] AND traffic[tiab]) OR (noise [tiab] AND transportation [tiab]) OR (noise [tiab] AND road [tiab]) OR (noise [tiab] AND (airplane [tiab] OR aircraft [tiab])) OR (noise [tiab] AND rail* [tiab]) OR (noise[tiab] AND environmental[tiab]) OR (noise[tiab] AND community[tiab])
Outcome	Adverse birth outcomes	Premature Birth [Mesh Terms] OR Infant, Very Low Birth Weight [Mesh Terms] OR Birth Weight [Mesh Terms] OR Premature Birth [Mesh Terms] OR Abortion, Spontaneous [Mesh Terms] OR Congenital Abnormalities [Mesh Terms] OR birth [tiab] OR birth weight [tiab] OR birth defects [tiab] OR preterm [tiab]
Outcome	Annoyance	annoy* [Mesh Terms] OR annoy* [tiab]
Outcome	Behavioural problems	Behaviour [MeSH Terms] OR behaviour [Title/Abstract] OR hyperactivity [MESH Terms] OR hyperactivity [tiab] OR aggression [Mesh Terms] OR aggression [tiab]
Outcome	Cancer	"Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR "Neoplasms"[tiab] OR "cancer*" [tiab] OR "tumor*" [tiab] OR "tumour*" [tiab] OR "oncolog*" [tiab] OR "benig*" [tiab] OR "malignan*" [tiab] OR "carcinoma" [tiab] OR "sarcoma" [tiab] OR "myeloma" [tiab] OR "leukemia" [tiab] OR "lymphoma" [tiab]
Outcome	Cardiovascular diseases (included due to 2023 review, here only blood pressure in eligibility criteria)	Vascular Diseases [Mesh Terms] OR blood pressure [Mesh Terms] OR heart rate [Mesh Terms] OR vascular Diseases [tiab] OR blood pressure [tiab] OR heart rate [tiab] OR pulse [tiab] OR "hypertension" [tiab] OR hypertension [Mesh Terms] OR ischemic heart disease [tiab] OR ischemic heart disease [Mesh Terms] OR stroke [tiab] OR stroke [Mesh Terms] OR CVD [tiab] OR "Heart Failure"[Mesh Terms] OR heart failure [tiab] OR "Myocardial

PECOS criteria	Description	Query
		Infarction"[Mesh Terms] OR myocardial infarction[tiab] OR "Coronary Disease"[Mesh Terms] OR coronary disease[tiab] OR "Arrhythmias, Cardiac"[Mesh] OR Arrhythmia[tiab]
Outcome	Cognition	"Cognitive Psychology" [Mesh terms] OR "Neuropsychological Tests" [Mesh terms] OR "Cognitive Neuroscience" [Mesh terms] OR Cogniti* [tiab] OR "Cognitive functions" [tiab] OR learning [tiab] OR reading [tiab] OR comprehen* [tiab]
Outcome	Mental health	"Depression"[Mesh Terms] OR depress*[tiab] OR "Depressive Disorder"[Mesh Terms] OR "Mental Health"[Mesh Terms] OR "Mental Disorders"[Mesh Terms] OR mental health[tiab]
Outcome	Obesity	Overweight [Mesh Terms] OR overweight [tiab] OR BMI [tiab] OR body mass index [tiab] OR waist circumference [tiab] OR BMI [Mesh Terms] OR body mass index [Mesh Terms] OR waist circumference [Mesh Terms]
Outcome	Respiratory disorders	"respirat*" [tiab] OR "pneumo*" [tiab] OR "asthma" [tiab] OR "bronch*" [tiab] OR "pulmon*" [tiab] OR "COPD" [tiab]
Outcome	Sleep disturbance	Sleep* [Mesh Terms] OR sleep* [tiab] OR fatigue [tiab] or "wake up" [tiab] OR sleep disturbance [tiab] OR sleep duration [tiab]
Study type	Reviews	"systematic review" [tiab] OR "metaanalysis" [tiab] OR "meta analysis" [tiab] OR "systematic review" [Publication Type] OR "meta analysis" [Publication Type] OR "Meta-Analysis as Topic" [MeSH Terms] OR review [tiab] OR "Review" [Publication Type]
Study type	Original studies	"Cohort Studies" [Mesh Terms] OR cohort [tiab]
Study type	Original studies	"Cross-Sectional Studies" [Mesh] OR cross-sectional [tiab]
Search period ^a	Initial search	2015/01/01:2023/07/03 [dp]
Search period ^a	Update search	2023/07/03:2024/03/05 [dp]
Search period ^b	Search for outcomes not included in 2023 report	2015/01/01:2024/03/05 [dp]

^a Used for behavioural problems, cardiovascular diseases, cognition, obesity and mental health.

^b Used for Adverse birth outcomes, annoyance, cancer, respiratory disorders and sleep disturbance.

Search terms within each search grid category were expanded with "OR" and the different categories combined with "AND".

Table 8.2 Search terms used for the Umbrella+ review on interventions to reduce risk and impact from environmental noise on the health of children and adolescents in Europe

PECOS criteria	Search	Query
Exposure	1	"noise, transportation"[Mesh] OR "noise"[Mesh:noexp] OR "noise*"[Tiab]
Exposure	2	"traffic"[Tiab] OR "transport*"[Tiab] OR "road"[Tiab] OR "roads"[Tiab] OR "road-traffic"[Tiab] OR "road-transport"[Tiab] OR "automobile*"[Tiab] OR "vehicle*"[Tiab] OR "vehicular movements"[Tiab] OR "motorcycle*"[Tiab] OR "tram"[Tiab] OR "train"[Tiab] OR "trains"[Tiab] OR "railway*"[Tiab] OR "railroad*"[Tiab] OR "airplane*"[Tiab] OR "aeroplane*"[Tiab] OR "aircraft*"[Tiab] OR "airport*"[Tiab] OR "air-traffic"[Tiab] OR "night flights"[Tiab]
Exposure	3	"transportation"[Mesh] OR "motor vehicles"[Mesh] OR "railroads"[Mesh] OR "aviation"[Mesh] OR "environmental exposure"[Mesh:noexp] OR "environmental health"[Mesh:noexp] OR "environment"[Tiab]
	4	#1 AND (#2 OR #3)
Exposure	5	"noise pollution"[Tiab] OR "noise exposure"[Tiab] OR "transportation noise"[Tiab]
Outcome	6	"annoyance"[Tiab] OR "disturbance"[Tiab] OR "nuisance"[Tiab] OR "bother*"[Tiab]
Outcome	7	"health"[Tiab] OR "morbidity"[Tiab] OR "wellbeing"[Tiab] OR "health"[Mesh:noexp] OR "health status"[Mesh:noexp] OR "mental health"[Mesh:noexp] OR "quality of life"[Mesh:noexp] OR "public health"[Mesh:noexp]
Outcome	8	"stress"[Tiab] OR "blood pressure"[Tiab] OR "heart rate*"[Tiab] OR "cardiovascular"[Tiab] OR "stress, psychological"[Mesh:noexp] OR "stress, physiological"[Mesh:noexp] OR "emotions"[Mesh:noexp] OR "child behavior"[Mesh:noexp] OR "blood pressure"[Mesh:noexp] OR "heart rate"[Mesh:noexp]
Outcome	9	"cognitive performance"[Tiab] OR "cognitive impairment"[Tiab] OR "cognition"[Tiab] OR "cognitive development"[Tiab] OR "cognitive effects"[Tiab] OR "memory"[Tiab] OR "recognition"[Tiab] OR "loudness perception"[Tiab] OR "reading"[Tiab] OR "pre-reading"[Tiab] OR "school performance"[Tiab] OR "performance"[Tiab] OR "comprehension"[Tiab] OR ("disturbance"[Tiab] AND "daily activity*"[Tiab]) OR "emotion*"[Tiab] OR "perception"[Tiab] OR "speech"[Tiab] OR "intelligibility"[Tiab]
Outcome	10	"cognition"[Mesh:noexp] OR "cognition disorders"[Mesh:noexp] OR "memory"[Mesh:noexp] OR "reading"[Mesh:noexp] OR "mental recall"[Mesh:noexp] OR "recognition, psychology"[Mesh:noexp] OR "loudness perception"[Mesh:noexp] OR "perception"[Mesh:noexp] OR "auditory perception"[Mesh:noexp] OR "comprehension"[Mesh:noexp] OR "adaptation, psychological"[Mesh:noexp] OR "speech intelligibility"[Mesh:noexp]
Outcome	11	"sleep"[Tiab] OR "insomnia"[Tiab] OR "awakening*"[Tiab] OR "sleep disorder*"[Tiab] OR "sleep"[Mesh] OR "sleep wake disorders"[Mesh:noexp] OR "sleep deprivation"[Mesh:noexp] OR "wakefulness"[Mesh:noexp]
Outcome	12	"reproductive outcome*"[Tiab] OR "pregnancy outcome*"[Tiab] OR "birth outcome*"[Tiab] OR "birth weight"[Tiab] OR "pregnancy outcome"[Mesh:noexp] OR "birth weight"[Mesh:noexp]
	13	(#4 OR #5) AND (#6 OR #7 OR #8 OR #9 OR #10 OR #11 OR #12)
Intervention	14	"prevention"[Tiab] OR "preventive"[Tiab] OR "prevent"[Tiab] OR "preventative"[Tiab] OR "preventing"[Tiab] OR "intervening"[Tiab] OR "intervention*"[Tiab] OR "mitigation"[Tiab] OR "measures"[Tiab] OR "reduction"[Tiab] OR "reducing"[Tiab] OR "reduce"[Tiab] OR "improving"[Tiab] OR

PECOS criteria	Search	Query
		"minimizing"[Tiab] OR "program*"[Tiab] OR "campaign*"[Tiab] OR "project*"[Tiab] OR "policy"[Tiab] OR "policies"[Tiab] OR "strategy*"[Tiab] OR "guidelines"[Tiab] OR "directive*"[Tiab] OR "community response"[Tiab] OR "public health response"[Tiab]
Population	15	"child" OR "children" OR "pupils" OR "preschooler" OR "preschoolers" OR "student" OR "students" OR "adolescent" OR "adolescents" OR "infant" OR "infants" OR "toddler" OR "toddlers" OR "newborn" OR "baby" OR "babies" OR "boy" OR "boys" OR "girl" OR "girls" OR "postnatal*" OR "post-natal" OR "school" OR "pediatric*" OR "paediatric*" OR "prenatal" OR "preterm" OR "birth" OR "gestational" OR "pregnancy" OR "fetal" OR "parturition"[Mesh] OR "adolescent"[Mesh] OR "birth cohort"[Mesh] OR "child"[Mesh] OR "infant"[Mesh]
	16	#13 AND #14 AND #15

9 Annex 2 - PRISMA Flow Diagrams of the Screening Process to Identify Relevant Reviews and Original Studies

Figure 9.1 PRISMA flow diagram for adverse birth outcomes

Note: Search period: 1st January 2015 to 5th March 2024.

Figure 9.2 PRISMA flow diagram for behavioural problems

Note: Search periods: 1st January 2015 to 3rd July 2023 (first search) and 3rd July 2023 to 5th March 2024 (second search).

Figure 9.3 PRISMA flow diagram for blood pressure

Note: Search periods: 1st January 2015 to 3rd July 2023 (first search) and 3rd July 2023 to 5th March 2024 (second search).

Figure 9.4 PRISMA flow diagram for cognition

Note: Search periods: 1st January 2015 to 3rd July 2023 (first search) and 3rd July 2023 to 5th March 2024 (second search).

Figure 9.5 PRISMA flow diagram for obesity

Note: Search periods: 1st January 2015 to 3rd July 2023 (first search) and 3rd July 2023 to 5th March 2024 (second search).

Figure 9.6 PRISMA flow diagram for interventions

Note: Search period: 1st January 2015 to 29th February 2024

10 Annex 3 – Country Specific Health Data

Table 10.1 Prevalence rates for each health outcome per country from the 2019 GBD study or the 2016 GHO data of the WHO

Country IOS Code	ADHD (5-9 years)	ADHD (10-14 years)	ADHD (15-19 years)	Conduct disorder (5-9 years)	Conduct disorder (10-14 years)	Conduct disorder (15-19 years)	Overweight (5-9 years)	Overweight (10-19 years)
AT	0.033307	0.042156	0.030648	0.014877	0.035480	0.021621	0.281	0.258
BE	0.028068	0.035548	0.025332	0.015659	0.037192	0.022363	0.255	0.231
BG	0.018129	0.024650	0.020346	0.011097	0.034176	0.019094	0.312	0.271
CH	0.034179	0.043461	0.031677	0.015685	0.037229	0.022456	0.230	0.212
CY	0.028278	0.035781	0.025439	0.015742	0.037304	0.022424	0.366	0.315
CZ	0.018098	0.024610	0.020325	0.011084	0.034148	0.019081	-	-
DE	0.014479	0.018076	0.012241	0.015695	0.037252	0.022539	0.287	0.253
DK	0.026672	0.033824	0.024162	0.015676	0.037205	0.022376	0.276	0.238
EE	0.018099	0.024645	0.020303	0.011084	0.034172	0.019068	0.228	0.194
EL	0.028066	0.035515	0.025323	0.015658	0.037176	0.022358	0.410	0.353
ES	0.061190	0.077289	0.056585	0.015692	0.037220	0.022390	0.379	0.319
FI	0.035280	0.044748	0.032565	0.015658	0.037177	0.022393	0.295	0.254
FR	0.034327	0.041284	0.027266	0.015661	0.037183	0.022384	0.324	0.289
HR	0.018128	0.024647	0.020310	0.011097	0.034173	0.019071	0.319	0.257
HU	0.018117	0.024630	0.020329	0.011092	0.034162	0.019084	0.314	0.269
IE	0.036958	0.047088	0.034345	0.015650	0.037197	0.022349	0.339	0.294
IS	0.032419	0.041289	0.029644	0.015652	0.037230	0.022262	0.309	0.270
IT	0.024249	0.032028	0.024305	0.015297	0.039955	0.023707	0.420	0.342

Country IOS Code	ADHD (5-9 years)	ADHD (10-14 years)	ADHD (15-19 years)	Conduct disorder (5-9 years)	Conduct disorder (10-14 years)	Conduct disorder (15-19 years)	Overweight (5-9 years)	Overweight (10-19 years)
LT	0.018112	0.024576	0.020327	0.011090	0.034125	0.019082	0.229	0.192
LU	0.028215	0.035781	0.025360	0.015717	0.037303	0.022379	0.290	0.248
LV	0.018148	0.024607	0.020290	0.011106	0.034147	0.019059	0.235	0.204
MT	0.028301	0.035793	0.025237	0.015751	0.037310	0.022310	0.399	0.352
NL	0.033225	0.041979	0.029933	0.014629	0.035614	0.021414	0.269	0.237
NO	0.019887	0.026286	0.019935	0.014382	0.038616	0.022671	0.292	0.265
PL	0.018456	0.025430	0.021567	0.011617	0.037381	0.020499	0.295	0.236
PT	0.028067	0.035553	0.025337	0.015658	0.037194	0.022366	0.371	0.302
RO	0.018126	0.024634	0.020331	0.011096	0.034165	0.019085	0.272	0.231
SE	0.022937	0.031042	0.025091	0.015292	0.039950	0.023734	0.252	0.229
SI	0.018136	0.024634	0.020363	0.011100	0.034165	0.019105	0.305	0.254
SK	0.018109	0.024626	0.020316	0.011089	0.034159	0.019075	0.262	0.218

* All estimates per person and per year.

ADHD = Attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder

Data from IHME 2019 (<https://vizhub.healthdata.org/gbd-results/>) and GHO data from WHO 2016

(<https://apps.who.int/gho/data/view.main.BMIPLUS1C05-09v?lang=en>)

Table 10.2 YLDs rates for each health outcome per country from the 2019 GBD study

Country IOS Code	ADHD (5-9 years)	ADHD (10-14 years)	ADHD (15-19 years)	Conduct disorder (5-9 years)	Conduct disorder (10-14 years)	Conduct disorder (15-19 years)
AT	0.000413	0.000520	0.000373	0.001838	0.004351	0.002610
BE	0.000348	0.000437	0.000309	0.001934	0.004553	0.002711
BG	0.000223	0.000302	0.000247	0.001371	0.004211	0.002318
CH	0.000422	0.000534	0.000387	0.001943	0.004558	0.002698
CY	0.000351	0.000440	0.000310	0.001944	0.004568	0.002713
CZ	0.000223	0.000300	0.000249	0.001378	0.004207	0.002320
DE	0.000179	0.000221	0.000149	0.001938	0.004561	0.002722
DK	0.000330	0.000414	0.000295	0.001930	0.004563	0.002706
EE	0.000223	0.000303	0.000249	0.001376	0.004216	0.002321
EL	0.000346	0.000436	0.000308	0.001933	0.004550	0.002699
ES	0.000755	0.000950	0.000689	0.001949	0.004561	0.002703
FI	0.000435	0.000548	0.000396	0.001938	0.004547	0.002702
FR	0.000425	0.000504	0.000332	0.001924	0.004547	0.002693
HR	0.000224	0.000303	0.000247	0.001381	0.004203	0.002314
HU	0.000224	0.000302	0.000250	0.001365	0.004196	0.002318
IE	0.000458	0.000575	0.000418	0.001926	0.004562	0.002687
IS	0.000400	0.000507	0.000360	0.001940	0.004559	0.002698
IT	0.000300	0.000393	0.000297	0.001893	0.004892	0.002861
LT	0.000223	0.000302	0.000248	0.001374	0.004196	0.002321
LU	0.000348	0.000438	0.000311	0.001947	0.004577	0.002703

Country IOS Code	ADHD (5-9 years)	ADHD (10-14 years)	ADHD (15-19 years)	Conduct disorder (5-9 years)	Conduct disorder (10-14 years)	Conduct disorder (15-19 years)
LV	0.000224	0.000304	0.000249	0.001375	0.004204	0.002320
MT	0.000349	0.000439	0.000308	0.001940	0.004571	0.002693
NL	0.000410	0.000518	0.000365	0.001809	0.004367	0.002576
NO	0.000245	0.000322	0.000243	0.001782	0.004726	0.002738
PL	0.000227	0.000312	0.000264	0.001436	0.004598	0.002493
PT	0.000346	0.000436	0.000308	0.001935	0.004538	0.002697
RO	0.000225	0.000304	0.000250	0.001376	0.004190	0.002323
SE	0.000283	0.000382	0.000305	0.001890	0.004889	0.002860
SI	0.000223	0.000303	0.000249	0.001365	0.004200	0.002329
SK	0.000223	0.000304	0.000249	0.001380	0.004210	0.002316

* All estimates per person and per year.

Abbreviations: ADHD = Attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder, YLD = Years of healthy life lost due to disability

Data from IHME 2019 (<https://vizhub.healthdata.org/gbd-results/>)

11 Annex 4 - Number of Children and Adolescents Affected by Multiple Health Outcomes due to Transportation Noise by Country

Table 11.1 Number of children and adolescents (6-17 years) affected by *reading impairment* due to transportation noise above the END threshold (55 dB) in 2021, EEA-31

Country	Cases of reading impairment from road noise	Cases of reading impairment from railway noise	Cases of reading impairment from aircraft noise	Total cases of reading impairment from environmental noise	Public health impact (DALYs/year)
AT	10,310	3,299	105	13,714	178
BE	15,667	2,317	381	18,365	238
BG	5,067	481	5	5,553	72
CH	7,825	793	186	8,804	114
CY	2,229	0	28	2,257	29
CZ	11,435	852	158	12,445	161
DE	78,587	14,707	2,350	95,644	1,245
DK	4,628	110	3	4,741	61
EE	434	19	33	486	5
EL	4,713	518	109	5,340	70
ES	52,656	3,624	510	56,790	738
FI	3,698	539	7	4,244	55
FR	126,987	13,632	2,458	143,077	1,859
HR	3,736	92	0	3,828	50
HU	6,842	1,202	130	8,174	106
IE	6,414	723	53	7,190	94
IS	614	0	6	620	8
IT	42,409	26,349	771	69,529	904
LT	1,458	36	42	1,536	20
LU	2,047	124	267	2,438	31
LV	1,432	161	8	1,601	20
MT	239	0	26	265	3
NL	19,678	1,850	38	21,566	280
NO	3,996	570	93	4,659	60
PL	21,348	2,578	248	24,174	314
PT	3,271	486	383	4,140	53
RO	22,079	1,616	61	23,756	308
SE	9,946	5,466	34	15,446	200
SI	926	218	0	1,144	15
SK	1,698	531	19	2,248	29
Total	472,369	82,893	8,512	563,774	7,329

Table 11.2 Number of children and adolescents (6-17 years) affected by *behavioural problems* due to transportation noise above the END threshold (55 dB) in 2021, EEA-31

Country	Cases of behavioural problems from road noise	Cases of behavioural problems from railway noise	Cases of behavioural problems from aircraft noise	Total cases of behavioural problems from environmental noise	Public health impact (DALYs/year)
AT	1,206	372	10	1,588	89
BE	1,515	225	28	1,768	112
BG	411	44	0	455	31
CH	884	96	17	997	57
CY	314	0	4	318	20
CZ	979	62	10	1,051	72
DE	5,385	1,149	154	6,688	544
DK	493	13	0	506	33
EE	35	2	2	39	2
EL	493	60	9	562	34
ES	10,062	699	71	10,832	474
FI	431	69	0	500	30
FR	15,910	1,555	261	17,726	1,048
HR	308	8	0	316	22
HU	552	96	8	656	44
IE	738	84	5	827	47
IS	66	0	0	66	3
IT	4,615	3,677	62	8,354	566
LT	121	2	2	125	8
LU	256	14	31	301	20
LV	122	7	0	129	8
MT	18	0	2	20	1
NL	2,140	228	3	2,371	136
NO	329	58	7	394	27
PL	1,930	225	17	2,172	154
PT	373	44	30	447	27
RO	1,913	139	4	2,056	142
SE	1,084	587	2	1,673	115
SI	70	16	0	86	7
SK	130	38	2	170	11
Total	52,883	9,569	741	63,193	3,884

Table 11.3 Number of children and adolescents (6-17 years) affected by *overweight* due to transportation noise above the END threshold (55 dB) in 2021, EEA-31

Country	Cases of overweight from road noise	Cases of overweight from railway noise	Cases of overweight from aircraft noise	Total cases of overweight from environmental noise
AT	4,546	1,399	38	5,983
BE	5,520	817	101	6,438
BG	2,283	244	2	2,529
CH	2,631	285	52	2,968
CY	1,595	0	18	1,613
DE	29,636	6,329	843	36,808
DK	1,916	53	1	1,970
EE	138	5	11	154
EL	2,781	342	51	3,174
ES	31,594	2,194	222	34,010
FI	1,542	249	2	1,793
FR	67,140	6,552	1,098	74,790
HR	1,675	46	0	1,721
HU	3,059	536	46	3,641
IE	2,945	341	21	3,307
IS	260	0	2	262
IT	26,473	21,160	356	47,989
LT	494	10	11	515
LU	1,026	54	126	1,206
LV	516	31	2	549
MT	100	0	13	113
NL	7,511	797	13	8,321
NO	1,582	279	31	1,892
PL	9,138	1,060	81	10,279
PT	1,831	218	150	2,199
RO	9,095	665	19	9,779
SE	4,089	2,215	11	6,315
SI	376	87	0	463
SK	598	176	6	780
Total	222,090	46,144	3,327	271,561

12 Annex 5 - Lower and upper confidence of the environmental burden of disease estimation

Table 12.1 Lower and upper 95% confidence interval (CI) for the number of children and adolescents (6-17 years) with behavioural problems and overweight attributable to transportation noise above the *END threshold* (55 dB) in 2021, EEA-31

		Behavioural problems		Overweight	
		Lower CI (RR=1.009)	Upper CI (RR=1.142)	Lower CI (RR=1.007)	Upper CI (RR=1.122)
Inside urban areas	Road	5,442	76,630	20,257	319,661
	Rail	599	8,498	2,378	37,795
	Air	60	952	259	4,203
Outside urban areas	Road	1,436	20,638	5,630	90,147
	Rail	654	9,005	3,037	46,777
	Air	27	437	122	2,017
Total		8,218	116,160	31,683	500,600

Table 12.2 Lower and upper 95% confidence interval (CI) for the number of children and adolescents (6-17 years) with behavioural problems and overweight attributable to transportation noise above the *WHO guideline values* in 2021, EEA-31

		Behavioural problems		Overweight	
		Lower CI (RR=1.009)	Upper CI (RR=1.142)	Lower CI (RR=1.007)	Upper CI (RR=1.122)
Inside urban areas	Road	6,875	96,828	25,598	404,168
	Rail	688	9,732	2,721	43,238
	Air	312	4,516	1,217	19,794
Outside urban areas	Road	1,703	24,413	6,667	106,868
	Rail	675	9,331	3,124	48,135
	Air	193	2,848	797	12,994
Total		10,446	147,668	40,124	635,197

Note: WHO guideline value for road, rail and air are 53 dB, 54 dB, and 45 dB, respectively.

Table 12.3 Lower and upper 95% confidence interval (CI) for the number of children and adolescents (6-17 years) with behavioural problems and overweight attributable to transportation noise above the *Scenario 3 threshold* (45 dB) in 2021, EEA-31

		Behavioural problems		Overweight	
		Lower CI (RR=1.009)	Upper CI (RR=1.142)	Lower CI (RR=1.007)	Upper CI (RR=1.122)
Inside urban areas	Road	10,494	148,007	39,268	620,613
	Rail	1,270	18,034	5,030	80,001
	Air	312	4,516	1,217	19,794
Outside urban areas	Road	3,286	47,357	12,874	207,287
	Rail	985	13,748	4,287	66,908
	Air	193	2,848	797	12,994
Total		16,540	234,510	63,473	1,007,597

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